

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

climes.se/impactsconference

9–11 March

Follow climes on LinkedIn

Uppsala | Sweden

The programme may be subject to change. For the latest updates, please visit www.climes.se/impactsconference

Contents

KEYNOTES.....	8
Adaptation to flood risk in dynamic human-water systems.....	9
Use of individual-level cohort data for climate health research: methodological challenges, barriers, and opportunities.....	10
Governing Transformative Change in Disruptive Times	11
ORALS.....	12
Health I.....	13
Real-Time Forecasting of Weather-induced Healthcare Demand Across Vulnerable Populations In Himachal Pradesh, India	14
Forecasting European heat-related mortality in 2024: data driven vs physics based forecast approaches.....	15
Sudden stratospheric warmings as predictability windows of cold-related mortality in Europe	16
Heat-mortality impacts under 1.5°C overshoot pathways	17
Unprecedented heatwaves and impacts on preterm birth: A storyline approach.....	18
Designing Out Mosquito-borne Disease Transmission: Building and Landscape Environment Strategies for Present and Future Scenarios in Scandinavia and Sub-Saharan Africa.....	19
Energy Systems	20
A method for assessing the comparative risk posed by low- and high-wind extremes for power grids with high offshore wind energy penetration	21
Climate-driven compounding effects and historical trends in renewable electricity droughts in Europe.....	22
Climate Change Impacts on Photovoltaic and Wind Power: Insights from a Convection-Permitting Model Ensemble	23
Mapping LLM-Derived Weather Hazard Database to Outage Reports - Impact on the Swedish Power System	24
Integrating Climate Resilience in Energy Access Planning.....	25
Assessing Power Network Resilience to Catastrophic Medicanes: The Case of Ianos (2020) in Present and Future Climate	26
Societal adaptation I.....	27
Breaking vicious cycles of hydro-climatic disasters and socio-economic inequalities	28
Climate Extremes and Urban Slums: Heatwave Impacts, Social Vulnerabilities, and Community Adaptation in Jaipur.....	29
Who Gets to Stay Cool? Extreme Heat and Social Inequality in Delhi’s Urban Microclimates	30
Working in the heat: Disrupted livelihoods and rising insecurity in urban Ghana	31
A justice approach to climate and environmental disaster risk in Turkey's Kurdish region.....	32

Climate Impacts on the Nordic Riviera: Environmental Justice and Privilege in Coastal Sweden....	33
Health II.....	34
Building a repository of exposure-response functions for climate and health research: a case study in European urban areas.....	35
A data-driven modelling framework for global extrapolation of temperature–mortality relationships in cities	36
Exploring the association between droughts and mortality and the potential mediating role of air pollution on a global scale	37
Air temperature and thrombotic cardiovascular disease in England: a case time series using population-wide electronic health records during the COVID-19 pandemic	38
The short-term effect of multiple heat indicators on birth outcomes in Africa, Europe and Latin America	39
Wildfire in-plume chemistry implications on air quality and health	41
Impact Data I.....	42
Temporal trends, spatial distribution, and co-occurrences of global geocoded shocks (1990–2020)	43
The SHEDIS dataset: Subnational Hazard and Exposure information linked to international DISaster impact records	44
An LLM-Constructed Database of Natural Disasters’ Impacts.....	45
Building a dataset of drought impacts to the water sector using Large Language Models	46
A 50-year natural hazard impact database for Sweden	47
Unveiling the Socio-Economic Footprint of Mediterranean Tropical-Like Cyclones through AI-Driven News Analysis.....	48
Societal Adaptation II.....	49
Navigating Dry Spells: A Scoping Review of Drought-Adaptation Strategies Across the Southern African Development Community	50
Climate adaptation tools under scrutiny: implications for just and sustainable adaptation in the Mediterranean.....	51
Assessing Climate Adaptation Behaviors and Livelihood Strategy Prioritization in Coastal Bangladesh: Evidence from Kalapara Upazila.....	52
Adapting to overheating in UK homes: an empirical evaluation of occupant ventilation and shading behaviour	53
Assessing Societal Response to Extreme Temperature Shocks	54
Do trees in croplands support the heat adaptation of agricultural workers? A quasi-experimental study of natural regeneration effect on human environmental and physiological outcomes.....	55
Foodsystems I	56
Cascading climate extremes in global food supply chains and future food demand.....	57

Swedens food security vulnerability to AMOC collapse	58
Impacts of climate extremes and variability on the reliability of crop yields.....	59
Crop yield response to short-term climatic conditions and cropping system options for adaptation	60
Stratospheric Precursors of European Vegetation Dynamics and Crop Yield	61
Effects of climate change on key winter variables relevant for agriculture	62
Impact Data II.....	63
Climate Risk STAC: A living metadata catalog of geospatial data for assessing climate impacts	64
Multi-Hazard Impacts in EM-DAT—Not Just the Sum of Their Parts?.....	65
A global stocktake of research on the interactions between flood and drought risk	66
Socio-economic impacts of compound drought-heatwave events at a global scale	67
Mapping Resilience to Compound Events in a Global Metropolis: A Case Study of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.....	68
Flood impact assessment across spatial scales: Insights from Bayesian Modelling.....	69
Governance I.....	70
An exploration of the resilience factors that support rural learners to adapt to climate catastrophe stressors	71
Translating Climate Risk to Local Realities – A Case Study of Kenya	72
Building Food Security and Trust in Refugee Settlements under Climate Stress	73
Climate Change Extremes and Coastal Groundwater: Building Urban Water Supply Resilience in the Megacity of Mumbai (India)	74
When the Sea Devours the Land: A case of Climate Passport for Bangladesh’s Sinking Shores.....	75
Living between droughts and floods: unpacking climate extremes from ‘below’ in Western India	76
Foodsystems II	77
When Land Runs Out: Future Cropland Demand Exceeds Regional Arable Supply	78
A case study on forest practitioners’ perspectives on climate extremes: consensus on impacts and conflicts in responses.....	79
Amazon drought sensitivity: geographical patterns in wetland and terrestrial forests.....	80
Climate Extremes in Lakes: Ecological and Socioeconomic Consequences.....	81
Is Volumetric Water Pricing Key to Safeguarding Wetland Ecosystems under Climate Stress?	82
How coupled are soil and vegetation responses to precipitation extremes?	83
Impact Data III.....	84
Multi-decadal analysis of major global risk assessments reveals consistent biases and low predictive capacity	85
European designs for climate-risk insurance systems	86

Bridging climate projections and flood risk: A simple tool to develop storylines of flood impacts under global warming.....	87
Quantifying risks to economic growth from hydroclimate volatility under climate change	88
Linking Emissions from Fossil Fuel Megaprojects to Lifetime Climate Impacts Across Generations	89
Assessing Coastal Dynamics under Climate Stressors: Evidence from UAV, Satellite, and Geophysical Data in Ghana	90
Governance II	91
Explaining Environmental Successes and Failures	92
Bridging Earth System Science and Earth System Governance	93
Climate change impacts: perspectives for a global harmonized law?	94
Conflict, Disasters, and Social Trust: A Cross-national Analysis in Southeast Asia	95
Climate Change Adaptation of the Railway Sector.	96
Unsustainability as Deep Uncertainty: Rethinking Risk Governance for Climate-Extreme Futures.	97
Attribution II.....	98
Is climate change accelerating soil moisture droughts? Evidence from a global attribution analysis.	99
Impact Attribution for Climate Law: The Case of Storm Irene	100
Attribution of aviation impacts during the 3 May 2025 Western Europe hailstorm.....	101
The future of European outdoor summer sports through the lens of 50 years of the Tour de France	102
Impact-Based Seasonal Forecasting of Drought and Extreme Rainfall in Europe	103
Cascading impacts of precipitation variability in North Africa under climate change.	104
Panel on Immobility	105
Climate Change, Aspirations to Stay and Climate Immobility in Mozambique	106
Climate Thresholds and Gendered Immobility: Insights from Ghana's Volta Delta	107
Immobility in the Context of Climate Change.....	108
The Social Production of Immobility in Coastal Sweden: Determinants and Mechanisms in the Context of Sea Level Rise	109
Staying Despite the Storm: Intersectional Immobility and Climate Injustice in the Amazon Coastal Zone	110
POSTERS	111
Societal adaptation and justice dimensions	112
Thailand's Rising Water Budget: The Challenge of Shifting from Reactive Spending to Proactive Climate Adaptation via the National Adaptation Plan (NAP)	113
Climate Change, Cattle Violence and State Politics in Ghana.....	114

Bridging Climate Adaptation Gaps through Fiscal Policy Framework for Agricultural Resilience in Northeastern Bangladesh	115
Just Adaptation in German Cities? Assessing Social Justice Dimensions in Urban Climate Adaptation Strategies	116
Reengineering Resilience: A Justice-Centered Framework for Climate-Resilient Public-Private Partnerships in Flood-Prone Urban Africa	117
Intersections of Ethnicity, Sense of Belonging, and Climate Displacement: How Generation Z Adapts to Rising Sea Levels in the Global South	118
Gender Roles' Influence On Implementation And Outcomes Of Gender Equality Policies On Climate Adaptation In Kenya	119
Governance, policy and society mediating impacts	120
Media, Metaphors, and Environmental Security: How Language Shapes the Climate Crisis.....	121
Profiling Climate-Change Leanings in Large Language Models	122
Assessing Heat Mitigation Potential from Green Transit-Oriented Development: A Case Study in Thu Duc District, Ho Chi Minh City.....	123
Resources in Dispute: Rethinking Circularity in an Age of Climate Extremes.....	124
Emotional Responses to Drought in the Western Cape News Media	125
Foodsystems, crops, and ecosystem impacts	126
Farm-level economic impacts of climate change adaptations in cropping systems across Sweden	127
Socio-Economic Impacts of Energy Transition in the Agriculture Sector of India	128
Climate Extremes Driven Shifts in Crop Seasonality and Livelihood Vulnerability: A Case Study of Semi-Arid Rajasthan.....	129
Health and healthcare impacts	130
Effect of air pollution on pregnancy outcome	131
Wildfires and Birth Outcomes:Evidence from Spain.....	132
Flood Impacts on Healthcare Access and Social Vulnerability in Germany.....	133
Impact of Heatwaves on Health: A Multicentric Retrospective Observational Study on Morbidity, Hospitalizations, and Mortality Patterns	134
Climatic Drivers of Malaria risk in Children Under Five: A Large-Scale Analysis of individual-level data for 350,000 children in 26 Sub-Saharan African Countries	135
Impact of temperature extremes on school going children's health in Sweden.....	137
The impact of compound hydroclimate extremes on population health.....	138
Degrees of inequality: How educational attainment shapes mortality associated to non-optimal temperatures in different provinces of Belgium	139
Temporal structure of the impact of meteorological conditions on pneumonia hospitalizations in Germany.....	140

Predicting mortality during heatwaves through the application of machine learning on large register data.....	142
Exploring perceptions of heat risk and user-experience of a heat-Early Warning System (EWS) app for pregnant women and mothers in Sweden: A mixed-methods study	143
A time series analysis of temperature and mortality in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina	144
Identifying and Modelling Pathways between Flood and Health in Vietnam	145
Impact: data, modelling, and overviews.....	146
Towards improved modelling of windstorm damage risk through Impact Model calibration.....	147
Shape-constrained exposure-response functions for modelling the impacts of climate extremes in small populations.....	148
Compounding impacts of climate change and urbanisation on water-energy-food Nexus in global south countries	149
Quantifying the rarity behind European loss-causing floods: a precipitation-frequency framework	150
A social science typology of climate change storylines	151
Evaluating Microclimatic Impacts of Citywide Rooftop Photovoltaic Deployment Using WRF and a Multilayer Urban Canopy Model: Evidence from Sendai, Japan	152
Wikimpacts 1.0: A new global climate impact database based on automated information extraction from Wikipedia	153
Challenges and Opportunities for Understanding Societal Impacts of Climate Extremes	154
Energy system impacts	155
Storylines of future summertime renewable electricity droughts in Europe under climate warming and rising air conditioning demand	156
Investigation of meteorological conditions leading to extreme variable renewable energy shortage events in Germany	157
Power consumption and carbon footprint of open warming beds and closed incubators.....	158
Climate attribution, forecasting, monitoring, and projections.....	159
AI-Driven Monitoring and Forecasting of Marine Mucilage: A Climate Impact Case from the Marmara Sea.....	160
Assessing Power Network Resilience to Catastrophic Medicanes: The Case of Ianos (2020) in Present and Future Climate	161
Analyzing Rainfall Patterns and Intensity in Bangkok Using GNSS-Derived PWV and Meteorological Observations.....	162
Sensitivity of Extreme Precipitation to Warming in a Global Storm-Resolving Model.....	163
Evaluating ERA5 Precipitable Water Vapor and Its Application to Drought Monitoring through the SPCI over Thailand	164
Projected Changes in Extreme Precipitation from CMIP6 in the Mae Klong River Basin, Thailand.....	165

Consecutive hot and dry events: a compound event attribution study	166
Uncertainty Quantification of the regional temperature consequences of a large AMOC decrease	167
Building Climate Resilience through Urban Climate Analysis. Case study: Galanta (Slovakia).....	168
Future Water Dynamics of the Nitra River Basin under Climate Change and Land Use Scenarios	169
Groundwater on the Edge: How Climate Warming and Urban Growth are Reshaping Bihar's Water Future.....	170
Characterization of aviation turbulence associated with Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones (Medicanes)	171
Assessing the real-world economic value of weather forecasts under compounding extremes...	172

KEYNOTES

Adaptation to flood risk in dynamic human-water systems

Heidi Kreibich

GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany

Abstract

Effective adaptation to flood risk is increasingly critical as flood-related losses continue to rise. However, societies face inherent limits to their adaptive capacity. Social vulnerability factors—such as low income levels or advanced age—can constrain households' ability to implement private precautionary measures, thereby increasing the physical vulnerability of their buildings. Consequently, adaptation strategies must be grounded in risk assessments that explicitly account for the dynamics, complex interactions, and feedback mechanisms within human–water systems. Integrating human behaviour into dynamic flood risk assessments poses a significant challenge, particularly given the already high levels of uncertainty involved. Recent advances in this field include the collection and analysis of comprehensive qualitative and quantitative data on changes in flood risk using the paired-event concept in case studies and the development of probabilistic flood loss models based on Bayesian networks. Probabilistic flood loss models offer a key advantage in that they can capture temporal changes in vulnerability while inherently providing quantitative estimates of predictive uncertainty. Further development of these approaches is therefore recommended, including the application of more dynamic modelling techniques in large-scale flood risk analyses. In addition, quantitative assessments of both the potential and the limits of flood adaptation, considering underlying vulnerability drivers, are needed. Such insights are essential for effectively prioritizing adaptation investments.

Use of individual-level cohort data for climate health research: methodological challenges, barriers, and opportunities

Antonio Gasparrini

The London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

Traditionally, research on the health impacts of climate change has relied on aggregated, population-level administrative data. While valuable for large-scale analyses, these resources remain limited for addressing more refined aetiological questions and for defining targeted public health interventions. Recent advances in exposure assessment and data linkage now enable the integration of high-resolution environmental data with individual-level cohort studies. This talk will explore the novel research opportunities created by this shift, alongside the methodological challenges and practical barriers to implementation in climate and health science.

Governing Transformative Change in Disruptive Times

Björn-Ola Linnér

Centre for Climate Science and Policy Research, Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden

Abstract

Calls for transformative change now permeate climate and biodiversity agendas, but how societal transformations occur around the world – their drivers and how they can be governed – remain contested. This keynote draws on recent work from the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment to synthesise six overarching approaches to how transformative change occurs – systems, structural, empowerment, inner transformation, knowledge co-creation, and science-and-technology approaches – and examines what they imply for climate governance as societies confront increasingly uneven, cascading, and disruptive climate change impacts. The talk addresses how these perspectives illuminate different leverage points for reconfiguring views, structures, and practices, and how weaving them together can expand the repertoire of governance strategies available to address planetary change. By foregrounding epistemic and methodological pluralism, justice, and power, the keynote outlines how transformative governance can support decarbonisation pathways and climate-resilient futures.

ORALS

Health and healthcare impacts I

Real-Time Forecasting of Weather-induced Healthcare Demand Across Vulnerable Populations In Himachal Pradesh, India

Claudia Offner^{1,2}, Paul Kattuman³, Hua Lu¹, Matthew Osman², Andrew Orr¹, Philip Bett⁴

¹British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ²University of Cambridge – Department of Geography, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ³University of Cambridge – Judge Business School, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ⁴Met Office, Exeter, United Kingdom

Abstract

Extreme weather is becoming more frequent and severe due to climate change, placing increasing pressure on healthcare systems—particularly in climate-vulnerable countries like India, where about 25% of accidental deaths are weather-related. Mountainous regions such as Himachal Pradesh face heightened risks due to rapidly shifting climate patterns and challenging terrain, and the effects are not uniform across age groups and genders. Here, we combine daily resolved BigThaw (~5km) reanalysis meteorological data (temperature, rainfall, and relative humidity) with a unique database of patient admissions from 12 Himachal Pradesh healthcare facilities (2015-2023) to forecast daily, weather-induced hospital admissions over a seven-day predictive-horizon. Using a two-stage analytical approach, we first identified local, impact-based definitions of extreme weather with Distributed Lag Non-linear Models (DLNMs), which we then applied to novel Time Series Growth Curve (TSGC) models to assess disaggregated impacts across vulnerable populations and facility capacities. Our preliminary findings – validated using out-of-sample historical data – suggest that cold events are the strongest predictor of increased next-day registrations, especially amongst women and young children in paediatric and ENT wards. We demonstrate that DLNM and TSGC models can improve real-time forecasting of weather-related healthcare demand across vulnerable groups in high-risk regions, aiding in timely and targeted healthcare responses. Predicting localised and population-specific healthcare demand in response to extreme weather is vital to advancing India's progress toward Sustainable Development Goals 3 (Good Health and Well-being) and 13 (Climate Action).

Forecasting European heat-related mortality in 2024: data driven vs physics based forecast approaches

Emma Holmberg^{1,2}, Leonardo Olivetti^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Heat has emerged as a major public health concern. Over 62,000 heat-related deaths were estimated to have occurred during the European summer of 2024, exemplifying the pressing need to develop effective early warning systems. Such systems depend critically on the quality of the underlying forecasts, and recent work has focused on developing impact-based forecasts for heat-related mortality, which provide explicitly impact-oriented information. To date, heat-related mortality forecasts have been based on the output of numerical weather prediction models, or physics-based forecasts. The field of weather forecasting is undergoing a rapid transformation with the advent of skillful data-driven forecasts. This case study compares European heat-related mortality forecasts for 2024 based on physics-based weather forecasts with those based on data-driven weather forecasts. Our results highlight the non-linear relationship between temperature and mortality, and the sensitivity of forecasts to errors at high temperatures, although the generalisability of our results is hampered by the small sample size. The targeted improvement of forecast models for high temperatures would be particularly beneficial for heat-related mortality forecasting, and we suggest the application of this approach to both data-driven and physics-based forecast ensembles as an important next step in the continued development of informative, explicitly impact oriented forecasts.

Sudden stratospheric warmings as predictability windows of cold-related mortality in Europe

Michael Schutte^{1,2}, Emma Holmberg^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Sudden stratospheric warmings (SSWs) are major disruptions of the stratospheric polar vortex that can substantially alter tropospheric circulation. Their occurrence often increases the likelihood of persistent atmospheric blocking patterns over Europe, leading to colder-than-usual surface temperatures. These events therefore represent both windows of opportunity for extended-range prediction and periods of elevated risk for cold-related societal impacts.

We investigate the relationship between SSWs, surface temperature anomalies across Europe, and the associated cold-related mortality. Using reanalysis data, sub-seasonal to seasonal forecasts, and mortality data, we assess how the predictability of SSWs translates into potential foresight of cold-related health outcomes. First, we quantify the statistical association between SSWs and cold-related mortality across different European regions. A detailed case study then examines attribution and predictability for a recent, well-documented SSW event.

By linking stratospheric dynamics, surface climate hazards, and impacts on human health, this work highlights the potential for integrated climate-health early warning systems. The findings contribute to ongoing discussions on how enhanced atmospheric predictability can inform preparedness and reduce vulnerability to climate extremes in a changing world.

Heat-mortality impacts under 1.5°C overshoot pathways

Samuel Lüthi¹, Mireia Ginesta², Ana Vicedo-Cabrera¹, Rupert Stuart-Smith²

¹University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ²University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

Abstract

The risk of heat-related mortality is rapidly increasing as our planet continues to heat. With this continued warming, it has become highly likely that the world will experience a time of temperature overshoot, before reaching the Paris Agreement's goal of limiting long-term warming to 1.5°C.

In this study we therefore explore the increase of heat-related mortality when overshooting the 1.5°C target by combining climate model output with a well-established epidemiological model. The epidemiological analysis relies on quasi-Poisson regression time series analyses and requires daily city-level mortality data. We can access mortality data for more than 850 locations across 52 countries through the MCC (Multi-Country Multi-City) database and subsequently establish location specific temperature-mortality relationships.

We then project heat-related mortality levels across all 540 Paris Agreement-aligned scenarios available in the IPCC AR6 Scenario Database. To this end, we estimate local heat-mortality impacts for each location as a function of global mean surface temperature, by sampling climate data from large ensembles. Additionally, we validate our approach using bespoke climate model simulations that represent physically consistent overshoot and stabilization pathways.

We find that both, the length and intensity of the overshoot is relevant for heat-mortality, as the impacts increase linearly with overshoot-degree-years as compared to no-overshoot scenarios. At the same time, we can highlight that AR6 scenarios with lower future CO₂ emissions have a lower burden of heat-mortality. Our results lay an important foundation for law and policy makers, as they explicitly state that delaying climate action leads to increased heat-mortality.

Unprecedented heatwaves and impacts on preterm birth: A storyline approach

Ricardo Berenguer Navarro^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{2,3}, Jette Möller¹, Maria Rusca⁴, Elena Raffetti^{1,2,3}

¹Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁴Global Development Institute, University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

Abstract

Public health has assessed future climate-related health risks by analysing retrospective epidemiological data and then applying climate projections to estimate how risks evolve. This approach has informed policy but is limited in changing climates. It assumes a static population vulnerability and does not account for determinants such as adaptation. As a result, it can mischaracterise future risk, particularly under more frequent and intense climate extremes.

To address this gap, we propose a novel methodology for developing context-specific scenarios, integrating potential adaptation measures. This approach extends physical climate storylines by Shepherd to encompass societal and population health impacts. We use exposure to extreme heat and risk of preterm birth as a case study.

The proposed methodology integrates:

- Historical and Future Climate Data: Integrate historical climate observations with numerical projections to construct geographically specific extreme heat scenarios.
- Analysis of Past Heat Extremes: Examine retrospective associations between extreme heat and preterm birth within same regions to establish exposure-outcome associations.
- Cross-Contextual Analysis: Compare heat–health relationships across regions and event magnitudes, adapting scenarios conceptually to reflect local contexts.
- Adaptation: Incorporate adaptation strategies and socio-political determinants to model levels of preparedness, response, and resilience.
- Simulations: Translate narrative and conceptual scenarios into quantitative estimates through microsimulation or equivalent models, enabling dynamic exploration of future risks and the potential impacts of interventions.

This quantitative–qualitative framework produces future scenarios that capture measurable health risk and the social processes that shape vulnerability and adaptation. It is designed to support decision-making in public health planning and climate adaptation.

Designing Out Mosquito-borne Disease Transmission: Building and Landscape Environment Strategies for Present and Future Scenarios in Scandinavia and Sub-Saharan Africa

Otis Sloan Wood¹, Eliza Lupenza², Jakob Brandberg Knudsen¹, Karin Linda Schiøler³, Fatma Saleh⁴

¹Royal Danish Academy, Copenhagen, Denmark. ²Kilimanjaro Christian Medical University College, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania, United Republic of. ³University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. ⁴The State University of Zanzibar, Zanzibar City, Tanzania, United Republic of

Abstract

Urbanisation, climate change, and global trade are rapidly expanding the habitats of disease-carrying mosquitoes across Europe. *Aedes albopictus*, a vector for diseases such as Zika and dengue was detected in Sweden in 2023 and large regions of the country and much of Europe as projected to become climatically suitable for this mosquito by 2050. With universal vaccines remaining limited and increasing concerns regarding the overuse of insecticides, there is a pressing need for sustainable, preventative strategies such as designing the built environment to prevent mosquito breeding and reduce human-mosquito contact.

This paper presents ongoing work from the MBD-Free project, which is co-creating building and landscape interventions with stakeholders and end users at four hospital sites in Zanzibar, an area where mosquito-borne diseases are endemic. These interventions aim to reduce disease transmission risk through adaptations to the building, surrounding landscape and how it is managed and runs parallel to similar initiatives within Sub-Saharan Africa using design as a preventative approach.

We examine emerging risks of mosquito-borne disease transmission in northern European cities, using Copenhagen as a case study under future climate scenarios, and highlight the growing burden of these diseases in endemic regions of sub-Saharan Africa, where significant construction is anticipated in the coming decades. Drawing on lessons from the MBD-Free Project, we identify critical knowledge gaps and opportunities for cross-regional learning and interdisciplinary collaboration as these territories address new public health challenges resulting from expanding mosquito habitats. The MBD-Free Project is funded by Danida.

Energy system impacts

A method for assessing the comparative risk posed by low- and high-wind extremes for power grids with high offshore wind energy penetration

Geoffrey De Sena^{1,2}, Samuel Forsberg^{1,2}, Mikael Bergkvist^{1,2}, Malin Götteman^{1,2}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Increasing variable renewable energy penetration poses a risk for electricity grids that have traditionally been designed and operated to provide electricity on-demand. Offshore wind farms pose a particular risk in that relatively uniform wind conditions can lead to the loss of production on the scale of large conventional power plants. Both low- and high-wind conditions can cause loss of production, but the risk of loss of production differs between the two scenarios.

We present a method for assessing the risk posed by low- and high-wind conditions with the aid of long-term reanalysis meteorology data and optimum power flow (OPF) simulations.

From an initial investigation into the comparative risks associated with low- and high-wind extremes, we present metrics for assessing the severity of the impacts of extreme weather on the system. We apply established extreme value theory methods for estimating the probabilities of certain wind extremes to arise at a given project location. We also propose a lightweight model of wind farm production. We use a case study to show how OPF simulations can be used to estimate the probability and severity of disruptions due to low wind power production. Finally, we show how these probabilities and impacts can be combined to assess the risk of low- vs. high-wind extremes to power grids.

Given the limited resources available for adapting the power system to changing production patterns, this work enables better understanding of the comparative risks posed by wind speeds at both the lower and upper extremes.

Climate-driven compounding effects and historical trends in renewable electricity droughts in Europe

Yu Meng^{1,2}, Johannes Schmidt³, Jakob Zscheischler^{1,2}, Emanuele Bevacqua¹

¹Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Leipzig, Germany. ²TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany. ³University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

Abstract

In the interconnected European power system, renewable electricity droughts (REDs)—periods of unmet demand by renewables—may be triggered by weather-driven compounding effects of high demand and low renewable generation, particularly when simultaneous REDs compound across multiple regions. Yet, our understanding of such compounding effects and historical trends in REDs, remains limited. We study REDs using weekly electricity data from 1941 to 2023 derived via the PyPSA-Eur framework, focusing on the season most affected by REDs and, to isolate climate-driven impacts, assuming fixed present-day installed generation capacities. Across nine European macro-regions, each comprising highly interconnected small-scale areas, REDs are mainly driven by wind generation and demand, with prominent compounding effects in central Europe, Italy, and across the UK and Ireland. Wind-demand correlations enhance REDs in central and northern Europe but weaken them in the south. Furthermore, macro-regional REDs primarily occur due to simultaneous REDs in small-scale areas. In an increasingly interconnected continental power system, we find that correlations between residual loads of macro-regions increase the probability of simultaneous macro-regional REDs, ultimately intensifying Europe-wide REDs by 40 % on average compared to a scenario without correlations. Finally, we assess weather-driven trends in REDs, finding that increasing temperatures lowered winter heating demand and thus reduced RED frequency, while changes in correlations between demand and generation sources, along with between residual loads across macro-regions, amplified Europe-wide RED risk. This research underscores the importance of considering compound effects between demand and generation across regions, along with long-term climate change, to optimize power systems.

Climate Change Impacts on Photovoltaic and Wind Power: Insights from a Convection-Permitting Model Ensemble

Milan Mathew¹, Giorgia Fosser¹, Xiaoli Guo², Sara Müller²

¹University School for Advanced Studies IUSS, Pavia, Pavia, Italy. ²Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark

Abstract

Renewable energy is essential for decarbonising the power sector, one of the largest sources of greenhouse-gas emissions. However, solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind generation are intrinsically linked to atmospheric conditions and therefore vulnerable to climate change. To quantify these vulnerabilities, we analyse an ensemble of 14 convection-permitting climate models (CPMs) from the CORDEX-FPSCONV project (Coppola et al., 2020). Unlike conventional climate models, CPMs explicitly resolve deep convection, yielding improved representations of heavy precipitation, near-surface winds, orographic effects, and land-sea interactions (Fosser et al., 2024; Belušić & Lind, 2025; Molina et al., 2024).

We leverage climate projections from the CPM ensemble to assess changes in PV and wind resources toward the end of the century under the IPCC's RCP8.5 scenario. For southern Europe, particularly Italy, CPM output indicates that surface shortwave radiation may increase by up to 5 %, but concurrent rises in surface air temperature offset this gain by reducing PV cell efficiency, resulting in overall unchanged or slightly declining PV potential.

For wind energy we examine changes in both strong-wind and weak-wind extremes and their implications for generation variability. The CPM ensemble reveals modest shifts in extreme-wind frequency, with regional differences that could affect reliability and dispatch planning.

These results highlight the added value of high-resolution, convection-permitting simulations for assessing future changes in renewable energy generation potential and underscore the need to incorporate such ensembles into energy system planning under severe climate change scenarios.

Mapping LLM-Derived Weather Hazard Database to Outage Reports - Impact on the Swedish Power System

Sanja Duvnjak Zarkovic^{1,2}, Murathan Kurfali^{3,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden. ³RISE, Stockholm, Sweden
Abstract

Modern power systems are facing rising disruption from weather and climate extremes. This study quantifies and explains weather-related electricity outages in Sweden by combining utility outage reports obtained from Energiföretagen Sverige (2007–2021) with a hazard database generated by a large language model (LLM) from Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) narratives. Using Power BI to merge, explore, and visualize the data, we map spatial and temporal patterns and measure how multiple hazards, such as wind, lightning, rain, snow, ice, snow- and wind-induced treefall, contribute to grid disruptions. The dataset covers more than 220,000 weather-related outages, enabling consistent cross-hazard comparisons and utility-focused metrics on event frequency and outage burden. We show how the LLM pipeline turns unstructured weather text into structured, searchable events that, linked to outage records, produce actionable insights for planning and operations. Results reveal clear seasonal and regional risk profiles, identify compound-hazard conditions tied to higher outage counts and durations, and pinpoint locations where targeted measures, such as vegetation management, hardening of overhead lines, and weather-aware maintenance scheduling, can most effectively reduce customer impact. The methodology offers a scalable decision-support framework to prioritize resilience investments and anticipate outage risks under a changing climate.

Integrating Climate Resilience in Energy Access Planning

Daniel Adshead¹, Scott Thacker², Raghav Pant², Jim Hall², Francesco Fuso Nerini¹

¹KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden. ²University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

Abstract

As climate change intensifies, energy planning frameworks must evolve to incorporate not only cost-efficiency, but also long-term climate resilience. Current approaches to electrification and clean cooking often prioritize least-cost solutions without fully accounting for the spatial distribution of physical risks posed by hazards such as floods, droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires. We emphasize the importance of embedding climate risk considerations into energy access planning, particularly in regions like sub-Saharan Africa where infrastructure gaps and climate vulnerability acutely intersect. Using spatial overlays of representative climate hazard scenarios on modelled outputs from geospatial electrification and clean cooking planning tools, we illustrate how exposure to climate extremes varies across energy technologies and geographies. This demonstrates that many energy access investments, including decentralized solutions like mini-grids and LPG cooking solutions, may be deployed without sufficient attention to their long-term reliability under climate stress. This signals an urgent need to embed resilience measures in existing planning tools and strategies.

Assessing Power Network Resilience to Catastrophic Medicanes: The Case of Ianos (2020) in Present and Future Climate

Emmanouil Flaounas^{1,2}, Zacharias fasoulakis³, Dimitrios V. Bilonis³, Dimitrios Vamvatsikos³

¹ETH, Zurich, Switzerland. ²HCMR, Athens, Greece. ³Institute of Steel Structures, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

Abstract

Catastrophic Medicanes—Mediterranean hurricanes—are among the most destructive environmental hazards in the region. Despite their smaller size, relative to tropical cyclones, they can reach comparable intensities, producing severe windstorms that inflict substantial socioeconomic impacts, especially on critical infrastructure.

This study focuses on the case of Mediane Ianos (2020), which caused widespread power outages across western Greece. Our aim is to evaluate the resilience of the electrical power network with emphasis on damage to distribution poles. High-resolution atmospheric modeling is used to simulate Ianos' wind-gust footprint while stochastic risk methods are used to assess structural vulnerability and cascading effects on the grid. To probe climate-change implications, we conduct a sensitivity experiment in which sea-surface temperatures are increased, thereby emulating a warmer Mediterranean Sea. The resulting changes in wind intensity and spatial damage probabilities enable us to quantify Ianos' potential future impacts under warmer SSTs.

Using the Greek power grid as a case study, we demonstrate that Medicanes—projected to intensify with SST warming—pose an increasing risks to energy infrastructure. The work proposes a transferable framework for assessing power-network vulnerability to extreme wind events, offering insights applicable to other Mediterranean countries confronting the growing threat of Medicanes.

Societal adaptation and justice dimensions I

Breaking vicious cycles of hydro-climatic disasters and socio-economic inequalities

Giuliano Di Baldassarre¹, Mariana de Brito², Sara Lindersson¹, Frederike Albrecht³, Maria Rusca⁴

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²UFZ Leipzig, Leipzig, Germany. ³FHS, Stockholm, Sweden.

⁴University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

Abstract

Floods and drought events often worsen socio-economic inequalities, as marginalized groups face disproportionate impacts and have fewer resources to recover. Inequalities, in turn, limit their ability to recover, and amplify the impacts of future hydro-climatic extremes, creating vicious cycles of worsening disasters. Yet, such floods and drought events can also serve as opportunities for transformative change addressing underlying vulnerabilities and reducing inequalities. Progress in sociohydrology has been essential for better understanding these two-way interactions, requiring case studies and models of human-water systems that account for uneven risk distribution, along with global comparative analyses using emerging datasets. This presentation proposes an interdisciplinary research agenda combining sociohydrological modelling, critical social science perspectives on power and inequality, and the innovative, but carefully scrutinized, use of AI tools, such as text mining. This integrated approach can reveal context-specific dynamics, and help break vicious cycles of disasters and inequalities.

Climate Extremes and Urban Slums: Heatwave Impacts, Social Vulnerabilities, and Community Adaptation in Jaipur

Vandana Choudhary, Milap Punia

Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, Delhi, India

Abstract

According to the MHF&WD of Rajasthan, a total of 6,069 heat stroke cases were reported in 2024, reflecting the severe health implications of extreme temperatures in the state. This raises critical questions of who is being impacted, why certain groups are more vulnerable, and how they cope with such climate extremes. Slum populations, already burdened by livelihood insecurity and inequality, are disproportionately exposed to climate extremes impacts. This study was undertaken during the summer months of 2024 with two objectives: first, to assess the impacts of heatwaves and the associated vulnerabilities in the slums of Jaipur city; and second, to explore the adaptive strategies, key challenges and propose pathways for policy interventions. Personal interviews and FGDs were conducted with residents of five slum settlements, alongside interactions with institutional stakeholders. Heatwaves severely affect community health, water resources, and livelihoods, with disproportionate impacts on vulnerable groups such as pregnant women, children, the elderly, and women, leading to unreported deaths. The adaptive capacity is categorised in generic and specific strategies, supported by a SWOT-based assessment of policy and field realities. The findings underscore the persistent vulnerability of marginalized populations, challenging the current policy emphasis on resilience-building without adequately addressing underlying vulnerabilities. The study argues that true resilience requires inclusive strategies addressing structural vulnerabilities of marginalized communities, beyond narrow adaptive capacities. By identifying who is most affected, how, and why, such studies can inform long-term transformative solutions that address both climate change vulnerabilities and entrenched social inequalities.

Who Gets to Stay Cool? Extreme Heat and Social Inequality in Delhi's Urban Microclimates

Ravindra Singh, Milap Punia

Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, Delhi, India

Abstract

Extreme heat events are becoming one of the most severe climate impacts in rapidly urbanising regions. In cities of the Global South, high population density and social inequality amplify exposure to heat extremes while limiting adaptation capacity. In Delhi—where summer temperatures now exceed 49°C—understanding how environmental and governance factors shape access to cooling is critical for effective adaptation.

Paradoxically, Delhi's total green cover has increased over the past three decades and now accounts for nearly 25% of the city's area, earning it the label of India's "green capital." Yet the benefits of this greenery are distributed unevenly across neighbourhoods. Using a spatial modelling approach (InVEST Urban Cooling Model) that integrates vegetation cover, water, built density, etc, as key physical variables influencing local temperature, this study combines model outputs with neighbourhood-level socio-economic data.

The analysis shows that wealthier areas have cooler microclimates because they have more green infrastructure, while low-income communities are often stuck in areas that are more exposed to heat. These spatial inequalities are further reinforced by urban governance practices that dictate who can access and manage green spaces. Field observations show that neighbourhood community park managers and technocratic planning often restrict access to public green areas and prioritise aesthetic projects that displace vulnerable people. These institutional patterns, reinforced by elite governance, deepen heat-related vulnerabilities and limit adaptive capacity.

By linking Delhi's green paradox to climate adaptation equity, the study reframes unequal cooling as an *adaptation deficit* that undermines fair and effective responses to extreme heat.

Working in the heat: Disrupted livelihoods and rising insecurity in urban Ghana

Katherine Gough¹, Ebenezer Amankwaa²

¹Department of Human Geography, Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ²Department of Human Geography and Resource Development, University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana

Abstract

Cities across sub-Saharan Africa are increasingly experiencing extreme weather events, which disproportionately affect the urban poor. Focussing on severe heat, this paper discusses the impact working in high temperatures is having on residents of low-income urban communities in Ghana. Temperature data recorded in homes and workplaces are linked to qualitative interview data collected in eight neighbourhoods within the cities of Accra and Tamale. The data reveal the high indoor temperatures experienced and how extreme heat events are impacting vulnerable populations through disrupting their livelihood activities. Lower productivity, loss of goods, restricted mobility and poorer health are resulting in reduced incomes. Although numerous coping strategies are adopted, including working extended hours, seeking cooler spaces, moving around at cooler times of the day, and making minor modifications to structures to try to reduce indoor temperatures, the impact of extreme heat on livelihoods is still severe. Urban residents' ability to adopt coping strategies that reduce the temperatures they experience while working varies, hence livelihood insecurity is likely to increase as temperatures continue to rise.

A justice approach to climate and environmental disaster risk in Turkey's Kurdish region

Suanne M. Segovia-Tzompa^{1,2}, Nisan Alici³

¹Swedish Defence University, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science, Uppsala, Sweden. ³University of Derby, Derby, United Kingdom

Abstract

This paper uses a justice approach to analyse novel data and to reanalyse existing information about disaster preparedness and recovery in the Turkish Kurdish region. The paper builds upon disaster justice, a burgeoning subfield of disaster risk management. It also offers an interdisciplinary approach to analysing disasters in complex contexts, as the Kurdish region, where disasters are deeply linked to both natural hazards and human-induced risks originating from ethnic-related conflicts.

We structure the paper in five sections. Section one provides an overview of the Turkish context concerning disasters, from climatic and natural hazards to induced risks. Section two continues by reviewing the state of the art of disaster research in Turkey, paying closer attention to the Kurdish region from a justice perspective. Section three contains the data analysis, in which the authors provide novel data on the perceptions of local stakeholders concerning disaster management. Section four discusses these perceptions in attention to current disaster studies and in light of the new justice subfield, providing an alternative view on how disasters could have intensified injustices and inequalities on the one hand, and exploring how disaster risk management can improve its effectiveness through a justice approach, from reimagining the conceptualisation of vulnerability, adaptation and loss & damage, to promoting more inclusive and integrated forms of governance. In the fifth and last section, we summarise the findings and emphasise the importance of these findings for the current transitions in the region.

Climate Impacts on the Nordic Riviera: Environmental Justice and Privilege in Coastal Sweden

Emilia Ganslandt^{1,2}

¹Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies (LUCSUS), Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Climate Extremes (climes), Lund, Sweden

Abstract

In many high-income countries, living on the coast is considered a luxury. Yet, as climate change intensifies, this privilege is increasingly becoming a liability due to sea-level rise, storms, and coastal erosion. Climate adaptation strategies such as sea walls can be employed to protect communities, but they can also have social and environmental impacts. They can also raise environmental justice questions such as what climate adaptation should protect and who should pay for it.

This study examines how the construction of a sea wall in Skanör-Falsterbo, Southern Sweden—colloquially known as the “Nordic Riviera”—is experienced, understood, and contested. Drawing on 19 semi-structured interviews with residents, it explores how climate adaptation becomes a site where privilege and justice are negotiated and contested. The analysis highlights tensions around what it means to receive protection and why those who have been afforded such protection may still resist or contest it.

By unpacking local perspectives of climate adaptation in an affluent coastal context, this research offers insights into the complexities of adaptation and technical solutions to climate change. These findings contribute to broader debates on climate adaptation and environmental justice, emphasizing the need to “study up” within the field of adaptation.

Health and healthcare im pacts II

Building a repository of exposure-response functions for climate and health research: a case study in European urban areas

Pierre Masselot, Malcolm Mistry, Antonio Gasparriani

London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

With the climate crisis accelerating, it becomes important to understand the health impacts of climate change, notably through increased exposure to environmental stressors. This objective is pursued by various types of studies, in particular health impact assessments that estimate the burden related to an exposure, projections studies which estimate how the burden would evolve under future climate change scenarios and attribution studies that link the burden to anthropogenic climate change. All these studies rely on the accuracy of exposure-response functions (ERF), that are estimated from complex epidemiological studies necessitating large health outcome databases. In this contribution, we aim to show how we built a comprehensive repository of ERFs for temperature-related mortality across 854 European urban areas, allowing the research community to build upon our work for climate and health research. We illustrate the usefulness of this approach through the use of this repository to estimate the mortality burden of temperature in Europe, evaluate the net effect of climate change on temperature-related mortality, assess local greenness policies and assess the role played by climate change in recent heat waves. These ERFs are made publicly available through a Zenodo repository allowing its wide use.

A data-driven modelling framework for global extrapolation of temperature–mortality relationships in cities

Huiqi Chen¹, Malcolm Mistry¹, Francesco Sera², Pierre Masselot¹, Antonio Gasparrini¹

¹London school of hygiene and tropical medicine, London, United Kingdom. ²University of Florence, Florence, Italy

Abstract

Background

Quantifying temperature-related mortality globally is challenging due to limited amounts of health outcome data in some regions, especially in low- and middle-income settings. This study develops a framework to estimate temperature–mortality relationships globally by integrating large-scale climate, demographic, and socioeconomic data with advanced statistical modelling.

Methods

We analysed daily time series data from 848 cities in the Multi-Country Multi-City (MCC) Network (2000–2019) to estimate city-specific exposure-response functions using distributed lag non-linear models (DLNMs). We then pooled them in a meta-regression model with the goal to predict exposure-response functions for 11,422 cities worldwide from the Global Human Settlement Urban Centre Database. To improve prediction, the model incorporated environmental and socioeconomic factors, population demographics, and urban characteristics, through partial least squares (PLS) regression to handle this large number of meta-predictors.

Findings

We selected six PLS components that optimized model performance while minimizing residual heterogeneity. Across 11,422 urban areas worldwide, cold- and heat-related mortality risks at the 1st and 99th percentiles versus minimum mortality temperature (MMP) exhibited substantial spatial variability, with interquartile range of risks spanning 1.17–1.25 for cold-related mortality and 1.03–1.09 for heat-related mortality.

Interpretation

This study provides a data-driven and reproducible framework for estimating temperature-related mortality risks in data-scarce regions. The approach supports global assessments of climate-related health impacts, the design of targeted adaptation strategies, and can be built upon for future climate and health research.

Exploring the association between droughts and mortality and the potential mediating role of air pollution on a global scale

Coral Salvador^{1,2}, Sergio M. Vicente-Serrano^{3,4}, Luis Gimeno⁵, Raquel Nieto⁵, José-Carlos Fernandez-Álvarez^{5,6}, Ana M. Vicedo-Cabrera^{1,2}, Multi-Country Multi-City collaborative research network⁷

¹Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ²Oechger Center for Climate Change Research, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ³Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (IPE- CSIC), Zaragoza, Spain. ⁴Laboratorio de Climatología y Servicios Climáticos (LCSC), CSIC-University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain.

⁵Environmental Physics Laboratory (EPHysLab), Centro de Investigación Mariña, Universidade de Vigo, Ourense, Spain. ⁶Galician Supercomputing Center (CESGA), Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ⁷-, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

Climate change is amplifying drought exposure and vulnerability, posing unprecedented challenges to public health. However, the association between droughts and health remains uncertain, and the underlying mechanisms are not fully understood.

In this multi-location study, conducted in collaboration with the Multi-Country Multi-City collaborative research network, we aimed to 1) assess the effects of short-term and long-term droughts (measured by the 1-month and 12-month Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index, respectively) on mortality, and 2) evaluate the role of air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and O₃) as potential mediators of the drought-mortality associations. We applied an extended two-stage time series analysis and compared two models: a main model adjusted for baseline characteristics and another model with an additional adjustment for each pollutant, separately. We limited analyses to locations with available data.

Overall, we found increased mortality risks associated with different drought conditions, with notable geographic differences in long-term drought-related risk patterns. An indication of the mediation effect of particulate matter was suggested (e.g., for extreme conditions, overall risks changed from 1.011 (1.008, 1.015) to 1.006 (1.002, 1.010) for short-term droughts and from 1.013 (1.009, 1.017) to 1.007 (0.998, 1.015) for long-term droughts after the PM₁₀ adjustment). For some countries, the effect was no longer apparent after the adjustment. For ozone, overall risks for long-term droughts slightly decreased from 1.012 (1.008, 1.016) to 1.007 (0.997, 1.017), with minimal differences across countries or under short-term droughts.

These findings provide valuable evidence supporting more ambitious measures to reduce drought-related health risks in the context of climate change.

Air temperature and thrombotic cardiovascular disease in England: a case time series using population-wide electronic health records during the COVID-19 pandemic

Isabel Walter^{1,2}, Alexia Sampri², Thomas Bolton^{3,4}, Stelios Boulitsakis Logothetis², Shivang Pandey¹, Leonardo Olivetti⁵, Yueying Li⁶, Fionna Chalmers^{3,4}, James Farrel^{3,4}, Rachel Denholm⁶, Samantha Ip², Luigi Filippo Brizzi⁷, Gabriele Messori⁵, Arturo de la Cruz Libardi⁸, Antonio Gasparrini⁸, Angela Wood², Elena Raffetti^{1,2}

¹Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ²University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ³British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre, London, United Kingdom. ⁴Health Data Research UK, London, United Kingdom. ⁵Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁶University of Bristol, Bristol, United Kingdom. ⁷University of Padova, Padova, Italy. ⁸London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

Background

Hot and cold temperatures are associated with thrombotic cardiovascular disease, but evidence on non-fatal outcomes remains limited. As COVID-19 has lasting cardiovascular effects and may coincide with non-optimal temperatures, we assessed the association of air temperature with thromboembolic disease and its modification by prior COVID-19.

Methods

We conducted a case time series using whole-population electronic health records in England (Jan 2020-Dec 2022). Daily mean air temperature per Lower Super Output Area was linked to person-level arterial thrombotic events (AEs), venous thrombotic events (VEs), acute myocardial infarctions (AMIs), and ischaemic strokes (ISs). We estimated short-term effects of temperature using Conditional Poisson regression with distributed lag non-linear models.

Findings

Among 49,080,575 individuals, we identified 604,655 AEs, 215,090 VEs, 275,390 AMIs, and 231,485 ISs. Heat was associated with VEs, with cumulative effects over 21 days (IRR 1.33, 95% CI 1.21-1.47, 99th percentile 23.1°C vs median 10.8°C), most pronounced among those of Black ethnic group, with comorbidities, smokers, and London residents. 3.38 (1.16-5.41) VEs per 100,000 person-years were attributable to temperatures above the median. For those with prior COVID-19 (within 6 months), the estimated association was stronger at cold temperatures (1st percentile, -0.7 °C; 1.32, 1.01-1.74). Cold (1st perc.) was associated with AMI (14-day cumulative IRR 0.90, 0.82-0.99), particularly among those ≥65 years, of White ethnic group, most deprived, (ex-)smokers, with comorbidities. No associations were found for AEs/ISs.

Interpretation

Our findings suggest susceptibility to temperature-related thrombotic events varies across population groups and may change following recent viral respiratory disease.

The short-term effect of multiple heat indicators on birth outcomes in Africa, Europe and Latin America

Lebohang Radebe^{1,2}, Chloe Brimicombe³, Michalis Koureas⁴, Federica Nobile^{5,6}, Mian Bao⁷, Paula Pereda Suárez⁸, Valentina Colistro⁸, Elizaveta Fomenko⁹, Paul Lokubal¹⁰, Tobias Monthaler³, Katharina Wieser³, Georgios Charvalis⁴, Varvara Mouchtouri⁴, Christos Hadjichristodoulou⁴, Massimo Stafoggia^{5,6}, Sibusiso Mkwanzani², Shobna Sawry², Carmen Briner¹¹, Alane Izu^{12,13,14}, Ziyaad Dangor¹², Shabir Madhi^{12,13,14}, Claudia Hanson^{15,16,17}, Peter Waiswa¹⁸, Andrea Barnabas Pembe¹⁹, Jean-Paul Dossou¹⁹, Effie Chipeta²⁰, Hussein Kidanto¹⁷, Mercedes Colomar⁸, Ilona M. Otto³, Debra Jackson^{21,22}, Stanley Luchters^{23,24,25}, Matthew Chersich^{1,2,26}, Jeroen de Bont⁶

¹Wits Planetary Health Research Division, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ²Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ³Wegener Centre for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Graz, Austria. ⁴Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Thessaly, Larissa, Greece. ⁵Department of Epidemiology, Lazio Region Health Service /ASL Roma 1, Rome, Italy. ⁶Institute of Environmental Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁷Clinical Epidemiology Division, Department of Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁸Pan American Health Organization, Washington, United States. ⁹University of Ghent, Ghent, Belgium. ¹⁰Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology and International Health, Faculty of Epidemiology and Population Health, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ¹¹Perinatal HIV Research Unit, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ¹²South African Medical Research Council Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics Research Unit, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ¹³Department of Science and Innovation/National Research Foundation South African Research Chair Initiative in Vaccine Preventable Diseases Unit, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ¹⁴African Leadership in Vaccinology Expertise, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ¹⁵Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ¹⁶Department of Disease Control, Faculty of Infectious and Tropical Diseases, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ¹⁷Centre of Excellence for Women and Child Health, Aga Khan University, Nairobi, Kenya. ¹⁸Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda. ¹⁹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences, Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania, United Republic of. ²⁰Centre for Reproductive Health, Kamuzu University of Health Science, Blantyre, Malawi. ²¹MARCH Centre, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, Keppel St, London, United Kingdom. ²²School of Public Health, University of the Western Cape, Cape Town, South Africa. ²³Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research, Harare, Zimbabwe. ²⁴Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine, Liverpool, United Kingdom. ²⁵Department of Public Health and Primary Care, Ghent University of Public Health and Primary Care, Ghent, Belgium. ²⁶Public Health and Primary Care, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

Abstract

Objective: Comparing studies worldwide that evaluate the adverse effects of heat exposure on birth outcomes poses multiple challenges, including heterogeneity in study designs. In

this study, we aimed to assess the association between multiple heat indicators and various birth outcomes using data from Africa, Europe and Latin America (LAM).

Methods: Using hospital (Benin, Malawi, Tanzania, Uganda, Argentina, Bolivia, Dominican Republic, Guatemala, Honduras, Uruguay), regional (Italy, South Africa) and national (Greece, Sweden) birth registry data, we employed a time-stratified case-crossover design to evaluate the association between short-term (<7 days) heat exposure and birth outcomes (preterm birth (PTB) and stillbirth (SB)). We generated country-specific effect estimates and meta-analyzed the results for maximum Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) temperature. We further compared the association using minimum, mean, maximum and diurnal range of four different heat metrics (temperature, WBGT, UTCI, and heat index).

Results: From 1999-2024, 5,445,771 births occurred across the 15 settings, with 7.8% [2.5%-17.1%] PTBs and 0.5% [0.1%-7.2%] SBs. In meta-analysis, compared to the 75th percentile of max UTCI, the 99th percentile was associated with a 10% increase in the odds of PTB [95% CI: 1.07-1.14]. We observed stronger heat exposure effects in LAM and Africa versus Europe. We observed an 8% increase in the odds of SB [95% CI: 0.96-1.22]. Heat exposure metrics were strongly correlated, yielding similar effect estimates, while UTCI showed higher effects in humid countries.

Conclusion: We provide robust estimates for the detrimental effects of heat on PTB, especially in Africa and LAM, using an harmonized statistical approach.

Wildfire in-plume chemistry implications on air quality and health

Eleni Dovrou^{1,2}, Apostolos Voulgarakis^{3,2}

¹University of Crete, Heraklion, Crete, Greece. ²Leverhulme Center for Wildfires, Environment and Society, London, United Kingdom. ³Technical University of Crete, Chania, Crete, Greece

Abstract

Wildfire events present a rising frequency in recent years, especially in regions dominated by elevated temperatures, dry and windy conditions. During such events, the generated fire plume contains a mixture of gaseous and particulate species, driving the chemical processing during the initial and aging stage. Organic aerosols comprise a large portion of the available chemical species inside a fire plume and their fate is primarily determined by two competing regimes: (1) oxidation-driven condensation and (2) dilution-driven evaporation.

In this work we evaluate the conditions of prevalence of each regime, identifying the oxidation-driven condensation as the driving mechanism in fresh plumes and the dilution-driven evaporation in aged plumes. Data obtained from FIREX-AQ flights are used to examine the conditions affecting and favoring each regime, considering the vegetation and meteorological profile of northwestern area in the US. The effect and differentiation between the two regimes are also investigated in regional model simulations. Past and future scenarios reveal the air quality and health impact of wildfire events in selected regions. Targeting specific fire events will allow for in-depth analysis and evaluation of the regional model representation of fire plume chemical evolution, with implications for better understanding the signature of wildfires on atmospheric composition and climate.

Impact: data, modelling, and overviews I

Temporal trends, spatial distribution, and co-occurrences of global geocoded shocks (1990–2020)

Julie Sampieri^{1,2}, Loui Delannoy^{1,3,4}, Peter Sjøgaard Jørgensen^{1,3,2}

¹Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Anthropocene Laboratory, The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden. ³Global Economic Dynamics and the Biosphere, Royal Swedish Academy of Science, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁴Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Shocks—sudden events with noticeable impacts on human and natural systems—are central to how polycrisis unfolds. Building on our global database of national shocks (Delannoy et al., 2025, *Global Sustainability*), we introduce a geocoded extension that enables subnational mapping of shock patterns and cross-domain co-occurrences. We harmonize and template multiple datasets of climatic, geophysical, ecological, economic, technological and conflict-related shocks for 150 countries from 1990 to 2020, creating a consistent, versioned pipeline that supports reproducible updates. Preliminary analyses suggest three broad features: (i) an increase in the frequency and spatial clustering of reported shocks since the early 2000s; (ii) marked regional heterogeneity in both levels and trends, with distinct domain compositions across regions; and (iii) rising co-occurrence across domains—most notably between climate-related extremes and socio-economic disruptions—forming persistent hotspots in some settings. By coupling geocoded events with a standardized taxonomy and co-occurrence metrics, the new database opens the door to systematic assessment of shared drivers, cascading pathways and place-based vulnerabilities. We outline the data architecture, validation steps and illustrative applications, and discuss how this resource can support improved risk governance.

The SHEDIS dataset: Subnational Hazard and Exposure information linked to international DISaster impact records

Sara Lindersson^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Understanding the outcomes of disasters triggered by extreme climate events requires integrating information on the resulting impacts with the climate hazards and human exposure. However, international disaster databases often lack detailed data across all these risk dimensions. For example, the widely used disaster database EM-DAT provides impact information but contains limited information on the underlying hazard and exposure conditions.

To address this gap, we present SHEDIS: an open-access series of datasets that link Subnational Hazard and Exposure information to international DISaster impact records. The first release, SHEDIS-Temperature, provides hazard and exposure metrics for temperature-related extremes (heatwaves and cold waves) recorded in EM-DAT from 1979 to 2018, covering 382 disaster records across more than 2800 subnational locations in 71 countries.

High-resolution hazard metrics have been derived from 0.1°, 3-hourly meteorological reanalysis data and include both absolute indicators (e.g. 3-hourly maximum temperature) and percentile-based indicators (e.g. exceedance over the 95th percentile). Population exposure metrics, calculated using annually interpolated population maps, quantify indicators such as person-days of exposure to threshold-exceeding temperatures.

SHEDIS provides outputs at multiple spatial aggregation levels – grid cell, administrative unit, and disaster record – enabling diverse analytical applications. Future extensions of SHEDIS will expand to also cover additional hazard types and more recent records. By systematically linking detailed hazard and exposure information with validated reports of disaster impacts, SHEDIS enables more rich international analyses of past climate-related disasters.

An LLM-Constructed Database of Natural Disasters' Impacts

Konstantinos Palaiologos¹, Panagiotis Ioannis Raptis¹, Giorgos Lampropoulos¹, Emmanouil Flaounas^{2,3}

¹Web2Climate, Athens, Greece. ²ETH, Zurich, Switzerland. ³HCMR, Athens, Greece

Abstract

The consequences of natural disasters are described inconsistently across journals, media, and institutional reports, varying in precision, terminology, and credibility. For climate-impact assessment and adaptation planning, these fragmented observations hold essential information. We have developed a structured, quality-assured database of disaster impacts, constructed through a large-language-model (LLM)–assisted extraction pipeline that transforms heterogeneous publicly available sources into comparable, traceable indicators.

Full-page documents from open-access scientific journals, multilingual news outlets, encyclopedic archives were ingested and filtered, preserving publication metadata and contextual cues (“who said what, when, and why”). A uniform event schema captures hazard type, timing, location, fatalities, displacements, losses, and institutional responses (evacuations, closures, power restoration). Automated routines handle deduplication, georeferencing, unit normalization, and conflict resolution, while provenance is retained at paragraph level.

Four models—ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-4o mini, Gemini 2.5 Pro, and Gemini 2.5 Flash—were benchmarked on a 250-event ground-truth database (from different sources) using field-level similarity metrics for dates, locations, hazards, and numerical impacts. Gemini 2.5 Pro achieved the highest weighted accuracy, but ChatGPT-4o mini delivered near-parity with four- to ten-fold lower token cost and was adopted for production extraction.

The curated ledger currently covers 185 events (1570–2025) across European coastal regions, encoded in FAIR-compliant formats (JSON, GeoJSON, NetCDF) and published via the OCEANIDS Zenodo community and GeoServer (WMS/WFS). Each record carries credibility scores, versioned values, and geocoding confidence, forming a reproducible, machine-readable foundation for climate-impact analysis and decision support.

Building a dataset of drought impacts to the water sector using Large Language Models

Jeanne Fernandez^{1,2}, Shorouq Zahra^{1,3}

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Research Institutes of Sweden, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Drought is a hydrological extreme that is increasingly gaining attention in the Nordic countries due to climate change. Indeed, over the 21st century, seasonal water shortages could become more common in some parts of the Nordic region, posing a challenge for municipal water supplies. To prepare for dry periods, there is a need not only to understand the physical impacts (e.g., declining groundwater levels) but also to document the societal implications and the local measures taken to respond to water shortages. In Sweden, the most common measure to respond to shortages is to reduce household water consumption through temporary water use restrictions. However, as such restrictions are implemented independently by each municipality, there is currently no long-term and national-level overview of where and when these events have occurred. To address this gap, we propose an extraction pipeline that leverages a Large Language Model (LLM) to build a dataset of water use restrictions from Swedish news articles. We explored different approaches for extracting key details: restriction type, location, start and end dates, and cause. We also tested a variety of LLM prompting techniques and frameworks controlling the generation process. The performance of the LLM was evaluated against an annotated test dataset. Preliminary results suggest that the model correctly extracts locations and dates, but it does not consistently identify the date a ban is lifted as an end-date. Nonetheless, the results confirm the potential of LLMs to generate datasets on drought measures, providing useful insights into the societal impacts of water scarcity.

A 50-year natural hazard impact database for Sweden

Johanna Mård

Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Climate-related hazards pose significant environmental and societal challenges in Sweden, complicating decision-making, planning, and risk management. Despite the country's exposure to floods, storms, wildfires, and landslides, no comprehensive record exists that documents where these events—and their impacts—have occurred. This study presents a Swedish natural hazard impact database covering a 50-year period. The database compiles information on sudden-onset climate hazards from diverse sources, including governmental reports, county board documents, and scientific publications. The database offer new insights into the spatiotemporal distribution of climate-related hazards, improve understanding of their underlying drivers, and support ongoing efforts to plan for and effectively manage future events.

Unveiling the Socio-Economic Footprint of Mediterranean Tropical-Like Cyclones through AI-Driven News Analysis

Daniel Pardo-García, Francisco Pastor, Samira Khodayar

Mediterranean Centre for Environmental Studies (CEAM), Valencia, Spain

Abstract

Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones, *medicanes*, represent some of the most damaging and socio-economically disruptive weather phenomena in the region. Despite their increasing severity, a comprehensive and systematic assessment of their societal and economic consequences has remained limited.

To bridge this gap, we present an innovative, AI-based framework designed to extract, classify, and monitor the socio-economic impacts of medicanes using unstructured textual data from diverse sources—including news articles, media reports, and documentation from international agencies. In the first phase, event-related texts are identified through an advanced filtering process combining geographical constraints, topic relevance, and keyword-based selection. In the second phase, we apply state-of-the-art Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques to analyze and categorize the types and magnitudes of impacts reported across different sectors.

By integrating NLP and ML with geolocation tools, our approach enables the automated spatial and temporal mapping of medicane-related damages, thereby minimizing subjective biases and reducing reliance on manual assessments. The resulting dataset provides new insights into the spatial distribution and temporal evolution of these impacts, demonstrating that news and other textual sources can serve as reliable and scalable indicators of disaster consequences.

This research offers, for the first time, a systematic and reproducible methodology to quantify the socio-economic footprint of Mediterranean cyclones. The findings open new pathways for impact-based forecasting, enhance risk understanding, and support adaptive strategies to strengthen community resilience in the face of future extreme weather events.

Societal adaptation and justice dimensions II

Navigating Dry Spells: A Scoping Review of Drought-Adaptation Strategies Across the Southern African Development Community

Leah Selters^{1,2}, Eleanor Vance², Vaibhav Anand³, Banawe Anissa⁴, Chris Hillbruner⁵, Christopher Ihinegbu^{6,7}, Miriam Israel⁸, Jubeena Judi Joe⁹, Caroline Kawira¹⁰, Megan Lukas-Sithole¹¹, Renate Meyer¹², Relebohile Mojaki¹³, Ian Moore², Miriam Nielson¹⁴, Susan Njambi-Szlapka¹⁵, Erin Coughlan de Perez^{1,2}

¹Feinstein International Center, Tufts University, Boston, Massachusetts, United States. ²Friedman School of Nutrition Science & Policy, Tufts University, Boston, Massachusetts, United States. ³Tobin College of Business, St. John's University, New York, New York, United States. ⁴Wageningen University, Wageningen, Netherlands. ⁵United States Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C., United States. ⁶University of California, Irvine, Irvine, California, United States. ⁷University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu, Nigeria. ⁸FilterLabs, Cambridge, Massachusetts, United States. ⁹Indian Institute of Forest Management, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India. ¹⁰University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya. ¹¹Cape Peninsula University of Technology, Cape Town, Western Cape, South Africa. ¹²Red Cross Red Crescent Centre, The Hague, Netherlands. ¹³National University of Lesotho, Roma, Lesotho. ¹⁴Columbia University, New York City, New York, United States. ¹⁵Jameel Observatory, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Abstract

As climate change contributes to increasingly severe drought, it is crucial to identify successful adaptation strategies in Sub-Saharan African countries with low water availability, poor water sanitation infrastructure, and reliance on rain-fed agriculture. According to the Global Adaptation Mapping Initiative (GAMI), existing climate adaptation data must be synthesized to determine successful risk reduction, particularly for under-assessed regions like Southern Africa. This scoping review draws from the GAMI methodology to determine how drought strategies in Southern African can lead to transformative change.

We conducted two rounds of academic article screening to identify articles published after 2019 that document implemented drought adaptation strategies in Southern African countries. The first round was conducted by two reviewers and included 171 out of 2,153 articles, while the second round of fifteen reviewers filtered this down to 141 articles. Data was extracted from the remaining articles on the type and categorization of adaptation, based on IPCC definitions, alongside the agents involved, evidence of risk reduction, and barriers or enablers to implementation.

Our findings will demonstrate which drought strategies are indicative of transformative change and identify aspects that both hinder and enable their success. By synthesizing existing literature on drought adaptation strategies in Southern Africa, this review can inform ongoing humanitarian and developmental efforts to prioritize the most effective drought adaptation strategies in an understudied region.

Climate adaptation tools under scrutiny: implications for just and sustainable adaptation in the Mediterranean

Elisa Savelli^{1,2}, Milica Tošić³, Irida Lazić³, Christian Pagé⁴, Aristeidis Koutroulis⁵

¹Triangle Policy Research and Media, Beirut, Lebanon. ²Mercy Corps, Portland, Oregon, United States. ³Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia. ⁴Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique (CERFACS), Toulouse, France. ⁵Technical University of Crete, School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Chania, Greece

Abstract

Climate change adaptation (CCA) tools are now widely used for risk assessment, planning, implementation, and monitoring across sectors and governance levels. Yet our review of 120+ tools exposes systematic gaps that may undermine just and sustainable adaptation in Mediterranean contexts. Key shortcomings concern who the tools are built for, how they frame space and sectors, and where they are applicable, particularly the limited attention to Southern Mediterranean countries.

Most tools target institutional and technical users (e.g., policymakers, municipal authorities, private-sector professionals), aligning with decision-making needs but sidelining other crucial constituencies such as educators, NGOs, and community groups, the very people who must adapt.

Limited integration of local knowledge, weak public awareness components, and the heavy technical expertise required by many tools create barriers to access, use, and durable resilience. Moreover, the prevailing orientation to administrative boundaries rarely aligns with biophysical realities. Few tools are designed around ecosystems, watersheds, or other physical geographies that structure climate impacts and cross-boundary processes in the Mediterranean. Likewise, only a minority provide the fine spatial detail or higher temporal resolution needed for operational, local-scale decision support. Together, these limitations risk reinforcing uneven capacities and outcomes. We argue for re-designing CCA tools to broaden user inclusivity, better reflect physical geographies, and deliver locally actionable outputs, especially for under-served areas in the Southern Mediterranean, so that tools genuinely enable fair, effective adaptation on the ground.

Assessing Climate Adaptation Behaviors and Livelihood Strategy Prioritization in Coastal Bangladesh: Evidence from Kalapara Upazila

Mithun Dutta¹, Gazi Saiful Islam¹, Sonia Binte Murshed²

¹Save the Children, Dhaka, Bangladesh. ²Bangladesh University Of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

Coastal communities in Bangladesh face escalating climate-induced challenges, including cyclones, tidal surges, and riverbank erosion. This study examining historical changes in climatic parameters and assessing adaptive mechanisms through adaptation strategy index (ASI) investigates livelihood vulnerability and adaptive strategies in Nilganj Union, an unprotected coastal area of Kalapara Upazila, Patuakhali District, using a mixed-methods approach. Historical climate data from 1993–2023 reveals a significant upward trend in maximum temperatures and fluctuating rainfall patterns, intensifying local environmental stressors. Household surveys (n=156), focus group discussions, and key informant interviews provided data on socio-economic conditions and adaptation practices. The findings reveal that 68.75% of households have not adopted any formal adaptation strategies, primarily due to financial constraints and lack of awareness. Multiple linear regression analysis shows that income is the only statistically significant factor influencing adaptation behaviour ($p < 0.05$), while gender, age, and education have negligible impact. The Adaptive Strategy Index (ASI) was employed to prioritize adaptation measures. Results highlight livelihood diversification, health service improvements, and crop insurance schemes as top strategies, while early warning systems and environmental conservation measures rank lower due to perceived irrelevance or inaccessibility. This study underscores the urgent need for holistic, evidence-based adaptation planning those bridges short-term livelihood needs and long-term resilience building. Two key strategies have been considered: piloting forecast-based financing mechanisms and allocating disaster management funds for the protection of livelihood assets. The ASI framework offers a valuable tool for prioritizing context-specific adaptation actions and guiding resource allocation in vulnerable coastal regions.

Adapting to overheating in UK homes: an empirical evaluation of occupant ventilation and shading behaviour

Ben Roberts, David Allinson, Kevin Lomas

Loughborough University, Loughborough, United Kingdom

Abstract

Climate change is driving more frequent and intense heatwaves, which is threatening occupant health and wellbeing due to overheating in the UK housing stock. This study demonstrates how occupants can reduce or exacerbate overheating with their use of windows, doors, and internal shading. A matched-pair of side-by-side test houses were used to compare different occupant behaviours. In one house, one behavioural strategy was enacted and was compared to the control strategy in the other house. Synthetic occupancy was installed to control the operation of windows, doors, blinds, curtains, and to generate internal heat gains. This enabled repeatable and predictable behaviours to be tested. The results showed that passive cooling interventions like window opening reduced indoor operative temperatures by 1.6°C on average, but that during a heatwave, overheating was not prevented. The insights could be used to develop public health guidance on behaviours during heatwaves and inform future building regulations on overheating to avoid reliance on mechanical cooling.

Assessing Societal Response to Extreme Temperature Shocks

Steffen Lohrey^{1,2}, Giacomo Falchetta^{3,1}, Kai Kornhuber^{1,4}

¹International Institute for Advanced Systems Analysis, Laxenburg, Austria. ²Technical University Berlin, Berlin, Germany. ³Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, Venice, Italy.

⁴Columbia University, New York, United States

Abstract

Climate projections suggest greatly increased exposure to heat, and they have recently been outpaced by record-shattering heat events. Not all physical mechanisms are understood, and also the coordinated and uncoordinated human responses to record-breaking events is not entirely clear. Insights into societal reactions to such outlier records are important for designing adaptation strategies and for anticipating societal dynamics. Here, we explore heat record exceedance in recent decades and then combine it with air-conditioning units trade data to infer whether heat records trigger uptake of air-conditioning. Our analysis focuses on Europe. We use daily maximum temperature from ERA5, and annual air-conditioning import data at country-level from UN Comtrade. We validate our hypothesis using both fixed effects regression and event coincidence analysis (ECA) techniques. While temperature records show a strong upward trend in entire Europe, the occurrence of large temperature record exceedance is spatially heterogeneous. Fixed effects analyses show a statistically significant effect of highest temperature and GDP on imports, and highlight the importance of a one-year time lag between highest temperature and air-conditioning imports. Further, the ECA points at a statistically significant result in some domains, but may be confounded by a relatively short timeseries. Overall, our results show promising insights into an issue that is of urgent societal importance. Real-world discussions reflect that Europe may be at the brink of large-scale adoption of air-conditioning. Insights into the driving role of single record-breaking events in these dynamics can be very valuable for informing policies and adaptation measures.

Do trees in croplands support the heat adaptation of agricultural workers? A quasi-experimental study of natural regeneration effect on human environmental and physiological outcomes.

Leonard Kadege¹, [Peninah Murage](#)², Faraja Chiwanga^{3,1}

¹LEAD Foundation, Dodoma, Dodoma, Tanzania, United Republic of. ²London School of Hygien and Tropical Medicine, London, London, United Kingdom. ³Mhimibili National Hospital, Dar es salaam, Tanzania, United Republic of

Abstract

Background:

Nature-based solutions (NbS) are increasingly recognized as cost-effective strategies for climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation. However, their potential to regulate microclimates and reduce heat exposure in rural low-resource settings is not well understood. This study evaluates the cooling effects and health impacts of regenerating native trees using Farmer Managed Natural Regeneration (FMNR) in agricultural landscapes of Central Tanzania.

Methods:

We conducted a quasi-experimental study involving 510 outdoor agricultural workers across 25 FMNR villages and 25 matched control sites. Microclimate data were recorded continuously during peak work hours using Kestrel D2 data loggers. Physiological measures (skin temperature, core body temperature, heart rate) were collected using research-grade Calera wearables. Participants were balanced on age and sex using Coarsened Exact Matching. Regression models estimated the effect of FMNR on microclimate parameters, while cosinor mixed-effects models are being used to analyze physiological outcomes.

Results:

Results show significant microclimate differences between FMNR farms and controls. Heat Index decreased by 1.28 °C ($\beta = -1.28$, $p = 0.020$, 95% CI: -2.36 to -0.20) in FMNR sites, indicating a cooling effect. Temperature increased by 0.32 °C ($\beta = 0.25$, $p = 0.499$), and relative humidity decreased by 2.57% ($\beta = -2.57$, $p = 0.136$). Analysis of FMNR's impact on physiological outcomes is ongoing.

Conclusions:

Findings suggest that native trees in agricultural landscapes regulates local microclimates and improve heat resilience among rural outdoor workers. Incorporating NbS like FMNR into climate adaptation strategies may provide a cost-effective approach to enhancing occupational heat resilience in low-resource settings.

Foodsystems, crops, and ecosystem impacts I

Cascading climate extremes in global food supply chains and future food demand

Johanna Hedlund¹, Bianca Biess², Michael Windisch², Sonia Seneviratne²

¹Stockholm Environment Institute, Stockholm, Sweden. ²ETH Zürich, Zürich, Switzerland

Abstract

Climate extremes threaten global food security by disrupting both local production and global food supply chains. This paper analyses how climate extremes cascade through global food supply chains by examining countries' exposure through both domestic production and trade networks under future warming scenarios. Using a climate-trade modelling approach, we integrate climate extreme projections from CMIP6 global climate model ensembles, aggregated at the country level across most countries worldwide, with FAO dyadic import-export and domestic production data. Preliminary results indicate contrasting roles of international trade in shaping exposure to climate extremes under 2°C global warming. In several arid and mid-latitude regions, impaired imports coincide with domestic production exposure, suggesting that trade may amplify exposure where climate extremes affect both trading partners. In contrast, diversified and trade-integrated economies tend to experience buffering effects, as imports from less-affected regions help stabilize total supply despite local production shocks. These emerging patterns highlight that trade does not uniformly reduce climate exposure - its effectiveness depends on the geographical co-occurrence of extremes across trade networks. Finally, we compare how this exposure from cascading climate extremes may create gaps with regards to future food demand. Our results provide an early indication that resilience strategies to combat food insecurity must consider both cascading and spatially compounding extremes, as well as their distribution.

Swedens food security vulnerability to AMOC collapse

Stephanie Rost, Russell Turner, Jayeon Lee

Gothenburg University, Gothenburg, Sweden

Abstract

Abstract

Emerging evidence suggests the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) may weaken or collapse much sooner than previously anticipated, with northern Europe especially exposed. Yet the implications for national food systems remain underexplored. This research investigates Sweden's potential food security risks through interviews with experts in climate science, agriculture, and frontline social work. Analysis shows that a collapse would likely bring longer, harsher winters, unstable seasons, and declining yields, compounded by shocks to food imports. While Sweden is often considered food secure, its high dependence on trade and limited preparedness indicate deep vulnerability. Social workers, viewed as a last line of defence against household food crises, described themselves and their institutions as wholly unprepared for prolonged shortages. By combining natural and social science perspectives, the study highlights the cascading risks of climate tipping points and calls for urgent inclusion of AMOC collapse scenarios in adaptation strategies.

Impacts of climate extremes and variability on the reliability of crop yields

Mahmoud Suliman, Riccardo Bommarco, Göran Bergkvist, Giulia Vico

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Food security requires sufficient crop yields that are reliably available year after year. Climate change is increasing climatic variability as well as the frequency and intensity of extremes, in many cases reducing average yields and increasing their variability. Yet, the impact of variable and extreme climatic conditions on the different aspects of crop yield reliability, that is, stability, risk of undesirable outcomes, resilience and robustness, remains only partially explored. Using metrics adapted from ecological, agronomic and engineering literature, we quantify multiple aspects of corn and soybean yield reliability in the USA 1990-2019. We assess the effects of temperature variability and extremes in the growing season, as well dry spell length and associated average temperature. Average corn and soybean yields decreased as intra-seasonal temperature variability and number of days with maximum temperature above 30 °C increased. However, increased temperature variability did not reduce yield stability or increase the risk of low yields. Corn yield robustness decreased, and most corn and soybean risk metrics increased, with longer and warmer dry spells. Yield stability also decreased under longer and warmer dry spells for corn and soybean, respectively. The detrimental effect of these adverse climatic conditions was not captured by all risk metrics. Moreover, we found no effect of climatic conditions on yields resilience to shocks. Overall, our results indicate varied sensitivity, and in some cases insensitivity, of yield reliability metrics to climatic stressors, highlighting the need to consider multiple aspects and metrics of yield reliability when assessing climate impacts on crop yields.

Crop yield response to short-term climatic conditions and cropping system options for adaptation

Giulia Vico¹, Riccardo Bommarco²

¹Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Uppsala, Sweden. ²Sciences (SLU), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Crop yields depend on climatic conditions. While most assessments focus on average growing season precipitation or temperature, there is increasing evidence that crops can be synergistically affected by their combinations, as well as by short, but potentially damaging extreme events. Using county-level yield data in the USA and Sweden, we show that dry spells length and their temperature explain a fraction of yield variance comparable to that of growing season precipitation total and average temperature. This high explanatory power demonstrates the importance of short-term detrimental climatic conditions. Moreover, climatic indicators relative to temperature and precipitation interact in defining crop yields, with reductions in yields if warmer temperatures are not accompanied by higher precipitation.

Temperatures are increasing globally, whereas projected changes in precipitation are region-specific and more uncertain. There is a general increase in frequency and intensity of dry spells, suggesting that the conditions we identified as detrimental are becoming more common. We thus need to find cropping systems that can buffer against these conditions. Using data from 32 long-term field experiments across Europe and North America, we show that rotating functionally different crops, such as cereals, legumes, and leys, can cancel the losses in yields caused by warming.

Stratospheric Precursors of European Vegetation Dynamics and Crop Yield

Marina Friedel¹, Johanna Beikert^{1,2}, Ana Bastos¹, Nora Linscheid¹, Marlene Kretschmer¹

¹Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany. ²Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany

Abstract

The strength of the stratospheric polar vortex (SPV) exerts a well-established influence on surface weather patterns, modulating temperature and precipitation across the Northern Hemisphere. Because these variables directly influence vegetation phenology, SPV variability is likely to leave a measurable imprint on European vegetation dynamics.

We classify winters (DJF) into strong and weak SPV years using ERA5 zonal-mean zonal wind at 10 hPa and 60° N, and analyze subsequent vegetation responses using satellite-derived indices. During weak SPV years, colder temperatures and reduced shortwave radiation suppress vegetation activity across much of Europe until March. By late spring and early summer (April–June), these anomalies reverse sign in several regions, consistent with circulation changes following the springtime polar vortex breakdown.

We further demonstrate that the mid-winter SPV strength influences both the onset of vegetation growth in spring and the maximum productivity in summer, which are key factors for agricultural yield. The winter SPV state also affects the frequency of vegetation hazards, including frost after bud burst, drought, and water excess. Drought and water excess are amplified during strong SPV years, while overall risk is reduced in weak SPV years. In the French “breadbasket”, winter crop yields are typically enhanced in weak SPV years, whereas strong SPV years are associated with increased climate-related risks and potential crop yield losses.

These results highlight a previously unexplored stratosphere–biosphere link, highlighting SPV variability as a driver of interannual fluctuations in European vegetation and crop productivity, with important implications for seasonal forecasting and climate risk management.

Effects of climate change on key winter variables relevant for agriculture

Faranak Tootoonchi^{1,2}, Giulia Vico¹, Flavio Lehner²

¹Swedish university of agricultural sciences, Uppsala, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Cornell university, Ithaca, NY, United States

Abstract

In the face of climate change, autumn-sown crops are gaining attention for their higher yields and resilience to early-season climatic stress, compared with spring-sown crops. However, their exposure to winter conditions makes them more vulnerable to frost damage, particularly when snow cover is insufficient. Assessing the future likelihood of such conditions requires reliable simulations of key winter variables, temperature, precipitation, and snow depth, and their interactions.

Single Model Initial-Condition Large Ensembles (SMILEs), combined with bias-correction methods, help disentangle natural climate variability from forced changes and correct systematic differences between simulations and observations. They offer the potential to better represent conditions critical to winter crops and to identify when long-term trends emerge from background variability. However, their effectiveness in capturing these processes remains insufficiently understood and requires further investigation.

We used a regional SMILE from the Canadian Regional Climate Model version 5 (CRCM5-LE) over Scandinavia under the RCP8.5 scenario (1955–2099) to analyse climate changes relevant to over-winter crops and evaluate the effect of bias correction. By 2050–2099, precipitation and snow depth decrease across most of Scandinavia, except the Norwegian mountains, while winter temperatures rise, exceeding 0 °C south of 59 °N. Bias correction reduced variability and slightly weakened trends, removing the weak precipitation trend altogether. Temperature and snow-depth trends emerged as early as the 2030s, strongest in Finland. The projected snow decline increases frost risk for autumn-sown crops despite overall warming, highlighting the need for adaptation strategies.

Impact: data, modelling and overviews II

Climate Risk STAC: A living metadata catalog of geospatial data for assessing climate impacts

Lena Reimann^{1,2}, Dirk Eilander^{2,3}, Timothy Tiggeloven^{2,4}, Milana Vuckovic⁵, Matti Kummu¹, Andrea Vajda⁶, Jeremy S. Pal⁴, Maurizio Mazzoleni², Fredrik Wetterhall⁵, Jeroen C.J.H. Aerts^{2,3}

¹Aalto University, Espoo, Finland. ²Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands. ³Deltares, Delft, Netherlands. ⁴CMCC, Venice, Italy. ⁵ECMWF, Reading, United Kingdom. ⁶Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

Abstract

Climate impacts are intensifying globally due to climate change, driven by stronger climate hazards (e.g., storms, floods) and evolving socioeconomic conditions that shape exposure and vulnerability. Climate impact assessments constitute a tool to understand these dynamics under current and future conditions using geospatial data. However, relevant datasets are often scattered across multiple platforms, limiting their Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). Consequently, identifying and selecting appropriate datasets for climate impact assessments remains a time-consuming task.

We present Climate Risk STAC, a living metadata catalog of open-access geospatial datasets designed to support climate impact assessments. Version 0.1 of the catalog contains 214 metadata entries describing 84 global-scale datasets, organized across nine climate hazards, five types of exposed elements, and seven vulnerability categories. A user-friendly web browser facilitates data exploration and selection. Hosted on GitHub, the catalog is designed as a collaborative resource, encouraging community contributions through an online submission form.

By promoting discoverability and reusability of key datasets, Climate Risk STAC advances FAIR data practices in the climate impact domain. While the current version focuses on global-scale datasets, its flexible design allows future expansion to regional or sectoral levels. As a living catalog, it aims to grow alongside evolving concepts and data needs in climate impact assessment. Climate Risk STAC is openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14018438>.

Multi-Hazard Impacts in EM-DAT—Not Just the Sum of Their Parts?

Wiebke S. Jäger, Marleen C. de Ruiter, Timothy Tiggeloven, Philip J. Ward

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Abstract

Understanding multi-hazard impacts is essential, as interactions among hazards, exposure, and vulnerability can generate far more severe consequences than single hazards alone. Using global EM-DAT records from 2000–2018, we develop a spatiotemporal algorithm to identify multi-hazard events and find that 35% of all events—and 61% of all hazards—occur in multi-hazard contexts. These hazards account for most recorded impacts: 78% of economic damages, 83% of affected people, and 69% of deaths. Statistical comparisons of hazard pairs, single hazards, and synthetic combinations of two single hazards indicate distinct patterns of compounding impacts, captured in four archetypes describing how interactions amplify, match, or limit combined effects. Across archetypes, hazard pairs generate impacts at least as large as single hazards. The uncertainties and limitations encountered in our study highlight the need for future research to improve data on multi-hazards and their impacts. Key uncertainties relate to the spatiotemporal information in EM-DAT, which hinders the integration with hazard, exposure and vulnerability data, and the identification of multi-hazard events. Recent and ongoing follow-up studies include the analysis of regional compound flood losses as well as improved subnational geocoding of EM-DAT.

A global stocktake of research on the interactions between flood and drought risk

Maralda Drosky, Taís M. Nunes Carvalho, Mariana M. de Brito

Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Saxony, Germany

Abstract

Floods and droughts are opposite extremes on the hydrological cycle, but they do not occur independently. Their interactions emerge through temporal and spatial overlaps, system dependencies, and dynamics across all risk determinants. The present study will synthesise research on these interactions through a systematic literature review.

A systematic keyword search identified 1,909 relevant papers, combining terms related to dynamics, floods, droughts, impacts, vulnerability, exposure and response. Following a preliminary round of manual coding, we applied a machine learning classification model, that identified 813 relevant studies focused on floods and droughts beyond hazard-only perspectives.

In the next steps, two levels of full text screening will be conducted. In the first stage, we will identify studies examining flood-drought interactions, and classify them according to their level of risk assessment: single-risk, multilayer single-risk or multi-risk. Only the latter group will be considered in the second stage, where we will capture temporal, spatial, cross-sectoral, and response-related dynamics. Furthermore, we will investigate the impacted sectors, additional hazards, applied methods, and the spatial and temporal scale of the analyses.

Using insights from the reviewed evidence, we will assess how comprehensively existing studies address the full risk framework and the interactions of flood-drought events. The methodological approaches used to explore these interactions will be synthesised to identify how they are studied, best practices, and where gaps remain. Finally, this review will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of compound flood–drought events and their systemic risks by revealing the diversity of their dynamics and non-linear relationships.

Socio-economic impacts of compound drought-heatwave events at a global scale

Koffi Worou^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2,3}

¹Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish centre for impacts of climate extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Department of Meteorology and Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Isolated and compound climate extremes, such as droughts and heatwaves, are intensifying under global warming. Recently, various frameworks have been developed to define and categorize compound events, and many studies have examined their physical dynamics. However, their socioeconomic effects are still not well quantified on a global scale using disaster record databases. Building on previous evidence that compound drought-flood events can lead to impacts (measured by affected populations and financial losses) up to eight times greater than those from isolated hazards in extratropical regions, this study investigates the socioeconomic impacts of compound drought-heatwave events using the Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT) from 1960 to 2025. We geocoded 518 country-level unique disasters (droughts and heatwaves) reported worldwide, covering 49 countries and 1,107 top-level administrative units, affecting a total of 5,457 locations. The analysis explores spatiotemporal trends in the occurrence and spatial extent of compound events. It quantifies the socioeconomic impact ratios of compound drought-heatwave events compared to isolated drought or heatwave events. This work contributes to advancing compound risks in climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction, highlighting the importance of considering the increased impacts from co-occurring extremes in a warming world.

Mapping Resilience to Compound Events in a Global Metropolis: A Case Study of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Alissa Murray¹, Louis Delannoy^{1,2}, Kara Pellowe¹, Magnus Nyström¹

¹Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm, Sweden. ²The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

The interconnectedness and amplification of crises across climatic, political, technological, and other dimensions—referred to as the polycrisis—is increasingly threatening cities worldwide. A key manifestation of polycrisis is the intensification of climate change hazards, including compound events, which combine multiple, potentially interacting climate and weather events. Yet, little research has examined compound events at an intra-urban scale, particularly within the Middle East. This study addresses this gap by considering compound events in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, a city of economic and political importance already experiencing various climate threats. Combining Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping with meteorological analysis of ERA5 data, I analyzed a) Riyadh’s vulnerability to extreme heat and flash flooding, and b) how Riyadh is impacted over time and space by three hazard scenarios: extreme heat, flash flooding, and their compound occurrence. The study integrated social, ecological, and technological dimensions with temperature and precipitation data, at a 3x3-kilometer resolution within and around Riyadh, from 2014-2024. Results show that areas of high potential hazard impacts are increasing in the north and portions of the south and west of Riyadh’s urban center, with hazard hotspots in the east, north, and southwest. The relationship between hazard scores and urban features such as impervious surface, building area, and green space varies by location and hazard type, suggesting the need for spatially differentiated mitigation strategies. This comprehensive approach to hazard mapping provides insights for Riyadh’s development, and also offers a replicable framework for other cities, supporting broader understanding of urban resilience to polycrisis.

Flood impact assessment across spatial scales: Insights from Bayesian Modelling

Bhadra Devadas¹, Nivedita Sairam², Soumendra Nath Kuiry¹

¹Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. ²GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Berlin, Germany

Abstract

Flood impact assessments often operate at either local or regional scales, with limited opportunities for transferring methodologies across different geographical areas. Our study develops a multi-scalar Bayesian framework that integrates regional adaptation insights with reported flood losses at the object level, enabling a coherent impact assessment across scales. The methodology is applied in two cases.

Case 1: At the European (continental) scale, the Bayesian Network model (BN-FLEMOcs) combined with probabilistic (return-period based) flood hazard projections, object-level exposure datasets quantified climate- and exposure-driven changes in flood damages, providing valuable metrics such as the Expected Annual Damage (EAD). By 2085, the EAD was found to rise 660% under RCP8.5, with Germany, France and Italy being the countries most severely affected. Precautionary measures could reduce EAD by up to 72% under the baseline and 67% under future scenarios.

Case 2: We adapt and extend the Bayesian Modelling approach to the 2018 floods in Alappuzha district, Kerala, India, at the regional scale by linking event-specific, retrospective hazard simulations with building damages, exposure, and socio-economic indicators at the village level to generate probabilistic impact estimates. By adapting from object-specific to generalised damage process modelling, the framework preserves methodological coherence while capturing vulnerability differences leading to varying flood impact pathways.

Validation against observed damages demonstrates robust predictive performance in both cases. Comparative analyses highlight the role of different drivers of flood impacts in both contexts. This study advances flood impact modelling across scales and provides actionable guidance for aligning resilience planning across local and continental contexts.

Governance, policy and society mediating impacts I

An exploration of the resilience factors that support rural learners to adapt to climate catastrophe stressors

Bontle Kgopa, Linda Theron

University of Pretoria, Pretoria, Gauteng, South Africa

Abstract

This study explores the resilience factors that enable rural learners to adapt to the psychosocial and educational stressors of climate-related catastrophes, like drought and extreme heat. Using a qualitative research design, data was generated through the arts-based *Draw-Write-and-Talk* method within focus groups involving 45 Grade 10 and 11 students (average age: 17) from Mamelodi Township, Pretoria East, South Africa. The Social Ecological Theory of Resilience framed the study, including the reflexive thematic analysis of the visual and narrative data. The findings emphasise that resilience emerges through physical adaptation and environmental adjustment (e.g., seeking natural shade, enhancing air circulation), health and self-care practices (e.g., staying hydrated, personal heat protection), resourcefulness and adaptive problem solving (e.g., creative use of local resources, agency and initiative) and environmental awareness and learning (recognising climatic patterns, experiential learning and behavioural adjustment). These strategies are co-enabled by peers and teachers. By amplifying students' voices, and drawing attention to the multisystemic nature of resilience resources needed to adapt to climate threats, this study underscores the need for context-specific, student-centered strategies in which parents, teachers, and elders collaborate to strengthen resilience in climate-vulnerable communities.

Keywords:

Resilience, climate change, rural learners, qualitative research, South Africa

Translating Climate Risk to Local Realities – A Case Study of Kenya

Shilpa Muliyl Asokan¹, Raphael Mulaha Kweyu², Julius M Huho³, Mary Makokha²

¹Nordic Africa Institute, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya. ³Garissa University, Garissa, Kenya

Abstract

Climate *hazards*, such as drought and flooding, interact with human *exposure*, *vulnerability* and *responses* in determining the risks. The UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction emphasizes the need for integrated or hybrid approaches in risk assessments for complex climate-related risks. The integration of the top-down and bottom-up approaches provides a comprehensive risk analysis of climate *hazard*, *exposure*, *vulnerability*, and *responses*. Translating global and regional climate risks to local realities requires integrating climate data with the local governance and socio-economic contexts. The dynamic nature of climate risks caused by both climatic and non-climatic factors makes its understanding and conceptualization challenging.

The study applied an integrated approach in translating climate risks to the local socio-economic context of Kenya. The methodology followed an integration of quantitative, spatial and dynamic models, indicators, and qualitative information to assess *hazard*, *exposure*, *vulnerability* and *responses*. Initially, spatial data on population density, temperature and drought risk are integrated and a risk index is mapped. This is followed by the integration of the Standardized Precipitation Index for the period from 2008 to 2024. This provides a spatially explicit map of Kenya representing climatic *hazards* (droughts, floods) and *exposure*. This map is further interpreted using granular data on challenges of water governance in case study areas in Turkana County to understand the local reality of *vulnerability*. The composite climate risk map of Kenya is further interpreted through the lens of *responses* by analyzing the community's drought adaptation methods and the government's adaptation strategies in case study areas in Garissa County.

Building Food Security and Trust in Refugee Settlements under Climate Stress

Stefan Döring^{1,2,3}, Jonathan Hall¹, Phaidon Vassiliou¹

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²PRIO, Oslo, Norway. ³Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden
Abstract

This paper examines how integrated climate-smart agricultural interventions and mental health support can strengthen food security, social trust, and social cohesion in refugee settlements exposed to climate stress. I report on an ongoing field experiment in the Nakivale refugee settlement in Uganda that combines climate-smart home gardening with a validated mental health program. The analysis integrates baseline survey data with remote sensing indicators, historical conflict exposure, and measures of climate variability to examine how environmental stressors and past violence shape trust and adaptation-related behavior.

Results presented here focus on baseline patterns prior to intervention. The findings show that social trust is strongly associated with exposure to natural hazards, particularly flooding and drought, and that these relationships remain robust after controlling for war exposure, mental health, and socio-economic characteristics. Ongoing analyses will assess how water access and variability influence trust, cooperation, and participation in climate adaptation practices over time.

While the study is limited to a single settlement and a 12-month intervention period, it provides early evidence on how trust and environmental stress interact in displacement contexts. By linking agricultural adaptation, mental health, and social trust—domains often studied separately—the paper advances an interdisciplinary framework for understanding how sustainability-oriented interventions may strengthen the social foundations for cooperation and peace in fragile refugee settings.

Climate Change Extremes and Coastal Groundwater: Building Urban Water Supply Resilience in the Megacity of Mumbai (India)

Honey Kumar, S Sreekesh

Center for the Study of Regional Development, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, Delhi, India

Abstract

Climate change is impacting society and the environment in coastal regions, which face the threat of sea level rise, extreme sea levels, and extreme climate events, leading to the hazard of salinization of coastal aquifers. Coastal megacities with more than 10 million people are particularly vulnerable, as groundwater extraction to meet urban water supply intensifies the process of aquifer contamination. The current research aims to investigate the vulnerability of Mumbai's coastal aquifers to saltwater intrusion (SWI), assessing their suitability for potable water supply, and exploring the socio-economic dimensions to provide policy recommendations for water supply management in Mumbai. The study uses chemical indicators, statistical tools, and empirical modelling (groundwater flow pattern mapping) to determine the incidence of SWI in Mumbai. Interestingly, the municipal corporation of Greater Mumbai has banned the use of groundwater for domestic purposes; however, this study supports the opposite, as we find no significant traces of SWI in Mumbai, and more than 95% of the water samples fall into the excellent water quality category according to the WHO drinking water standards. The groundwater quality in Mumbai has not deteriorated, and it could be a potential source of alternative/complementary water supply in the city. The study proposes the inclusion of groundwater as an integral part of urban water supply infrastructure in Mumbai, which can help build water resilience in the face of climate change. However, the regulated extraction of groundwater should be ensured through policy interventions to prevent SWI resulting from excessive groundwater extraction in the future.

When the Sea Devours the Land: A case of Climate Passport for Bangladesh's Sinking Shores

Zeba Farah Haque

North South University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

Climate change is destabilising borders as surely as it is submerging coastlines. Bangladesh, projected to lose up to 20 million people to displacement by 2050, illustrates the profound inadequacy of existing legal frameworks. The 1951 Refugee Convention excludes climate-displaced persons, while human rights law offers protection in principle but not mobility in practice. This paper advances the case for a Climate Passport—a legal instrument inspired by the Nansen Passport for stateless persons—as a means of ensuring identity, dignity, and cross-border mobility for those forced to move by rising seas. Grounded in Bangladesh's constitutional guarantees of life, dignity, and environmental protection, the paper situates climate displacement as both a legal and moral obligation of states. It further engages with the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities (CBDR) to argue that high-emitting nations carry duties to support mobility frameworks for vulnerable countries. By drawing on comparative experiments, including Nauru's 'climate citizenship' scheme, the paper positions the Climate Passport as a pragmatic response to a legal vacuum. Ultimately, it contends that when territory is lost to the sea, law must evolve to ensure that rights travel with people.

(Here is the link to my Op-Ed on this topic, published on 18 September 2025:

<https://www.thedailystar.net/opinion/views/news/case-adopting-climate-passport-3988841>, currently working on expanding this as a full paper.)

Living between droughts and floods: unpacking climate extremes from 'below' in Western India

Shilpi Srivastava¹, Megha Sheth², Shibaji Bose³, Chaithra ST⁴, Krishna AchutaRao⁴, Vinitha Bachina⁵

¹Institute of Development Studies, Brighton, United Kingdom. ²Independent Consultant, Ahmedabad, India. ³NIT, Durgapur, India. ⁴IIT, Delhi, India. ⁵Independent Consultant, Chennai, India

Abstract

Changing rainfall patterns caused by climate change can increase the severity and frequency of both droughts and floods, which are becoming increasingly co-located. By co-location, we refer to the incidence of closely timed or concurrent extreme weather events, especially in contexts with limited or no prior record of occurrence. This, we argue, creates a radical uncertainty, signifying a rupture from past climates. This paper explores how climate extremes (floods, droughts, heatwaves) are experienced from 'below' in the semi-arid regions of Western India, which are now witnessing a hydrological shift towards high rainfall and floods. Drawing on ethnographic insights, visual methods and some work in (physical) climate science, the paper unpacks diverse dimensions and lived experiences of these extremes, their cascading impacts and how communities prepare for these episodes as they intersect with their social and material worlds. In particular, we critically interrogate the social construction of extremes (how they are understood and experienced by various actors), and their temporal and spatial co-location with other systemic drivers of vulnerability. We show how these hazards that occur one after the other produce multiple co-locations and dislocations within the local communities. In doing so, we argue that while much of the emphasis remains on extremes as shocks, and their episodic incidence, it is important to understand how local people are living 'during and between' extremes on longer time scales to understand impacts and inform robust preparedness and adaptation responses.

Foodsystems, crops, and ecosystem impacts II

When Land Runs Out: Future Cropland Demand Exceeds Regional Arable Supply

Bianca Biess¹, Lukas Gudmundsson¹, Erwan Monier², Michael G. Windisch¹, Corey S. Lesk³, Sonia I. Seneviratne¹

¹Institute for Atmospheric and Climate Science, ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland. ²Department of Land, Air and Water Resources, University of California, Davis, CA, United States. ³Department of Earth and Atmospheric Science, University of Québec in Montréal, Montréal, QC, Canada

Abstract

Feeding a growing global population increasingly depends on how agriculture adapts to both social and environmental change. While intensification through technological advances and cropland expansion has historically sustained rising food demand, climate change is reshaping the limits of where crops can be grown. Global crop production depends on both the extent of cropland harvested and the productivity of that land. Although climate change has already impacted global crop yields, most projections of future agricultural output ignore whether land remains climatically suitable for cultivation, potentially overestimating the area available for cultivation. Here, we show that accounting for climate constraints sharply reduces arable land suitable for cropping. Some high-latitude regions appear to gain in climate suitability, but these gains largely disappear once soil and topography constraints are considered, leaving no net global increase in cultivable land. The decline in climate-suitable arable land is driven primarily by losses in the tropics and subtropics, which face regional cropland scarcity even under the most sustainable pathways, with scarcity increasing under higher greenhouse gas scenarios. South and Southeast Asia become land-scarce across nearly all scenarios, while Western and Northeastern Africa and northwestern South America face deficits under higher-emission pathways, limiting their ability to meet regional food demand. In these regions, potential yield gains are likewise constrained, as the increases required to offset land shortages exceed biophysical limits. Considering these biophysical limits is essential to ensure future cropland projections remain feasible under a changing climate, as they underpin food security assessments and Earth system modelling.

A case study on forest practitioners' perspectives on climate extremes: consensus on impacts and conflicts in responses

Florian Knutzen¹, Paul Auerbeck², Karsten Haustein³, Oliver Frör², Markus Groth¹

¹Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS), Hamburg, Germany. ²University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Landau, Germany. ³Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany

Abstract

Climate extremes present significant challenges to the forestry sector, impacting ecosystems, biodiversity, and overall forest health. This paper examines the perspectives of forest practitioners in Germany regarding the impacts of climate extremes, such as drought, heat waves, storms, and heavy rainfall, as well as their proposed responses and potential conflicts. Utilizing a transdisciplinary approach, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 28 forest practitioners. The findings reveal that over 89% acknowledge drought as the most significant climate extreme, highlighting its detrimental impacts on tree health and forest ecosystems. Drought-related damage since 2018 has also resulted in significant economic losses and necessitates large-scale reforestation. Notably, two divergent management approaches were identified: those prioritizing wood production (FWP) tend to focus on economic viability and timber management strategies, while those emphasizing protection and recreation (FPR) concentrate on ecological sustainability and biodiversity conservation. There is a broad consensus on the impacts of climate change, but responses remain contested. Both groups agree on the importance of promoting mixed, multi-layered forest stands to enhance resilience to climate extremes. However, important differences remain: the FWP group advocates active interventions and favors conifer species such as spruce for economic reasons, while the FPR group emphasizes natural processes and prefers native species like beech. Although climate adaptation serves as a shared rationale, their underlying priorities differ considerably. These insights underscore the need for integrating diverse perspectives in forest management to effectively address the complexities of climate change, facilitating collaborative approaches that address both economic and environmental aspects through integrated forest management.

Amazon drought sensitivity: geographical patterns in wetland and terrestrial forests

Robert Muscarella¹, Julia Tavares^{1,2}, Darlene Gris³, David Galbraith², Emmanuel Gloor², Oliver Phillips², Thiago Silva⁴

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²University of Leeds, Leeds, United Kingdom. ³Mamirauá Institute for Sustainable Development, Tefé, Brazil. ⁴University of Stirling, Stirling, United Kingdom

Abstract

Amazonia, the largest and most diverse tropical forest on Earth, increasingly faces changing precipitation regimes, including more frequent extreme droughts and floods. These changes have potentially broad impacts on biodiversity, carbon storage, and other ecosystem processes. We will present a summary of findings across a series of basin-wide field studies on tropical tree composition and physiology, with the aim to better understand diversity of tropical forest ecosystem responses to climate change. Through a multi-year effort, we assembled the first comprehensive dataset of hydraulic traits for Amazonian tree species. The data reveal substantial spatial variation in drought-related physiological thresholds, suggesting that sensitivity to extreme climatic events differs markedly in forests across the Amazon basin. We will also present new work on wetland forests; although they account for 14% of the Amazon basin area, our knowledge about the physiology of wetland forests is extremely limited in contrast with the relatively extensive literature focused on terrestrial forests. We obtained the first dataset of tree physiological characteristics related to resistance to water stress across a representative set of Amazonian wetland species along an extensive inundation gradient. Our results indicate different ability across Amazonian wetland forests to cope with a future hotter and drier climate, and we discuss these findings with those found across terrestrial Amazonian forests, deeply advancing our understanding of drought vulnerability variation within the largest and most biodiverse tropical forest on Earth. Overall, our results illustrate variation in the responses of different Amazonian forest types to cope with a future climate conditions.

Climate Extremes in Lakes: Ecological and Socioeconomic Consequences

Gesa Weyhenmeyer

Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Extreme events in lakes, such as heatwaves, droughts, floods, harmful algal blooms, and hypoxia, are globally increasing in frequency, intensity, and duration due to climate change. For seasonally ice-covered lakes, an additional extreme condition is increasingly observed: a rapid transition from ice-covered to ice-free states. Even minor changes in ice cover can critically affect water quality, fisheries, biodiversity, regional climate, and cultural and socioeconomic activities. Freshwater ice provides benefits such as recreation, cultural identity, ice fishing, and winter transportation via ice roads—used extensively for oil and gas exploration, military operations, and connecting remote communities. Rapid ice cover loss often co-occurs with other extremes, creating interactions that trigger feedback loops with severe ecological and socioeconomic consequences. Managing these growing risks demands integrated models, coordinated monitoring, and proactive adaptation strategies tailored to lake ecosystem vulnerabilities.

Is Volumetric Water Pricing Key to Safeguarding Wetland Ecosystems under Climate Stress?

Safa Baccour, Héctor Macián-Sorribes, Manuel Pulido-Velázquez, Adria Rubio-Martin

Research Institute of Water Engineering and Environment (IIAMA), Polytechnic University of Valencia, Valencia, Spain

Abstract

The increasing frequency of extreme weather events, political and cross-sectoral conflicts, and environmental pressures in Mediterranean regions underscores the urgent need for effective and adaptive economic instruments to enhance ecological resilience. However, the complexity of water systems and the uncertainty surrounding how pricing policies influence hydrological dynamics and ecosystem health pose significant challenges under future climate scenarios. This study addresses this gap by evaluating the effects of volumetric water pricing schemes on the resilience of the Albufera wetland and associated fish habitats, using the Júcar River Basin (Spain) as a representative Mediterranean case study. A hydro-economic model was developed to simulate water allocation, reservoir operation, and agricultural production under varying inflow, demand, and policy conditions derived from five global climate models and three socioeconomic pathways (SSPs). The analysis assesses the influence of volumetric pricing on water scarcity, agricultural opportunity costs, and wetland ecological integrity, incorporating metrics based on Habitat Provisioning Units (HPU%). Results indicate that volumetric pricing can substantially reduce unsustainable water withdrawals during dry periods, thereby mitigating ecological deficits in the wetland and strengthening the resilience of the broader socio-ecological system. The study also reveals trade-offs: stricter pricing may increase short-term agricultural costs under high-demand SSPs, highlighting the need for policies that balance ecological and economic objectives. These findings provide actionable guidance for sustainable water governance in Mediterranean basins, supporting the EU Water Framework Directive and advancing Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 15.

How coupled are soil and vegetation responses to precipitation extremes?

Maja Siegenthaler^{1,2}, Sini Talvinen^{3,4,2}, Marleen Pallandt^{1,2}, Daniela Guasconi^{1,2}, Xiankun Li^{1,2}, Paola Montenegro^{5,1,2}, Larissa Frey^{4,2}, Rebecca Varney^{1,2}, Ingo Fetzer^{6,2}, Stefano Manzoni^{1,2}, Maria Faticov^{7,8,2}

¹Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ³Department of Technical Physics, University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland. ⁴Department of Environmental Science, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁵Universidad del Azuay, Cuenca, Ecuador. ⁶Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁷Department of Wildlife, Fish and Environmental Studies, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå, Sweden. ⁸Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

As extreme dry and wet periods become more frequent, ecosystems might lose their capacity to function and provide essential services. While drought and extreme rainfall effects on either soil or vegetation processes have been widely studied, their joint responses remain poorly understood. To address this question, we synthesized data from precipitation-manipulation experiments that simultaneously measured vegetation and soil responses to assess when the responses were coordinated or independent. Soil responses included changes in carbon and nutrient storage and microbial activity (e.g., total carbon and nitrogen, microbial biomass and soil respiration), while vegetation responses were characterized by changes in plant productivity and respiration (e.g., root and shoot biomass, autotrophic respiration). Across experiments, we found that soil and vegetation responses were generally coordinated—drought reduced, and increased rainfall enhanced, both soil and plant storages and fluxes. However, changes due to drought and increased precipitation were more often significant in the living components, such as vegetation and soil microorganisms, while organic matter pools responded less. Notably, we identified major knowledge gaps in our understanding of joint soil and vegetation responses, as most studies focus on either one or the other ecosystem component. More integrated assessments including soil and vegetation measurements would help quantify the degree of coupling in the response of different ecosystem components to extreme events.

Impact: Data, Modelling and Overviews III

Multi-decadal analysis of major global risk assessments reveals consistent biases and low predictive capacity

Louis Delannoy^{1,2,3}, Mélis Busson^{1,4}, Peter Sjøgaard Jørgensen^{1,2,5}

¹Global Economic Dynamics and the Biosphere, Royal Swedish Academy of Science, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ³Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁴CentraleSupélec, Gif-sur-Yvette, France. ⁵Anthropocene Laboratory, Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Over the past two decades, global governance has increasingly been confronted with a growing sense of mutually reinforcing crises, referred to as “polycrisis”. Navigating these entangled dynamics requires a sound perception and communication of global systemic risks. Here, we present a multi-decadal analysis (2006–2024) of the World Economic Forum’s Global Risks Reports (GRRs), one of the most influential assessments of global risks. Using textual and statistical analyses, we examine the evolution of GRR narratives, their alignment with survey data, and their correspondence with observed historical shocks. Our results show that the framing of global risks in the GRRs has become increasingly technical and expert-oriented over time, emphasizing regulatory and economic dimensions over environmental and social concerns. Comparative analysis of report texts and survey responses indicates consistent and statistically significant underrepresentation of themes related to inequality, biodiversity loss, and ecological integrity, and elevation of themes related to economic growth. The back- and forecasting exercise reveals that, while the GRRs align moderately with past and future geopolitical risks, their predictive capacity remains low across most other categories, particularly for climate extremes, ecological disruptions, and technological shocks. Predictive capacity is also markedly higher for OECD countries and lowest for low-income ones. Our findings call for a radically more reflexive use of the GRRs. Given this background, we propose practical steps to design polycrisis-fit risk assessments, resting on transparency, diversified respondent bases, and better integration of systemic and cross-scale feedbacks.

European designs for climate-risk insurance systems

Matteo Colucci^{1,2}, Stefano Ceolotto^{1,2}, Simone Taddeo^{1,2}, Jaroslav Mysiak^{1,2}

¹CMCC, Venice, Italy. ²Ca' Foscari University, Venice, Italy

Abstract

Natural catastrophe insurance has proven effective in fostering financial resilience against mounting climate hazards. Due to diverse geographies and histories, European countries have designed various national climate insurance systems, following different societal values and economic models. A consistent research stream has emerged in recent years, describing and assessing European natural catastrophe insurance regimes in general terms. This work aims to review academic and grey literature on the structural investigation of the strengths and weaknesses of European (EU, EFTA, and UK) national systems, examining their key features and the interplay among them, as well as the role of the state. National systems, in their complexity, are evaluated based on affordability, long-run financial sustainability, and estimated penetration rates. This research provides support for policy insights and best practices for future design of national systems. Finally, it is found that the strong involvement of the state as provider, regulator, and guarantor of climate-risk protection fosters the effectiveness and sustainability of national insurance regimes.

Bridging climate projections and flood risk: A simple tool to develop storylines of flood impacts under global warming

Martina Kauzlaric^{1,2,3}, Lukas Munz^{1,2,4}, Markus Mosimann^{1,2,4}, Olivia Romppainen-Martius^{1,2,3},
Andreas Paul Zischg^{1,2,4}

¹Mobiliar Lab for Natural Risks, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ²Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ³Climate Impact Research Group, Institute of Geography, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ⁴Human-Environment-Systems Modelling Group, Institute of Geography, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland

Abstract

The frequency and intensity of floods rose in recent years, peaking in 2024 with catastrophic inundations worldwide. In Europe, despite advancements in flood forecasting and mitigation, record-breaking rainfall in 2024 caused severe socio-economic damage and resulted in over 300 fatalities. With ongoing climate warming, the risk of extreme precipitation events is expected to rise further, highlighting the critical need to re-evaluate flood risk assessment and adaptation strategies in a rapidly changing climate.

To address this challenge, we introduce an adaptable framework that extends the UNSEEN method to generate physically consistent storylines of extreme flood events under varying global warming levels. Our approach integrates pooled ECMWF reforecasts, providing an equivalent of 8400 years of plausible weather sequences, with hydrologic–hydraulic modelling. By scaling precipitation intensity according to the Clausius–Clapeyron relation, we explore the response of flood magnitudes to five different global warming scenarios.

Results reveal that record-breaking floods are already possible under present atmospheric conditions, while projected warming disproportionately amplifies flood peaks and impacts — often exceeding the rate of precipitation increase. To make these findings widely accessible, we have visualized our analysis and results into an interactive [online tool](#). This tool provides a transparent way to bridge climate projections, hydrological modeling, and risk assessment. It supports dialogue between researchers, decision-makers, and emergency planners, enabling users to explore high-resolution flood storylines, stress-test flood management strategies, and inform adaptation planning. By fostering resilience in a changing world, the tool empowers communities and stakeholders to prepare for and respond to evolving flood risks.

Quantifying risks to economic growth from hydroclimate volatility under climate change

Tyler Bagwell¹, Kelsey Murphy¹, Divya Saikumar¹, Anna Stravato¹, Justin Mankin², Frederi Viens¹, Sylvia Dee¹

¹Rice University, Houston, Texas, United States. ²Dartmouth College, Hanover, New Hampshire, United States

Abstract

Temperature and precipitation averages, variability, and extreme values have significant impacts on economic growth. Less understood are the effects of hydroclimate volatility, characterized by both the speed and magnitude of wet-to-dry and dry-to-wet variations, on economic productivity. In particular, hydroclimate “whiplash” – strong, abrupt swings between extreme wet and dry conditions – likely produces compound impacts to economies exceeding those of single-event shocks. As the planet warms, hydroclimate volatility is projected to intensify, posing unique risks to the global economy’s stability, while mitigation strategies tailored for shifts in the mean climate state alone will likely underestimate growing risks from climate volatility. Using Bayesian econometric modeling with empirical subnational economic data, we estimate the economic response to intra-year hydroclimate volatility using a novel hydroclimate whiplash metric, distinct from variability and extreme value summaries of observed climate. We quantify thresholds of whiplash for which economies tilt from resilient to vulnerable, controlling for past hydroclimate variability exposure; we estimate whether whiplash induces transitory level shifts or permanent trend changes in sub-national economic growth; and we determine whether wet-to-dry or dry-to-wet transitions provoke contrasting economic growth responses. Using historic baselines, we disentangle the contributions of anthropogenic warming from natural variability to assess their independent and joint risks on projected economic growth. Furthermore, we investigate the joint impacts of climate volatility and economic growth on social instability, namely, armed conflict. Recognizing volatility as a distinct climate hazard closes a key gap in climate economics and improves climate risk pricing, targeted adaptation, and climate attribution.

Linking Emissions from Fossil Fuel Megaprojects to Lifetime Climate Impacts Across Generations

Amaury Laridon¹, Wim Thiery¹, Rosa Pietroiusti¹, Joeri Rogelj¹, Chris Smith¹, Carl-Friedrich Schleussner², Inka Menke², Jacob Schewe³

¹Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussel, Brussel, Belgium. ²IIASA, Laxenbourg, Austria. ³Potsdam Institute for Climate Research, Potsdam, Germany

Abstract

The Permian Delaware Tight, located in Texas (USA), is the largest carbon bomb on Earth. Carbon bombs are defined as 425 fossil fuel megaprojects, of which about 60% are already under exploitation. With potential emissions of 27.8 GtCO₂, the Permian Delaware Tight would release three-quarters of total annual global CO₂ emissions. Exploiting this single project would consume more than ten percent of the remaining global carbon budget for limiting global warming to 1.5 °C by the end of the century. Considering all carbon bombs, the cumulative potential emissions from these coal, gas, and oil fields exceed at least twice the remaining global carbon budget consistent with the Paris Agreement.

Within the *Source2Suffering project*, we develop a methodology to translate the greenhouse gas emissions of any project into lifetime climate impacts. Our modeling framework estimates—while explicitly accounting for uncertainty—the number of extreme events, such as heatwaves, droughts, or floods, that current and future generations are likely to experience as a result of these specific emissions. Crucially, the method also captures how these impacts vary not only across generations but also among populations in different countries, thereby reflecting unequal exposure to climate risks. This unequal exposure is represented in the model as the combined outcome of two factors: first, the physical dynamics of global warming, which generate disproportionately higher impacts in the Global South; and second, the demographic reality that the majority of the world's population—including most future generations—resides in these regions.

Assessing Coastal Dynamics under Climate Stressors: Evidence from UAV, Satellite, and Geophysical Data in Ghana

Baah Asare-Bediako^{1,2}, Cyril Boateng^{1,2,3}, Jeffrey Armah Aryee⁴

¹Department of Physics, KNUST, Kumasi, Ghana. ²West African Geophysics Lab, Kumasi, Ghana.

³Caburu Company Ltd, Accra, Ghana. ⁴Department of Meteorology and Climate Science, KNUST, Kumasi, Ghana

Abstract

Coastal erosion along Ghana's eastern shoreline poses escalating risks to human settlements, infrastructure, and ecosystems under the combined pressures of sea-level rise, wave extremes, and human interventions. Towns such as Keta and Anyanui have experienced retreat rates exceeding 2 m/yr, threatening livelihoods and amplifying climate vulnerability. This study presents the first integrated assessment in Ghana that combines multi-temporal satellite observations, UAV photogrammetry, and subsurface geophysical analysis to investigate both surface and structural controls on shoreline change. Long-term analysis of Landsat imagery (1986–2024) revealed divergent erosion–accretion trends across three coastal zones, reflecting the influence of sea defenses, sediment dynamics, and estuarine processes. High-resolution UAV surveys in 2025 captured rapid short-term variability, including localized retreat exceeding 40 m near seawall boundaries and significant accretion in less engineered sections. Volumetric analyses confirmed contrasting sediment budgets, while aeromagnetic lineament mapping suggested a structural influence on erosion susceptibility. By integrating Earth observation with geophysical methods, this work demonstrates how multiple drivers, climatic, geomorphic, and structural, interact to shape coastal vulnerability. The findings provide insights for anticipating climate-induced shoreline change and support evidence-based strategies for sustainable coastal management in West Africa and beyond.

Governance, policy and society mediating impacts II

Explaining Environmental Successes and Failures

Malcolm Fairbrother

Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. Institute for Futures Studies, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Despite decades of scientific research on the potentially catastrophic consequences of global climate change, the world has thus far failed to take serious action to change course and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. What explains humanity's abysmal performance in meeting this critical challenge? Human societies have performed far better in confronting other environmental problems: protecting the ozone layer, mitigating acid rain, improving air quality, and reducing people's exposure to dioxins and lead. In this talk I will consider different environmental outcomes in comparative perspective, and conditions leading to better versus worse outcomes, once scientific evidence of anthropogenic harms became clear. I will argue, contrary to other perspectives, that there have been two key differences between climate change and more successfully mitigated problems. First, polluting industries have resisted regulation more strongly in the case of climate change, with exceptional political efforts to deny and delay in turn due to the uniquely unconvertible character of key industrial assets. Second, in the success cases, ordinary people were asked to make little or no material sacrifice, whereas in the case of climate change there is more of a price to be paid--and most people appear unwilling to pay a price, even though it is modest, because of their distrust. I will conclude by elaborating implications for how we should seek to resolve the climate crisis, given the need to avoid the terrible impacts that will follow if we fail to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.

Bridging Earth System Science and Earth System Governance

Rakhyun E. Kim¹, Eric Galbraith², Louis Kotzé³

¹Utrecht University, Utrecht, Netherlands. ²Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.

³Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Abstract

This study explains why the persistent divide between Earth system science (ESS) and Earth system governance (ESG) constrains both understanding of Earth-system change and the capacity to respond effectively, and what would make collaboration work in practice. We conceptualise the divide as a coupling failure: governance is rarely treated as an endogenous, feedback-generating component of Earth-system dynamics, while Earth-system change often enters governance research mainly as contextual constraint rather than as a dynamically coupled process. This disconnect creates predictable blind spots, from governance-driven nonlinear dynamics and implementation gaps that shape real-world trajectories to misalignment between scenarios and policy realities and transition pathways that prove politically and socially brittle. To move beyond generic calls for interdisciplinarity, we draw on a targeted survey of ESS and ESG researchers about cross-community collaboration, perceived barriers, and credible solutions. Four findings stand out: (1) collaboration is widely valued but often experienced as ineffective, with high transaction costs and limited payoff; (2) barriers cluster into epistemic frictions (problem framing, standards of evidence), institutional constraints (funding, publishing, career incentives), and relational gaps (networks, shared language, sustained spaces); (3) perceived hierarchies—where governance scholarship is treated as instrumental or secondary—shape which questions count; and (4) respondents converge on solutions centred on durable exchange infrastructures, joint projects and co-produced outputs, and shared frameworks, but stress that recognition and reward systems must shift for integrative work to scale. We discuss implications for research practice and enabling institutions, and develop an agenda of pathways for sustained ESS–ESG relational convergence.

Climate change impacts: perspectives for a global harmonized law?

Claudia Milli

Ca Foscari, Venice, Italy, Italy

Abstract

The research addresses the issue of climate change through a comparative analysis of judicial experiences, highlighting how the inadequacy of scientific and technical knowledge is overcome by resorting to the transplantation of legal models. The regulatory framework is multi-level and fragmented, and traditional environmental law is often inapplicable to climate damage due to its global, widespread nature and the difficulty of establishing a causal link. To overcome these challenges, we see the influence of the US experience, in particular the Public Trust Doctrine (PTD), which seeks to impose a fiduciary duty on the government to protect resources such as the atmosphere for future generations. This trend towards the circulation of models is favoured by the global nature of the phenomenon. Climate change litigation is a growing global trend, often aimed at influencing policy and regulation (“regulation through litigation”). Although a global model of action is developing, in which human rights violations are constantly invoked to overcome obstacles such as the separation of powers, the results are not uniform. The establishment of a global right is hampered by the peculiarities of individual legal systems. Consequently, the successful outcome of legal actions is closely linked to the characteristics of the legal process specific to each local jurisdiction.

Conflict, Disasters, and Social Trust: A Cross-national Analysis in Southeast Asia

Rosvold Elisabeth Lio¹, Dellmuth Lisa², Jonsson Evelina²

¹Department of Sociology and Political Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway. ²Department of Economic History and International Relations, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Social or interpersonal trust is central to societies' capacity to mitigate conflict and disaster impacts. However, we know little about the complex relationships between climate-related disasters, co-occurring violent conflict, and social trust. The conventional assumption is that protracted conflict deepens divisive lines in societies, which are hard to overcome. This article proposes an alternative mechanism, privileging climate-related disasters as a moderator influencing both conflict and social trust, as well as the relationship between conflict and trust. Using a novel subnational-level dataset on conflict, disasters, and trust in four major countries in Southeast Asia, the article shows that climate-related disasters function as a moderator, while granting weak support for the conventional wisdom. The article suggests three broader implications: climatic disasters have more far-reaching consequences for foundational, social trust, than previously understood; political efforts to alleviate disasters can simultaneously lead to a strengthening of benign social ties; and a comparative cross-country analysis is central to uncovering the complex relations between conflict, disasters, and social trust.

Climate Change Adaptation of the Railway Sector.

Michelle Ochsner

Lund University, Lund, Sweden. K2 - The National Knowledge Centre for Collective Mobility, Lund, Sweden

Abstract

Railways play an important role in climate mitigation, offering a low-carbon, energy-efficient alternative for transporting people and goods. However, their reliability is increasingly threatened by extreme weather events, whose frequency and intensity are amplified by climate change. This research examines the impact of weather on railway operations and infrastructure, as well as the influence of planning and governance frameworks on the sector's capacity to adapt.

Using an interdisciplinary and mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative analyses of weather-related disruptions and infrastructure vulnerabilities with qualitative insights from interviews and workshops. The findings show that current vulnerabilities in Sweden are most pronounced during winter, with low temperatures, snow, and high winds causing significant disruptions. However, future climate projections suggest a shift towards risks associated with high temperatures and increased precipitation.

While a range of technical and organisational adaptation strategies exist, their implementation is hindered by persistent barriers, including funding constraints, knowledge gaps, legislative ambiguity, and a lack of prioritisation. The research also highlights the value of international experiences in informing more dynamic and flexible adaptation pathways.

This work contributes to the understanding of climate adaptation in the railway sector by providing empirical evidence on weather impacts, identifying key barriers and enablers of adaptation, and offering insights into planning frameworks that support long-term resilience. It underscores the importance of integrating scientific knowledge into policy and practice to ensure that railways remain safe, reliable, and climate-resilient in the decades to come.

Unsustainability as Deep Uncertainty: Rethinking Risk Governance for Climate-Extreme Futures

Shruti Kashyap

Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden. Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Climate extremes expose decision-makers to a widening class of unsustainability risks (systemic and deeply uncertain interactive threats that emerge from ecological overshoot, social instability, and accelerating regulatory and market shifts). These risks challenge the foundational assumptions of established risk-based decision frameworks (e.g.: ISO 31000). They require a re-assessment of cost-benefit and probabilistic models that guide risk and resilience-oriented decision-making.

Drawing on contemporary risk theory, legal developments, and management literature, this paper presents a conceptual framework for decision-making under climate extremes and related environmental risks. This rests on a theorization of unsustainability risks as conditions characterized by weak knowledge, non-linearity, and structural interdependence between actors and also systems.

The paper offers three contributions. First, it conceptualizes unsustainability risks as knowledge-poor, consequence-rich conditions where scientific models indicate severe potential outcomes but decision-making is constrained by a low ability to specify likelihoods or probabilities. Second, it analyses how prevailing governance architectures, including compliance-based sustainability regimes and fragmented regulatory mandates, may inadvertently amplify vulnerability by privileging narrow risk metrics over systemic understandings. Third, it proposes a governance and management approach grounded in principles of robustness, precaution, and anticipatory capacity as well as capability. This includes reframing extant risk-based decision-making frameworks and processes to foreground uncertainty characterization and integrate knowledge-strength assessments. Such integration necessarily encompasses decision structures and institutional mechanisms.

This work provides a conceptual toolkit for decision-making under irreducible uncertainty, where organizational and policy choices have long-term systemic implications. It supports a shift from reactive risk governance towards proactive resilience-focused coordination and action.

Climate attribution, forecasting, monitoring, and projections for Impacts II

Is climate change accelerating soil moisture droughts? Evidence from a global attribution analysis.

Aristeidis Koutroulis, Manolis Grillakis, Athanasios Tsilimigkras

Technical University of Crete, School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Chania, Greece

Abstract

Agricultural and ecological drought trends are rising in many regions more clearly than meteorological drought, yet attribution studies remain dominated by meteorological indices, leaving a critical gap for indicators closer to societal impacts. Beyond how often, how strong, and how long droughts occur, an increasingly consequential dimension is how quickly they develop. Concerns are growing that climate change may be accelerating drought onset and propagation, with direct implications for early warning and risk management. We assess this hypothesis using an ISIMIP Global Water multi-model ensemble. Two coordinated experiments are contrasted: (i) a stationary-climate counterfactual with observed transient direct human forcings and (ii) reanalysis simulations that include climate-related and direct human forcings to assess the historical long-term changes attributed to climate change. Soil-moisture anomalies serve as our drought impact proxy. We derive both conventional drought features of frequency, severity, and duration, and introduce a development-speed metric quantifying the rate of intensification from drought onset to a specific severity level within the 1m soil depth. We detect an attributable climate change signal in both the speed and intensity of soil moisture droughts. Hotspots of accelerated and more aggressive development occur in the South American rainforests, Europe, and southern Australia, whereas parts of the elevated East African region exhibit muted changes. These findings challenge our capacity for drought hazard prediction and motivate monitoring, anticipatory allocation, and operational early action triggers that explicitly account for the pace at which drought conditions escalate.

Impact Attribution for Climate Law: The Case of Storm Irene

Mireia Ginesta¹, Shirin Ermis^{2,1}, Benjamin Franta¹, Rupert Stuart-Smith¹

¹Oxford Sustainable Law Programme, Oxford, United Kingdom. ²Atmospheric, Oceanic, and Planetary Physics, Department of Physics, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

Abstract

People are increasingly turning to courts to combat climate crisis. In the early 2000s, fewer than 10 climate change litigation cases had been filed globally. By 2024, this number has grown to over 2,500, with more than half originating in the United States. Some of these cases rely on extreme weather attribution science to link damages to anthropogenic climate change. Developing rigorous, legally useful assessments of damage attributable to climate change is an increasingly pressing need.

We present a framework for forecast-based impact attribution which can link physically consistent hazards to impacts, providing evidence for legal cases and climate cost recovery laws. As a case study, we analyze the severe impacts of Storm Irene in August 2011 when it was undergoing extratropical transition in the north-eastern USA. In the state of Vermont, Irene caused rainfall of up to 180 mm within a few hours, leading to fluvial and pluvial flooding with catastrophic consequences that caused \$850 million in economic damages. By integrating an operational weather forecast model (ECMWF's IFS) and a hydrological/hydrodynamic models (Deltares' Wflow and SFINCS) with economic impact assessments (FEMA's Hazus), we assess the extent to which these damages can be attributed to anthropogenic climate change.

This research underscores the potential of interdisciplinary attribution methodologies to enhance the scientific basis for judicial adjudication on climate change and climate law-making.

Attribution of aviation impacts during the 3 May 2025 Western Europe hailstorm

Davide Faranda¹, Tommaso Alberti²

¹IPSL/CNRS, Gif-sur-Yvette, France. ²INGV, Rome, Italy

Abstract

On 3 May 2025, a severe hailstorm impacted Paris and parts of Western Europe, causing widespread flight cancellations, diversions, and ground delays across several major airports, including Paris–Charles de Gaulle and Orly. This event highlighted the growing vulnerability of the aviation sector to convective hazards. We investigate the meteorological drivers of the storm and assess the role of anthropogenic climate change in modulating aviation impacts using an analogue-based attribution framework applied to ERA5 reanalysis. The synoptic configuration featured a cut-off low interacting with a surface cold front, shortly after an early-season heatwave that created a highly unstable thermodynamic environment. We identify atmospheric circulation analogues in past (1974–1999) and recent (1999–2024) climates, and evaluate associated changes in parameters relevant for aviation hazards such as convective available potential energy, vertical wind shear, freezing-level height, and low-level temperature. Hail probability and size are estimated with two models: a logistic formulation based on convective instability and shear, and a new hail growth model tailored to European environments. Results show that present-day conditions produce significantly higher hail probabilities and larger hailstones than analogous synoptic patterns in the past climate. These thermodynamic shifts translate into a higher likelihood of severe hail encounters along flight paths and greater potential for airport disruptions. Our findings suggest that anthropogenic warming has increased the intensity of hail-producing environments in the region, contributing to the enhanced aviation impacts observed during the 3 May 2025 storm.

The future of European outdoor summer sports through the lens of 50 years of the Tour de France

Ivana Cvijanovic¹, James Begg², Malcolm Mistry³, Desislava Petrova⁴, Chloe Brimicombe⁵, Benjamin Sultan¹

¹ESPACE-DEV, Univ Montpellier, IRD, Montpellier, France. ²Galson Sciences Limited, Oakham, United Kingdom. ³London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ⁴Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal), Barcelona, United Kingdom. ⁵Royal Meteorological Society, Reading, United Kingdom

Abstract

We consider how excessive heat, due to changing climate conditions, could affect the safety of summer sport competitions in Europe. We use the example of the world's largest bicycle race, the Tour de France, to assess the changes in heat stress over the past five decades and discuss extreme heat protocols, data gaps and safe ways forward.

We show that although July heat stress values have been increasing throughout France, the actual Tour de France race dates have so far been fortunate to avoid the days featuring the highest heat. For example, although July hourly heat stress values for Paris and its surroundings have crossed the high-risk threshold (Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) > 28 °C) on five occasions over the last 50 years, four of which have occurred since 2014, this has so far not happened on the date of the Tour de France stage through Paris. Between 1974 and 2023, the hottest Parisian stage finish was in July 2002, with the hourly WBGT maximum of 26.8 °C staying just below the high-risk mark.

Considering the historical heat stress values, we find that the episodes of dangerous heat levels exceeding 28 °C WBGT, have been most common around Toulouse, Pau, Bordeaux, Nimes and Perpignan. However, locations like Paris and Lyon are starting to cross the 28 °C WBGT threshold more frequently, becoming new heat stress hotspots. Morning hours are the safest part of the day while the high heat stress can persist late into the afternoon hours.

Impact-Based Seasonal Forecasting of Drought and Extreme Rainfall in Europe

Babak Mohammadi, Wei Yang, Ilias Pechlivanidis

SMHI, Norrköping, Sweden

Abstract

Impact-based forecasting (IbF) has emerged as a critical approach for translating hydro-meteorological predictions into actionable risk information for decision-makers. Here we present SMHI's pan-European IbF service for assessing drought and extreme rainfall risks with lead times of up to seven months. The seasonal hydro-meteorological forecasting service, which is based on the E-HYPE hydrological model forced with bias-adjusted ECMWF SEAS5 meteorological forecasts, integrates forecasted hazard indicators with exposure data through a risk matrix methodology. Drought hazard indicators, including the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) and Standardized Streamflow Index (SSI), are computed at multiple temporal scales (1, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 months) to capture both short- and long-term hydro-meteorological droughts. Additionally, extreme rainfall indicators, R10mm (days with precipitation ≥ 10 mm), R20mm (≥ 20 mm), R95p (days exceeding the 95th percentile), and R99p (days exceeding the 99th percentile) are calculated for each lead month to comprehensively capture both moderate and severe rainfall events. A risk matrix is further derived by combining the severity and probability of occurrence of each hazard indicator with the exposure data, including population density, forest and agricultural land-use density, air-traffic intensity near airport, road traffics and vulnerability etc. This innovative approach enables the classification of future impacts into distinct risk categories ranging from low through medium to high risk levels, providing important information for anticipatory action planning and resource allocation. The resulting IbF early warning system offers first responders and stakeholders a pan-European seasonal outlook of potential risks, supporting proactive disaster risk reduction, agricultural planning, and water resource management.

Cascading impacts of precipitation variability in North Africa under climate change.

Meryem Tanarhte¹, Andries J. De Vries², Georgios Zittis³, Moshe Armon⁴, Assaf Hochman⁴, Andreas Karpatis³, Dimitris Kaskaoutis⁵, Samira Khodayar⁶

¹Faculty of Science and Technology- University Hassa II, Casablanca, Morocco. ²Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland. ³Climate and Atmosphere Research Center (CARE-C), The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus. ⁴Fredy and Nadine Hermann Institute of Earth Sciences, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem, Israel. ⁵Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani, Greece. ⁶Mediterranean Center for Environmental Studies (CEAM), Valencia, Spain

Abstract

North Africa faces extreme water scarcity and high climate sensitivity, with precipitation patterns exhibiting considerable spatial and temporal variability as a result of both natural and human-induced climate forcings. Over the past 50 years, the region has experienced severe droughts and floods, with devastating socio-economic consequences. We examine observed trends and variability patterns from recent observational datasets, alongside model projections from CMIP6, to identify emerging shifts in seasonal precipitation distribution and extremes. The contrasting trends between the Mediterranean and Saharan zones, coupled with strong interannual variability, significantly influence the frequency and severity of hydrological extremes. These dynamics have significant cascading impacts on food security (wheat production), energy production and policy (hydroelectrical), water resource management, and overall economic growth, particularly in fragile oasis ecosystems that connect Mediterranean and Saharan zones. Additionally, Saharan precipitation variability significantly influences dust and water cycle dynamics, impacting both regional and global systems. Climate projections suggest that future precipitation may decrease by as much as 40% along the Mediterranean coast, while the Sahara could experience an increase in precipitation, potentially indicating an emerging "greening" trend within the desert region. Persistent data gaps, limited long-term observations, and uncertainties in regional climate projections remain major challenges for impact assessment.

Panel on Immobility

Climate Change, Aspirations to Stay and Climate Immobility in Mozambique

Carlos Shenga^{1,2}, Lorraine Howe², Amélia Macome²

¹University Joaquim Chissano, Maputo, Mozambique. ²Centre for Research on Governance and Development, Maputo, Mozambique

Abstract

Human mobility and climate change have been approached in a linear relationship, suggesting that once severely affected by climate hazards, humans migrate to other locations. This approach not only produced warnings about the threat of climate-induced mass migrations but also presented oversimplified models and assumptions, as it only considers moving away as the only effect that climate change may induce in people, ignoring that many might be trapped and/or decide to stay. Equally, it does not consider other factors that may account for variation in climate mobilities – that is, the decision to move or to stay when people are affected by climate hazards. By employing 2025 public opinion data with a representative, random, stratified probability sample of 416 individuals and multivariate regression models, we found that *climate change* explains very little of climate mobilities. But *aspirations to stay* mattered. People with a strong preference to stay in their home community (due to attachment to place, positive future, community services, neighbourhood safety, happiness and satisfaction, commitment to people and institutions, religion and culture, and family, cultural heritage and personal identity, and kept from negative influences) tend to be immobile compared to others. By probing the drivers of climate immobility, particularly aspirations to stay, we found that *capabilities to stay* and *needs*, followed by *adaptation*, explained climate mobilities. But *intersectionality* and then *dignity* also play their role.

Climate Thresholds and Gendered Immobility: Insights from Ghana's Volta Delta

Mumuni Abu, Charles Agyei-Asabere, Samuel Codjoe N.A

University of Ghana, Accra, N/A, Ghana

Abstract

The interplay between gender, immobility, and climate change is central to understanding differentiated vulnerabilities within environmentally fragile regions. This study conceptualises immobility as a dynamic and context-dependent condition, shaped by social, economic, and environmental thresholds, and mediated by an individual's mobility decision-making capacity. Focusing on the Volta Delta of Ghana - a region highly exposed to floods, sea-level rise, and coastal erosion - the research investigates how gendered norms and structural inequalities influence the capacity to respond to climate risks. Using survey data from 691 individuals, we examine how gender differences in mobility decision-making intersect with climate-induced thresholds to shape patterns of immobility. Findings indicate that women generally exhibit lower mobility decision-making capacity compared to men, constraining both their adaptive responses and resilience in the face of environmental stressors. At the same time, men engaged in ecosystem-based livelihoods such as fishing and farming experience place-based attachments that can lead to involuntary immobility. As climatic thresholds intensify - through flooding, erosion, and salinization - immobility may transition into migration; however, the capacity to move remains unevenly distributed along gender lines. The study underscores the need to incorporate gendered social differentiation into climate adaptation and mobility policies. Understanding how gender relations mediate the conditions and thresholds of movement within deltaic regions provides critical insight into why some individuals remain in place despite escalating climate risks, and how interventions can equitably support both mobile and immobile populations in building climate resilience.

Immobility in the Context of Climate Change

Adelle Thomas^{1,2}, Arunima Sircar², Mumuni Abu³, Emily Boyd⁴, Patricia Pinho⁵, Lorraine Howe⁶, Carlos Shenga⁶, Murray Scown⁴

¹NRDC, Washington, DC, United States. ²Climate Analytics, New York, NY, United States. ³Regional Institute for Population Studies, University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana. ⁴Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ⁵Instituto de Pesquisa Ambiental da Amazônia, Brasília, Brazil. ⁶Centre for Research on Governance and Development, Maputo, Mozambique

Abstract

In the face of escalating climate risks and impacts, the majority of people will not be able to move, will choose not to move, or may perhaps temporarily move and return to their homes. Understanding immobility in the context of climate change is thus essential to support the development of equitable and effective adaptation strategies and the resilience of people and communities that remain in at-risk locations. In this review, we provide a critical assessment of the growing literature on immobility. We draw on a range of critical research case studies to explore how immobility is experienced in different geographical contexts, including Africa, South America, Europe, and small islands. We identify areas for much needed further research on immobility, including governance of immobility; further expansion on connections between immobility, justice, and loss and damage; and the feasibility of immobility as a response to increasing climate impacts and risks.

The Social Production of Immobility in Coastal Sweden: Determinants and Mechanisms in the Context of Sea Level Rise

Emily Boyd^{1,2,3}, Viggo Forssblad¹, Emilia Ganslandt^{1,2}, Emilie Greve Pobiega¹, Elisabeth Schill^{1,2}, Joyce Soo¹

¹Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Lund, Sweden. ³Beijer Institute Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Coastal communities are increasingly exposed to sea level rise and erosion, yet many residents remain in place despite escalating risks. This paper reframes immobility not as a personal or passive choice, but as a socially and politically produced condition, shaped by intersecting social factors. Drawing on critical environmental justice theory (Pellow, 2025) and an intersectional lens, we situate immobility in areas prone to extreme coastal events within broader social, historical, and governance systems that determine whose lives, properties, and futures are protected or lost. Focusing on Falsterbo näset in Southern Sweden, we combine qualitative interviews, survey, policy analysis, and historical context to examine the mechanisms and determinants of voluntary and constrained immobility. Building on Watts and Bohle's (1993) notion of vulnerability as a social process, we identify intersecting historical, economic, and governance trajectories, including property regimes, social networks, economic drivers, institutional frameworks, and local norms that actively produce conditions that reproduce immobility. Framing immobility as socially mediated highlights how climate hazards intersect with inequality, place attachment, and social identities. The findings challenge the assumption that relocation is a straightforward adaptive response and emphasize the need for equitable, context-sensitive adaptation strategies. While grounded in Sweden, the insights are of global relevance, illustrating how intersectional social structures shape human responses to climate change. This research contributes to debates on climate justice, adaptation policy, and the ethical dimensions of mobility, emphasizing that vulnerability and immobility transcends wealth, requiring attention to the intersecting social mechanisms that enable or constrain movement.

Staying Despite the Storm: Intersectional Immobility and Climate Injustice in the Amazon Coastal Zone

Patricia Pinho¹, Olivia Benin¹, Larissa Castro², Ray Alves¹, Carolina Guyot³

¹Instituto de Pesquisa Ambiental da Amazônia, São Paulo, Brazil. ²Instituto de Pesquisa Ambiental da Amazônia, Belém, Brazil. ³Instituto de Pesquisa Ambiental da Amazônia, Brasília, Brazil

Abstract

As climate extremes intensify across the Amazon's coastal zone, not all residents are able—or willing—to leave. This study examines the phenomenon of immobility through an intersectional lens, using data from over 200 interviews and surveys conducted in three municipalities in Pará state, Brazil. Results reveal that while 70% of respondents report experiencing climate impacts, especially flooding and extreme heat, nearly half believe these changes are not driven by human activities, reflecting a concerning disconnection between lived experience and climate literacy. Intersectional analysis reveals that women, lower-income residents, and those with less formal education are more likely to remain despite escalating risks. For example, women express higher psychological stress and greater concerns about food insecurity, while men more often report material losses. Those with lower income and education levels are disproportionately affected by housing damage, health complications, and lack of access to adaptation resources. Despite exposure to hazards, most residents express a deep sense of “rootedness”—cultural, spiritual, and social ties that anchor them to place. This raises critical questions for adaptation policy and climate finance: how can justice, dignity, and resilience be supported for those who stay? By challenging the mobility bias in climate adaptation frameworks, this study urges a shift toward understanding why people don't move and how to protect them in place.

POSTERS

Societal adaptation and justice dimensions

Thailand's Rising Water Budget: The Challenge of Shifting from Reactive Spending to Proactive Climate Adaptation via the National Adaptation Plan (NAP)

Pongsak Suttinon¹, Piyatida Ruangrassamee¹, Supattra Visessri^{1,2}, Chalermchon Satirapod^{3,4}

¹Department of Water Resources Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand. ²Center of Excellence in Disaster and Risk Management Information Systems, Faculty of Engineering, Bangkok, Thailand. ³Department of Survey Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand. ⁴Mapping and Positioning from Space (MAPS) technology research center, Faculty of Engineering, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

Abstract

Thailand ranks among the world's most climate-vulnerable countries, placed ninth globally in terms of exposure and impact. The nation faces recurring and increasingly severe floods and droughts that pose significant socio-economic and environmental risks. In response, the Thai government has substantially scaled up its public investment in water management, allocating over USD 3 billion annually—approximately USD 3.7 billion in FY2024 and USD 4.05 billion in FY2025—representing nearly one-fifth of the national investment budget. However, despite this substantial financial commitment, water management in Thailand remains predominantly reactive, with responses largely focused on post-disaster recovery and short-term infrastructure measures. Moreover, institutional fragmentation across multiple agencies continues to hinder integrated and climate-informed planning. To address these systemic challenges and strengthen long-term resilience, Thailand has formulated the National Adaptation Plan (NAP) as the national framework for integrating adaptation strategies across sectors. Water Resources Management is identified as one of the six priority vulnerable sectors under the NAP. The framework calls for a paradigm shift from reactive infrastructure spending toward strategic, climate-proof, and resilience-oriented investments. Central to this transition is the promotion of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) and Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA) or Nature-based Solutions (NbS), emphasizing international collaboration and evidence-based planning to enhance national water security and adaptive capacity.

Climate Change, Cattle Violence and State Politics in Ghana

Akwasi Maama

College of Natural Resources and Environmental Governance, Kumasi, Ghana

Abstract

In the 1900s, cattle herders from the Sahel region migrated into the southern Guinea savannah belt in search of pasture and returned when climatic conditions improved. Severe Sahelian drought in the 1960s, however, caused many herders to move south from the Sahel to settle in the savannah and even the forest belts of coastal countries like Ghana. In Ghana, herders (Fulani ethnicity) first settled in north-eastern cities and later moved towards the south. By the late 1990s, cattle production formed part of Ghana's crop-based rural economy, attracting the participation of national elites who employed the services of migrant herders to care for their livestock. However, since the early 2000s, severe confrontations and violent extremism have occurred between arable farmers and cattle herders. The government of Ghana constructed a 272-ha ranch in eastern Ghana to keep cattle at one location and away from farmlands. Initially, there was little local opposition, allowing the ranch to be established and to experience a large growth in cattle population. However, the ranch began to experience difficulties. This paper explores why the government's ranching intervention has not worked, by focusing on how it is being implemented in practice, and the nature of the conflict it generates. The article shows how the development of the ranch manifested as part of the political regime of the New Patriotic Party; the process enhanced the party's political legitimacy but did not provide pastoralists with enough forage and security. The article illuminates the practical issues surrounding the establishment of cattle ranches.

Bridging Climate Adaptation Gaps through Fiscal Policy Framework for Agricultural Resilience in Northeastern Bangladesh

Mukhtarun Islam, Sabyasachi Niloy

Sylhet Agricultural University, Sylhet, Sylhet, Bangladesh

Abstract

Climate change poses unprecedented threats to agricultural productivity in northeastern Bangladesh through extreme weather events and hydro-climatic vulnerability. This study employs mixed-methods approach combining 40 years climate trend analysis (1984-2023), household surveys (n =180), focus group discussions, and expert interviews to assess climate impacts, adaptation practices, and institutional barriers in Sunamganj District.

Results reveal shifting seasonal patterns, substantial rainfall variability (CV=94.93%), and rising mean temperatures (25.13°C to 25.40°C). Farmers reported that direct agricultural losses including increased crop failures, disease prevalence, and pest invasions. Current adaptation strategies like intensified fertilizer application and irrigation prove frequently maladaptive. Critical barriers include institutional weaknesses, prohibitive input costs, limited localized climate information access, and recurrent natural disasters.

This research identifies a critical gap in localized Climate Information Services (CIS) provision and proposes a strategic fiscal policy framework. Recommendations include expanding index based crop insurance, deploying automated weather stations for decentralized data collection, and providing targeted subsidies for solar powered irrigation and drought resistant seeds. Crucially, the study emphasizes integrating indigenous knowledge with modern scientific tools to enhance climate service accuracy and cultural relevance.

Implementing this framework requires inter-ministerial coordination to overcome institutional silos and fostering public-private partnerships to strengthen resilience. The phased intervention strategy spans immediate risk mitigation to long-term institutional capacity building, ensuring food security and sustainable development aligned with global climate goals.

This farmer-centric framework provides actionable policy pathways for accelerating climate adaptation in smallholder agricultural systems, ensuring food security and contributing to sustainable development goals and international climate commitments.

Just Adaptation in German Cities? Assessing Social Justice Dimensions in Urban Climate Adaptation Strategies

Friederike Hippe

Universität Augsburg, Augsburg, Germany. Institut für ökologische Wirtschaftsforschung, Berlin, Germany

Abstract

The consequences of climate change and society's ability to adapt are distributed unequally, with marginalised groups particularly vulnerable due to higher exposure and limited adaptive capacities. Considering social justice is therefore essential to address different vulnerabilities and to prevent adaptation measures from reinforcing existing inequalities. In the process of designing and implementing adaptation strategies, cities play a crucial role as central actors.

Research on social justice in municipal climate adaptation—especially in Germany—is still in its early stages. This study examines for the first time the question: To what extent are recognition, procedural, and distributive justice considered in German municipalities? Ten major cities, identified as particularly ambitious in climate adaptation, are analysed through qualitative content analysis of their municipal adaptation strategies. The study contributes methodologically by developing a coding framework tailored to the German municipal context and empirically by identifying current approaches and gaps regarding social justice in climate adaptation.

The findings reveal significant shortcomings in all three justice dimensions. There is a lack of socio-economic and intersectional perspectives on vulnerability, as well as insufficient recognition of its causes. While participatory procedures are common, they are rarely targeted specifically at vulnerable groups, increasing the risk of perpetuating existing inequalities. Regarding distributive justice, the analysis shows that the distributional impacts of adaptation measures on vulnerable groups are as well scarcely considered. For example, issues such as the question of allocation of costs and benefits as well as the risk of maladaptation are largely absent.

Reengineering Resilience: A Justice-Centered Framework for Climate-Resilient Public-Private Partnerships in Flood-Prone Urban Africa

Mohammed Rabiou Suleiman¹, Ifeoluwa Jegede²

¹University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu, Nigeria. ²Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria

Abstract

Urban flooding, intensified by climate change, disproportionately affects informal settlements across the Global South. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) are often promoted as scalable solutions, yet their implementation frequently neglects socio-institutional dynamics, resulting in inequitable outcomes and community resistance. This study asks: *Under what governance conditions can PPPs deliver climate-resilient infrastructure that is both effective and just?* Using Trademore Estate in Abuja, a chronically flood-prone urban community as a diagnostic case, we employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design integrating geospatial flood analysis, structured household surveys (n=220), and expert Policy Delphi panels (n=28). Our findings reveal that institutional fragmentation and pervasive “justice deficits”, including renter displacement and procedural exclusion, pose greater barriers than technical or financial constraints. We propose the Critical Governance-Risk Alignment Framework (CGRAF), a novel model synthesizing risk allocation, institutional theory, and justice principles. Methodologically, we introduce two applied tools: a PPP Viability Index and a Participatory Equity Assessment Protocol. These innovations offer policymakers a roadmap to: (i) Recalibrate PPP units into polycentric coordination hubs, (ii) Mandate equity audits in resilience infrastructure contracts, and (iii) Deploy blended finance to ensure bankability without sacrificing inclusivity. This research bridges the gap between engineering resilience and social justice. It offers a replicable, interdisciplinary blueprint for urban planners and development agencies to ensure climate adaptation fosters a sustainable and equitable future for the world’s most vulnerable urban residents.

Keywords: Public-Private Partnerships, Climate Resilience, Urban Flooding, Distributive Justice, Polycentric Governance, Climate Adaptation, Nigeria

Intersections of Ethnicity, Sense of Belonging, and Climate Displacement: How Generation Z Adapts to Rising Sea Levels in the Global South

Mohammadjavad Maghsooditilaki, Sharifah R.S. Dawood, Massoomeh Hedayatimarzbali

Universiti Sains Malaysia, Gelugor, Penang, Malaysia

Abstract

Abstract:

As sea levels continue to rise across Southeast Asia, Malaysia's coastal communities face mounting challenges that threaten both livelihoods and cultural heritage. This study investigates how Generation Z individuals from major and minor ethnic groups in Malaysia perceive and respond to climate-induced displacement. Using a qualitative, interview-based approach, it captures the lived experiences and adaptive strategies of young people in ethnically diverse coastal zones, including Malay, Chinese, Indian, and indigenous communities. Grounded in Social Identity Theory and the Community Resilience Framework, the research explores how ethnicity, sense of belonging, and collective attachment to place influence adaptive capacities. Findings reveal that the intention to stay or relocate is not uniformly perceived across ethnic groups—concerns about displacement are more evident in some families. In contrast, others express a strong desire to remain and adapt locally. Many Gen Z respondents display digital resilience, actively leveraging social media to reinforce social cohesion, exchange coping strategies, and foster motivation for climate action. These online networks have become critical spaces for sharing local knowledge, mobilizing awareness, and promoting solidarity across ethnic boundaries. By integrating these perspectives, the study contributes to debates on climate justice, youth agency, and inclusive resilience in the Global South, emphasizing the transformative power of social belonging and digital solidarity in shaping equitable adaptation pathways for multicultural societies.

Keyword:

Generation Z, Climate-Induced Displacement, Ethnicity, Sense of Belonging, Community Resilience, Social Media Trending

Gender Roles' Influence On Implementation And Outcomes Of Gender Equality Policies On Climate Adaptation In Kenya

Lynnah Mugotitsa

Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Budapest, Hungary

Abstract

Gender roles exert a substantial influence on individuals' experiences and adaptations to climate change. In numerous regions, such as Kenya, women are predominantly assigned household responsibilities, which constrain their participation in community decision-making and climate policy frameworks. This role may result in their marginalization within policy implementation processes, potentially neglecting their distinct needs and insights in climate adaptation. Despite advancements, gender assumptions—such as viewing women as a homogeneous vulnerable group—continue to hinder the comprehensive integration of gender perspectives in climate adaptation policies. Such assumptions can lead to policies that inadequately address women's specific needs and inadvertently perpetuate gender inequality. Moreover, in developing countries, policies often overlook the socio-cultural barriers that limit women's access to resources and decision-making platforms essential for effective climate adaptation. The study explore how gender roles' influence on implementation and outcomes of gender equality policies on climate adaptation in Kenya.

Governance, policy and society mediating impacts

Media, Metaphors, and Environmental Security: How Language Shapes the Climate Crisis

Sarvsureshth Dhammi

University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

The convergent nexus between media discourse, metaphorical framing, and environmental security is key to interpreting how societies build and react to the climate crisis. Under the paper titled "Media, Metaphors, and Environmental Security: How Language Shapes the Climate Crisis," a constructivist ecolinguistic framework is adopted to explore processes whereby media-based linguistic selection informs public opinion, political agendas, and security regimes around climate change. By analysing a wide continuum of international press, the study identifies commonly repeated metaphors, such as "war on climate change," "carbon footprint," and "planetary emergency", which shape environmental threat framing. Rather than simply framing the climate crisis as an existential security imperative, such constructions also restrict agency, responsibility, and urgency in public discourses. Under this paper, widespread militaristic and technocratic metaphors usually underlie state-centric and reactive security thinking to the detriment of cooperative, ecological, and community-based thinking. Through qualitative discourse analysis, the study illustrates how words constitute a social construction device in which meanings of "security" and "threat" are constantly in ecological and political discourses. Finally, the paper speaks to a necessity for linguistically inclusive and sustainability-sensitive constructions that support ecological equilibrium, shared responsibility, and long-term resilience. The study contributes to ecolinguistics and environmental security studies. It offers a prospect whereby media language change can underlie a fruitful climate communication agenda with a more efficient and empathetic character.

Key Words: Ecolinguistics, Constructivism, Environment Security, Climate Change and Media Discourse.

Profiling Climate-Change Leanings in Large Language Models

Murathan Kurfali^{1,2}, Joakim Nivre^{3,2}, Gabriele Messori^{4,2}

¹RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Department of Linguistics and Philology, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁴Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) are increasingly used in climate-related discourse analysis, yet their leanings on climate policy remain underexplored. In this ongoing study, we construct a climate-opinion survey sourced primarily from the European Investment Bank's (EIB) annual climate surveys (2019–2024). The EIB surveys are international polls that track public beliefs, priorities, and policy preferences on climate change. By removing items requiring personal action or local context, we compile an 89-item survey covering concepts like climate knowledge, policy preferences (taxes, bans, standards), adaptation vs. mitigation priorities, governance/trust.

A preliminary evaluation of the 89 items across nine instruction-tuned LLMs (1B–9B) shows broad agreement on basic climate facts (what climate change is, its main causes, and the largest emitters), on the view that climate change will remain a serious problem by mid-century, and on the necessity of financial measures (e.g., progressive carbon/wealth taxes and ending fossil-fuel subsidies). By contrast, models diverge on specific policy instruments—whether to use coercive transport/urban measures (e.g., banning short-distance flights, lowering speed limits), how to split costs (wealthier individuals vs. businesses vs. everyone), and whether the transition to a low-carbon economy should proceed only if inequality is addressed.

We believe that profiling LLM leanings in this way is crucial to guide future research where these models will be used as tools to analyze public discourse. By uncovering model-specific biases related climate change, we aim to inform model selection, prompt design, and bias mitigation in downstream tasks.

Assessing Heat Mitigation Potential from Green Transit-Oriented Development: A Case Study in Thu Duc District, Ho Chi Minh City.

Dieu Nguyen Thi Minh, Duyen Thieu Thi My

Institution of Geodesy, Technical University of Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Hessen, Germany

Abstract

Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) concepts focus on promoting diversity of land use and connectivity. However, these characteristics can also contribute to intensified Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. To approach ecological and environmental goals in urban planning, combining green urbanism principles with TOD development is considered a heat mitigation strategy. In the context of high-density development and increased mobility, Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) has been experiencing thermal discomfort as well as health issues related to heat exposure. This research assesses the potential for Green TOD development to improve local microclimate conditions in HCMC. A residential block in Thu Duc District is examined as a case study. ENVI-met simulation is employed to assess the cooling effect. The findings show that Green TOD supports its integration in climate-adaptive strategies in urban planning with various green transformation solutions.

Keywords: Green TOD, Urban Heat Island effect, heat mitigation, cooling effect, climate-adaptive strategies, green transformation.

Resources in Dispute: Rethinking Circularity in an Age of Climate Extremes

Rasa Zuzeviciute

NTNU- Industrial Economy and Technology Management, Trondheim, Norway

Abstract

This ongoing research explores how climate extremes influence the practical implementation of circular economy frameworks in Norwegian aquaculture. The study focuses on end-of-life plastic netting systems governed under Norway's new Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulation, investigating how climatic variability interacts with material continuity, regulatory design, and industrial adaptation. Preliminary analysis suggests that the ramifications of extreme weather—damage, stricter maintenance requirements, and changing logistical conditions—may indirectly strengthen large-scale operational models by demanding high levels of technical and financial capacity. Circularity thus appears not only as an environmental strategy but also as an adaptive mechanism that reorganizes access to resources and responsibilities. The project applies a relational systems approach combined with multi-criteria decision analysis to examine how circular transitions unfold under unstable conditions and how resilience is distributed across industrial and regulatory actors. By viewing resources as dynamic relations shaped by climate, infrastructure, and governance, the research seeks to clarify how climate extremes redefine what “circularity” means in practice for material governance in marine industries.

Emotional Responses to Drought in the Western Cape News Media

Seunghui Choi¹, Giuliano Di Baldassarre², Jonghun Kam¹

¹Pohang University of Science and Technology, Pohang, Korea, Republic of. ²Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Drought is a slow-onset hazard that gradually intensifies its impacts on society, often influencing both emotional reactions and social behavior. We aim to explore how emotional dynamics in drought-related news articles are linked to both meteorological drought severity and water management policies. This study examines emotional dynamics in news media during drought periods over 2015–2020 in the Western Cape, South Africa. In this study, drought-related news articles across multiple municipalities in the Western Cape were collected and quantified emotional content using AI-based text analysis. Among these, Cape Town consistently appeared as the most frequently mentioned locality, indicating its central role in media narratives and public discourse during the crisis. Among various time scales (3, 6, 9, and 12 months), the 12-month Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI-12) and Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI-12) showed the strongest correlation with the volume of drought-related news articles. Emotional responses in news coverage intensified most notably at water restriction level 3, indicating a sharp shift in media sentiment during that stage of the drought. Our findings suggest that news media not only reflect public concern but also shape emotional responses and water-use behavior. These insights underscore the value of integrating media-based emotional analysis into drought preparedness strategies and public engagement plans.

Foodsystems, crops, and ecosystem impacts

Farm-level economic impacts of climate change adaptations in cropping systems across Sweden

Hanna Sjulgård¹, Pia Nilsson², Riccardo Bommarco¹, Giulia Vico¹

¹Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden. ²University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

Abstract

Climate change poses increasing challenges to agriculture. Climate change adaptations by farmers are crucial to reduce both food and farm economic losses. Promising practices to mitigate the negative impact of extreme weather include crop diversification, keeping the soil covered for a longer period across the year, and cultivating more drought- and heat-resistant crops, such as autumn-sown crops instead of spring-sown crops. However, to what extent these practices affect the farm economy, negatively or positively, in the short and long-term, is not well understood.

Using data from official registries for all crop-specialized farms across Sweden for 2009–2022, we investigated how the economic outcomes of farms changes with diversity of their crops, share of overwintering crops, and share of autumn-sown cereals. At each farm, we also investigated whether the adoption of these practices contributed to reduced economic losses in the extreme year 2018 and at the same time improved the economy during 2015 – a year with favourable growing conditions. The company owners' age, gender, agricultural education and education level were included to account for differences in social responses.

Preliminary results show that a smaller economic loss in 2018 was related to a higher share of autumn-sown cereals in Dalarna County, higher crop diversity in Värmland County (central Sweden), and higher functional diversity in Skåne County (southern Sweden). However, in none of the 21 counties there was a relationship between the share of overwintering crops and the difference in economic outcome between 2018 and previous years.

Socio-Economic Impacts of Energy Transition in the Agriculture Sector of India

Rathna Kumar Tenneti, Trupti Mishra

Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Abstract

The International Energy Agency defines Energy Transition as the shift from fossil fuel energy sources to renewable and green energy sources (International Energy Agency, 2017). India has set an ambitious target of achieving net-zero emissions by 2070. The target can be achieved by taking effective steps of 'Energy Transition' in different sectors of its economy, particularly the ones with high energy intensity. The majority of India's population is engaged in the agricultural sector for livelihood. The energy transition in this sector will have large-scale implications for achieving the target of net-zero emissions. There have been efforts by the government to ease the energy transition in the agricultural sector. One such scheme focused on the energy-intensive irrigation activity in India is PM KUSUM (Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha Evam Utthaan Mahabhiyan). The scheme has three components and is implemented by both the central and state governments. In this study, we analyzed the impact of PM KUSUM in the state of Maharashtra to explain how energy transition through the PM KUSUM scheme is impacting the socio-economic indicators like health, education, livelihoods, income, housing, mobility, etc. in the agriculture households. We used mixed methods in this study. The scope of this study is much wider. We observed there are positive outcomes in income and livelihoods due to the implementation of the PM KUSUM scheme. We try to understand the relationship between energy transition in the agriculture sector and socio-economic impacts on the farmers in this paper.

Climate Extremes Driven Shifts in Crop Seasonality and Livelihood Vulnerability: A Case Study of Semi-Arid Rajasthan

Abhilasha Sevta, Milap Punia

Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, Delhi, India

Abstract

Climate extremes significantly amplify the sensitivity of rainfed agriculture regions, which are characterised by complex socio-economic conditions. In this study, rainfall and temperature extremes were assessed using the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) from 1961–2023 across the Rabi and Kharif seasons, coupled with crop seasonality analysis (Start and End of the season) using the MODIS Vegetation Indices 16-Day L3 Global 250m (MOD13Q1) product (2000–2023) in semi-arid North-East Rajasthan. The combined analysis resulted in the identification of exposure hotspots, which were further investigated through household survey of agricultural families categorised on landholding classes to evaluate livelihood vulnerability and adaptive capacity. *The results showed a significant rise in the Rabi rainfall, increased frequency of 1-day and 3-day extreme rainfall events, and increased intensity of very wet days alongside winter warming and an increase in night-time temperatures. Subsequently, shift in crop seasonality is also observed, with Kharif season sowing shifted early due to increased pre-monsoon rainfall and a decline in monsoon rainfall. Similarly, the Rabi season showed early harvest.* The primary survey revealed high vulnerability of small landholders. The economic status is the key factor shaping adaptation. This sensitivity is compounded by limited access to modern technologies, credit, and extension services. To reduce these risks, communities adopted early Rabi harvesting, seasonal migration, and shifts to the non-farm sector. At the same time, policy measures should prioritise climate-smart agriculture and locally grounded strategies to strengthen the livelihoods of especially small landholding communities.

Keywords: Climate extremes; Seasonality; Livelihood vulnerability

Health and healthcare impacts

Effect of air pollution on pregnancy outcome

Kiya Abagero¹, Rawleigh Howe¹, Alemseged Abdisa¹, Mahlet Yigeremu Yigeremu², Gurmesa Tura³, Ebba Malmqvist⁴

¹Armauer hansen research institute, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. ²Addis Ababa university, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. ³Jimma university, Jimma, Ethiopia. ⁴Lund university, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Abstract

Introduction: Air pollution is a leading global health risk, causing more premature deaths than AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis combined. Chronic exposure has been linked to adverse pregnancy outcomes, including preterm birth, low birth weight and intrauterine growth restriction. In Ethiopia, despite growing urbanization, evidence on the effects of air pollution on birth outcomes is scarce.

Objectives: To assess the impact of maternal exposure to ambient air pollution on birth outcomes using low-cost mobile application to track location and outcome data.

Methods: A prospective cohort study of 2,210 pregnant women is underway in Addis Ababa. Data are collected via a mobile phone app and conventional facility- and home-based methods. The app records participant location and birth outcomes, while citywide ground monitors provide air pollution data. Analyses will apply regression models, Bayesian multi-pollutant frameworks, mediation analyses, and multiple bias modeling.

Preliminary Results: As of now, 547 women have been enrolled from three hospitals, with 437 (79.8%) completing follow-up. Of these, 423 (96.8%) resulted in live births, 5 were stillbirths, 1 miscarriage, 4 low birthweight, and 2 preterm births. Mean birth weight was 3.37 kg. Cesarean section accounted for 58% of deliveries. Diabetes was reported in 5.8% of women, and nearly half (49.8%) relied on coal for cooking; 26.2% cooked in sleeping rooms. The result again shows high exposure to indoor and outdoor air pollution among study participants enrolled so far.

Collaborators: The project is funded by the Swedish Royal Academy of Science in collaboration with the Armauer Hansen Research Institute and NASA.

Wildfires and Birth Outcomes: Evidence from Spain

Risto Conte Keivabu¹, Maria Rubio Cabanez²

¹Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Rostock, Germany. ²CED, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract

Climate change is increasing fire-conducive weather conditions worldwide determining higher risks of wildfire exposure. Despite growing research on the impact of wildfires on health outcomes, studies on birth outcomes, socio-demographic heterogeneities and for the European context are lacking. This study examines the impact of wildfires on birth outcomes in Spain, a country facing multiple climate change-related health risks. We use Spanish administrative data covering approximately 3.5 million live births between 2008 and 2021. This dataset is combined with precise measurements of wildfire exposure based on data from the European Forest Fires Information System. We observe a decrease in birth weight and an increase in the probability of low birth weight and preterm birth due to wildfire exposure during pregnancy, with the effect concentrated in the first and third trimester of pregnancy. The results show no significant differences between socio-demographic groups, suggesting a uniform impact of wildfire exposure. We also examine the role of air pollution induced by wildfires, particularly PM2.5, and find that PM2.5 also contributes to adverse birth outcomes, suggesting that both maternal stress and air pollution determined by wildfires pose dangers to fetal development. The findings underscore the need for public health interventions aimed at mitigating the health effects of wildfires on vulnerable populations, particularly pregnant women.

Flood Impacts on Healthcare Access and Social Vulnerability in Germany

Angelina Evans, Nivedita Sairam,

Presenter: Verena Mühlberger

GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Brandenburg, Germany
Abstract

Flood events often create barriers for people requiring care for chronic illnesses, ongoing treatments, or medications, as flood hazards can increase travel times to hospitals, clinics, and pharmacies. This study aims to identify population groups in Germany that are most affected by disruptions to healthcare access when flooding occurs. Flood and transportation modeling software (Wassmer, 2024) from the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research will be combined with OpenStreetMap data and social indicators to assess healthcare access disruptions modeled by the German Regional Flood Model (RFM) from the GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences (Sairam et al., 2021). By comparing changes in travel times with social determinants of health, the study seeks to determine which communities are at higher risk of losing access to care during floods. Expected outcomes include maps and analyses that reveal patterns of disrupted healthcare access and highlight factors of vulnerability. The findings can support strategies for climate resilience and recovery, helping to avoid or reduce disruptions to healthcare access.

Wassmer, J. (2024). Software: Unveiling hidden risks in healthcare from flood-induced transportation disruption. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13990586>

Sairam, N., Brill, F., Sieg, T., Farrag, M., Kellermann, P., Nguyen, V. D., Lüdtkke, S., Merz, B., Schröter, K., Vorogushyn, S., & Kreibich, H. (2021). Process-based flood risk assessment for Germany. *Earth's Future*, 9, e2021EF002259. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EF002259>

Impact of Heatwaves on Health: A Multicentric Retrospective Observational Study on Morbidity, Hospitalizations, and Mortality Patterns

Tarun Kumar Suvvari¹, Chandra Shekar Kali^{1,2}, Venkataramana Kandi^{1,3}

¹Squad Medicine and Research (SMR), Amadalavalasa, Andhra Pradesh, India. ²Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram, Andhra Pradesh, India. ³Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana, India

Abstract

Background:

Heatwaves are emerging as one of the most serious climate-related health threats in South Asia. Despite frequent and severe heat events, systematic multicentric data quantifying their health burden remain limited. This study aimed to evaluate morbidity and mortality patterns during heatwave periods across diverse climatic regions of India.

Methods:

A retrospective observational study was conducted across four tertiary hospitals from April–June 2025. Data from emergency and inpatient records were extracted for all cases admitted during summer heatwave periods as per Indian Meteorological Department criteria. Demographics, comorbidities, clinical presentation, management, and outcomes were analyzed using multivariate logistic regression to identify predictors of ICU admission and mortality.

Results:

A total of 42 heatwave-related hospitalizations were recorded (mean age 54.2 ± 17.8 years; 61.3% male). The majority were outdoor laborers (46%) or urban poor residents (28%). Dehydration (64%), heat exhaustion (41%), and heatstroke (18%) were the predominant diagnoses.

Overall case fatality was 30.9%, with mortality highest in patients aged > 65 years and those with pre-existing cardiovascular (OR 2.9; 95% CI 2.1–4.0) or chronic kidney disease (OR 3.7; 95% CI 2.4–5.8). ICU admission was required in 57.1% of cases, with peak hospital burden coinciding with maximum daily temperatures > 44 °C.

Conclusions:

This multicentric study highlights the disproportionate health impacts of heatwaves on vulnerable populations in India. Targeted heat action plans, community cooling access, and early warning systems are critical to mitigate preventable morbidity and mortality as climate extremes intensify.

Keywords: Heatwave, Climate Change, Mortality, Morbidity, Public Health, India, Extreme Temperatures

Climatic Drivers of Malaria risk in Children Under Five: A Large-Scale Analysis of individual-level data for 350,000 children in 26 Sub-Saharan African Countries

Manuel Martellini O Nocentini^{1,2}, Shivang Pandey^{1,2}, Leonardo Olivetti^{2,3,4}, Francesco Defilippo⁵, Max Wybrant^{2,6,7}, Koffi Worou^{2,3}, Maurizio Mazzoleni^{1,8}, Eugenia Quiros-Roldan⁹, Pauline Byakika¹⁰, Carlo Torti^{11,12}, Cecilia Magnusson^{1,13}, Antonio Gasparrini¹⁴, Gabriele Messori^{2,3}, Elena Raffetti^{1,2,3,7,15}

¹Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁴Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science (CNDS), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁵Department of Virologia, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e Emilia-Romagna, Brescia, Italy. ⁶Department of Public Health, Environments and Society, Faculty of Public Health and Policy, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ⁷British Heart Foundation Cardiovascular Epidemiology Unit, Department of Public Health and Primary Care, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ⁸Institute for Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands. ⁹Infectious and Tropical Diseases Unit, University of Brescia and ASST Spedali Civili Hospital Brescia, Brescia, Italy. ¹⁰Mbarara University of Science and Technology, Mbarara, Uganda. ¹¹Dipartimento di Sicurezza e Bioetica, Sezione di Malattie Infettive, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Sezione di Malattie Infettive Largo Francesco Vito 1, Rome, Italy. ¹²Dipartimento di Scienze Mediche e Chirurgiche, Fondazione Policlinico Universitario "A. Gemelli" IRCCS, Rome, Italy. ¹³Centre for Epidemiology and Community Medicine, Region Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden. ¹⁴Environment & Health Modelling Laboratory, Department of Public Health Environments and Society, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ¹⁵Victor Phillip Dahdaleh Heart and Lung Research Institute, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom

Abstract

Malaria risk is influenced by climatic conditions, with children under five particularly vulnerable. We investigated associations between climatic factors and malaria risk in 350,000 children aged 5-59 months across sub-Saharan Africa over 18 years.

We included children aged 5-59 months with malaria tests from Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) in 26 sub-Saharan African countries (2006-2023). We linked these data to high-resolution climate exposures: temperature, precipitation, soil moisture, actual evapotranspiration and specific humidity. We fitted mixed-effect logistic regression models incorporating Distributed Lag Non-linear Models (DLNM) over 1-6 month lag for each exposure, controlling for seasonality and long-term trends. We examined effect modification by maternal education, wealth, residence type, water and sanitation, child demographics, insecticide-treated nets (ITN) and household head age.

Malaria prevalence was 19.5%. Malaria risk was highest at 24 °C (OR: 1.45, 95% CI: [1.36, 1.54]), driven by short-term exposures (1-2 months), and declined at higher temperatures. Precipitation increased risk up to ~ 120 mm (1.10, [1.07, 1.12]). Heavier rainfall reduced risk, particularly at short- to medium-term lags (1-4 months). Soil moisture presented increasing

risk up to ~80 mm (1.11, [1.08, 1.14]), plateauing at higher levels. Evapotranspiration showed a strong, near-linear positive association. Higher specific humidity (>14 g/kg) presented a lower risk, reaching a 45% reduction at 17 g/kg (0.55, [0.49, 0.61]), with strongest protective effects at short-term lags (1-2 months). Elevated risk at lower temperatures was particularly evident among children not sleeping under ITN-nets.

The findings provide evidence to guide targeted interventions and early-warning strategies for vulnerable populations.

Impact of temperature extremes on school going children's health in Sweden

Shivang Pandey^{1,2}, Leonardo Olivetti^{3,4,2}, Isabel Johanna Walter^{1,2}, Cecilia Magnusson^{1,5}, Maurizio Mazzoleni^{6,1}, Gabriele Messori^{7,3,2}, Elena Raffetti^{1,2,3,8,9}

¹Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Stockholm Län, Sweden.

²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Uppsala Län, Sweden. ³Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Uppsala Län, Sweden. ⁴Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science (CNDS), Uppsala, Uppsala Län, Sweden. ⁵Centre for Epidemiology and Community Medicine, Region Stockholm, Stockholm, Stockholm Län, Sweden.

⁶Institute for Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Sweden.

⁷Department of Meteorology and Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Stockholm Län, Sweden. ⁸British Heart Foundation Cardiovascular Epidemiology Unit, Department of Public Health and Primary Care, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ⁹Victor Phillip Dahdaleh Heart and Lung Research Institute, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom

Abstract

Climate change is driving substantial shifts in temperature and weather patterns, with major consequences for population health. Europe is warming at roughly twice the global rate, and Swedish summers are now marked by record heatwaves. School-age children (6-18 years) are particularly vulnerable to temperature-related health risks due to physiological and behavioral factors. Despite this, there is limited large-scale evidence, especially on prolonged and delayed effects of temperature extremes on children health. We aimed to study the effect of air temperature on hospitalization risk over 3 decades.

This national cohort study included all school aged children in Sweden from 1987 to 2018. We linked hospitalization data and socioeconomic data from LISA to high-resolution climate data. The primary outcome was all-cause admissions. We applied a case time series design with distributed lag non-linear models (DLNM) to estimate both immediate and delayed temperature effects over a 21-day lag, and stratified analyses by demographic, socioeconomic, and policy period.

More than 3.7 million children contributed to the follow-up, with 1.38 million hospitalizations. We observed a J-shaped association between temperature and hospital admission risk. cold had an effect at the lowest extremes, admissions rose sharply above the cohort median temperature, peaking at 25-30°C. Stratified analyses found intensified heat effects for childrens living in southern Sweden.

Ambient temperature, especially heat extremes, was associated with increased hospitalization risk. This underscores the need for targeted climate adaptation policies in schools and public health, and for further work on causal pathways, including cause-specific admissions.

The impact of compound hydroclimate extremes on population health

Elena Raffetti^{1,2,3,4,5}, Manuel Martellini O Nocentini^{1,5}, Maurizio Mazzoleni⁶, Richard Leeding^{4,5}, Gabriele Messori^{4,5}

¹Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ²British Heart Foundation Cardiovascular Epidemiology Unit, Department of Public Health and Primary Care, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ³Victor Phillip Dahdaleh Heart and Lung Research Institute, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom. ⁴Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁵Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁶Institute for Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Abstract

Under climate change, the frequency, intensity, and duration of climate extremes are increasing globally, exacerbating health risks. These events rarely occur in isolation; they increasingly manifest as compound events, meaning “consecutive and/or partially overlapping” extremes. Compound climatic extremes amplify risks, exceeding the sum of individual hazards and interacting with physical, environmental, and social processes. Yet these impacts remain understudied.

This study aims to characterise the mortality burden associated with compound hydroclimate extremes, specifically flood–cold spell, flood–heatwave, and drought–heatwave, and to assess whether impacts exceed those expected from single hazards.

We use weekly all-cause mortality at NUTS-3 resolution across Europe from 2000. Compound events are identified by temporal co-occurrence. For flood–cold spell and flood–heatwave, we consider overlapping periods and allow a one-month post-flood window to account for delayed effects. Thresholds for heatwaves and cold spells use area- and season-specific percentiles to reflect local climatology. We use a traditional Interrupted Time Series design to quantify the mortality burden attributable to compound health impacts of compound events. Each compound event represents a discrete “interruption” in the mortality time series. Attributable numbers will be calculated by multiplying observed cases during event weeks by the estimated attributable fraction ($AF = 1 - \exp(-\beta x)$), where βx is the regression coefficient corresponding to the intervention variable.

This study will provide the first comparable, population-scale estimates of mortality associated with exposure to compound hydroclimate extremes across Europe. The findings will inform multi-hazard early-warning systems, healthcare-service planning, and adaptation strategies.

Degrees of inequality: How educational attainment shapes mortality associated to non-optimal temperatures in different provinces of Belgium

Emmanuelle Kuijt

FWO (Fonds voor Wetenschap), Brussels, Belgium. VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Brussels, Belgium. UCLouvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

Abstract

This study investigates how age and educational attainment influence temperature-related mortality among the elderly across Belgian provinces, addressing a critical gap in understanding climate-related health inequalities. While climate change poses a major global health threat, evidence on socioeconomic and demographic disparities in temperature-mortality associations remains limited. Educational attainment shapes vulnerability through multiple pathways: enhanced cognitive skills improve risk assessment and adaptation, and higher socioeconomic status enables protective investments. Prior research suggests that lower-educated populations may face greater risks, though findings vary across contexts.

Using Belgian mortality data from 2000–2019 and a two-stage meta-regression framework, we examined temperature-mortality relationships across two separate analyses focusing on individuals aged 65+ across all 11 provinces. The first analysis stratified populations by age groups, while the second distinguished between low, secondary, and superior education levels as a proxy for socioeconomic status.

Results revealed strong age gradients, with adults aged 85+ experiencing substantially higher temperature-related mortality than younger elderly groups. The education analysis showed that lower-educated populations faced elevated risks, though effect sizes varied across provinces. Cold-related mortality predominated across all demographic and socioeconomic groups. Consistent regional differences emerged across both analyses, suggesting persistent geographic vulnerabilities independent of age or socioeconomic composition.

We are currently continuing this research to obtain more granular district-level results, which will allow us to identify specific meta-predictors—including demographic, socioeconomic, and environmental factors—that lead to higher relative risks of temperature-related mortality at the local level.

Temporal structure of the impact of meteorological conditions on pneumonia hospitalizations in Germany

Saeed A. Khan¹, Max Kutzinski^{2,3}, Thomas Brenner¹, Barbara C. Weckler^{2,3}, Christoph Reudenbach¹, Jörg Bendix¹, Jan Rupp^{4,5}, Martin Witzernath^{4,6}, Gernot Rohde^{4,7,8}, Mathias W. Pletz^{4,9,10}, Wilhelm Bertrams², Bernd Schmeck^{2,3,10}

¹Department of Geography, Marburg University, Marburg, Germany. ²Institute for Lung Research, German Center for Lung Research (DZL), Universities of Giessen and Marburg Lung Centre, Marburg University, Marburg, Germany. ³Department of Medicine, Pulmonary and Critical Care Medicine, University Medical Center Marburg, Marburg University, German Center for Lung Research (DZL), Marburg, Germany. ⁴CAPNETZ STIFTUNG, Hannover, Germany. ⁵Infectious Diseases Clinic and Institute of Medical Microbiology, University Hospital Schleswig-Holstein, Lübeck, Germany.

⁶Department of Infectious Diseases, Respiratory Medicine and Critical Care, Charité, Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Corporate Member of Freie Universität Berlin and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin, Germany; German Center for Lung Research (DZL), Berlin, Germany. ⁷Department of Respiratory, Intensive Care and Sleep Medicine, Marburg University, Marburg, Germany.

⁸Biomedical Research in End-stage and Obstructive Lung Disease Hannover (BREATH), Member of the German Center for Lung Research (DZL), Hannover, Germany. ⁹Institute for Infectious Diseases and Infection Control and Center for Sepsis Care and Control, Jena University Hospital and Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena, Jena, Germany. ¹⁰German Center for Infection Research (DZIF), the Center for Synthetic Microbiology (SYNMIKRO), Marburg, Germany, and the Institute for Lung Health (ILH), Giessen, Germany

Abstract

The risk of pneumonia-related hospitalizations increases under adverse impact of meteorological conditions. Despite growing evidence on the relationship between environmental factors and community acquired pneumonia (CAP), the temporal dynamics of these exposures remain poorly understood. Our study aims to understand the effects of meteorological conditions on CAP hospitalizations in Germany, characterizing the influence, timing and duration of these effects.

We used the CAPNETZ cohort covering pneumonia hospitalizations across 22 hospitals in Germany. Daily meteorological (air pressure, relative humidity, cloud cover, temperature, precipitation) were used. Delayed effects were captured using a custom weighted lag-response function over a 60-days period. To find out the temporal structure, we use logistic regression approach for daily CAP hospitalizations. Splines were applied to capture the non-linearity of the exposure effect. Model was adjusted for influenza, weekdays and cities. Optimal weighting parameters (μ , σ) were identified through model fitting to find minimum AIC across a grid of μ (1–20) \times σ (1–20). Heat maps are used to depict the peak (μ) and spread (σ) of the effect across lag days. Furthermore, odd ratios are calculated to find out the influence of variables on CAP.

Results show that hospitalization numbers react with a varying time delay on weather conditions. Minimum temperature showed immediate effect, while cloud cover exhibited

more intermediate effect. Humidity and precipitation showed delayed effects. Overall weather effects vary in timing and duration, influencing CAP hospitalizations from days to weeks. These findings will contribute to improving early warning systems and public health measures.

Predicting mortality during heatwaves through the application of machine learning on large register data

Klas Ytterbrink Nordenskiöld^{1,2}, Axel Carlsson^{1,2}, Caroline Wachtler^{1,2}, Christofer Åström³

¹Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society, Division of Family Medicine and Primary Care, Karolinska Institutet, Huddinge, Sweden. ²Academic Primary Care Center, Stockholm, Sweden.

³Department of Public Health and Clinical Medicine, Section of Sustainable Health, Umeå, Sweden

Abstract

Background

With rising global temperatures, the number of individuals exposed to heatwaves (HWs) is increasing. Although older individuals have a higher risk of mortality during HWs, who is most vulnerable remain unclear. This study aims to develop a machine learning-based prediction model for death during HW using healthcare data, to enable preventive interventions.

Methods

We included diagnoses, number of healthcare visits, and dispensed medications for all individuals ³ 65 years of age in the Stockholm Region (2010 to 2024). HWs were classified by the average of the maximum daily temperature of 4 consecutive days at Observatorielunden, as moderate (above the 95th percentile), or intense (above the 99th percentile). Optimal temperature (OT) was defined as the 85th–90th percentile. Stochastic Gradient Boosting models, stratified by nursing home status, were used to predict death during HWs compared to OT.

Results

274 days were classified as moderate, and 55 as intense HW. Mean daily mortality ranged from 32.7 during OT to 39.8 during intense HW, totalling 18 240 deaths. Model AUC-ROC varied from 0.56 (community dwellers, moderate HW) to 0.67 (nursing home residents, intense HW). Platelet inhibitors, B12/folic acid, doctors' visits (months 1–12), paracetamol, age, diuretics, beta-blockers, and ACE/ARB were the most influential variables. All variables exhibited non-linear ORME–exposure relationships, with ORME values ranging from 0.3 to 5.2.

Conclusion

Machine learning identified novel associations between medication dosages and healthcare interactions related to the risk of death during HW. These findings add knowledge to the ongoing work with preventive strategies concerning HWs.

Exploring perceptions of heat risk and user-experience of a heat- Early Warning System (EWS) app for pregnant women and mothers in Sweden: A mixed-methods study

Veronika Tirado^{1,2}, Clara Heil³, Chuansi Gao³, Veronique Filippi⁴, Koen Vander Sanden⁵, Boris Kingma⁵, Ijeoma Solarin⁶, Stanley Luchters^{7,8,9}, Olof Stephansson¹, Claudia Hanson^{1,4}

¹Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Swedish centre for impacts of climate extremes (climes) Stockholm, Sweden. ³Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ⁴London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ⁵TNO, Soesterberg, Netherlands. ⁶University of Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. ⁷Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ⁸Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research, Harare, Zimbabwe. ⁹Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine, Liverpool, United Kingdom

Abstract

Background: Rising temperatures poses a growing health risks, especially among pregnant women and infants. Extreme heat significantly increases the risk of adverse health outcomes, such as dehydration, cardiovascular strain, and impaired infant thermoregulation. This study evaluated the usability and relevance of a digital Early Warning System (EWS) app designed for pregnant and postpartum women, exploring heat risk perceptions and user experiences and recommendations for app improvement.

Methods: A convergent mixed-methods design. An online survey, targeting pregnant women and new mothers, was conducted across Sweden (June-August 2025), and in-depth interviews were held with women (August-November 2025). Quantitative data were analysed descriptively, and qualitative data were examined through content analysis. Integration of both datasets allowed comparison and contextual interpretation of user experience and behavioural responses for heat warning messages.

Results: Among 883 women who registered and intended to use the app, 25% completed it in full. Most participants (79%) were aged 30 years or older, and slightly more than half (53%) were not married. Fourteen women from different regions in Sweden participated in interviews. Preliminary findings suggest that women valued the app and were willing to recommend it, especially during summer months. Users expressed a need for more educational content beyond warning and preventive health messages, including greater recognition of UV light exposure, wind, and perceived ("feels-like") temperature.

Conclusion: The EWS app was positively received but underused. Enhancing usability of the EWS app, expanding educational content, and increasing awareness of heat-related risks may improve preparedness among expectant and new parents.

A time series analysis of temperature and mortality in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina

Lorissa Farrell¹, [Devon Nenon](#)², Malcolm Mistry²

¹London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ²Environment & Health Modelling (EHM) Lab, Department of Public Health, Environment & Society, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

Although it is well known that heat and cold are risk factors for human mortality, to our knowledge, no studies so far have assessed the impacts of temperature on daily mortality in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Previous studies have documented that this association varies substantially between countries, making it difficult to assume that the results of previous research can be extrapolated to unstudied areas. We aimed to quantify the temperature mortality association in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. We collected data on daily mean temperature and non-violent mortality for the 10 cantons in the Federation. We fitted quasi-Poisson time-series regressions for each canton, controlling for day of week and seasonality. We estimated temperature mortality associations with distributed lag non-linear models, then pooled the results in a multivariate meta-analysis. Lastly, we calculated attributable deaths for both heat and cold. The exposure-response functions displayed a J-shaped temperature-mortality association, as is commonly seen in the literature. We estimated relative risks of 1.80 (95% confidence interval 1.40 – 2.20) and 1.26 (1.04 – 1.15) for the maximum values of cold (-20 °C) and heat (31 °C), respectively. We estimated that 2,824 (944 – 4,453) deaths can be attributed to non-optimal temperature, annually, in FBiH, mostly attributable to cold. In conclusion, both heat and cold were associated with marked increases in mortality in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, though the cold effects seem to dominate the burden of mortality. These results can contribute to climate projection assessments and inform future adaptation priorities in the Federation.

Identifying and Modelling Pathways between Flood and Health in Vietnam

Verena Mühlberger, Nivedita Sairam

GFZ, Potsdam, Brandenburg, Germany

Abstract

Post-disaster risk assessment in the context of flood risk shows that flood impacts (direct and indirect) cannot be estimated by solely using physical flood characteristics but rather that flood damage depends on socioeconomic attributes and human behavior.

Multivariable models integrating flood damage into combined flood-economic models have proved to be reliable in estimating the monetary loss of flood events. However, the variables linking floods and health are not fully clear and integrated into impact prediction models.

To close this gap, a longitudinal structured household survey of Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), Vietnam, conducted in 2020 and in 2023, is used as a case study to map the links between physical characteristics of floods, regional socioeconomic factors, and physical and mental health. HCMC faces recurring seasonal flooding between June and November. In the survey respondents were asked to report their experience during flood events. In total, 559 participants answered the questionnaire in both 2020 and 2023 and described up to three flood events. The aim of the study is to identify potential connections between morbidity and flood characteristics and/or household characteristics. Results indicate, that physical flood characteristics can be linked with the rate of disease burden. Changes in flood frequency could be determining factors in changes in flood risk perception and result in changed morbidity.

The results of the empirical data analysis will be presented along with its relevance to the development of multivariable impact models that describe the pathways between flood experiences and health outcomes in HCMC, Vietnam.

Impact: data, modelling, and overviews

Towards improved modelling of windstorm damage risk through Impact Model calibration

Aditya Narayan Mishra^{1, 4}, Gabriele Messori^{1, 4}, Lukas Riedel², Athul R Satheesh³, Alexandre M Ramos³, Joaquim Pinto³

¹Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Institute for Environmental Decisions, ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland. ³Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research Troposphere Research (IMKTRO), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany, ⁴Swedish center for impacts of climate extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Winter windstorms rank as one of Europe's deadliest and most damaging natural disasters. To model the impacts of these windstorms, surface wind data can be incorporated into climate risk models to derive estimates of natural hazard-related impacts on natural or socio-economic systems. In CLIMADA, risk from a natural hazard can be modelled as the convolution between three components - hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. The vulnerability component links the hazard and exposure components to give total impact that can be approximated through functional relationships called vulnerability curves (or impact functions in CLIMADA). Advancing the science of impact estimation from windstorms is imperative for the mitigation and management of changing climate risks, and this relies on the appropriate calibration of the impact function. To this end, in this study, we calibrate a popular impact function from Schwierz et al. (2010) primarily using insurance loss data from PERILS (proprietary). Therein, we discuss the uncertainties associated with the use of different cost functions and optimisation techniques in the calibration process. Results indicate substantial differences between the calibrated vulnerability curves and highlight the importance of the choice of these methods. Uncertainty analysis and validation of calibration results are conducted to assess robustness and generalisation of the calibrated curves. The study helps better understand modelling uncertainty and supports the development of more reliable tools for climate risk assessment and adaptation.

Shape-constrained exposure-response functions for modelling the impacts of climate extremes in small populations

Devon Nenon¹, Antonio Gasparrini¹, Zaid Chalabi², Pierre Masselot¹

¹Environment & Health Modelling (EHM) Lab, Department of Public Health, Environment & Society, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom. ²UCL Institute for Environmental Design and Engineering, The Bartlett School of Environment, Energy and Resources, University College London, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

Accurate estimates of the exposure response functions for climate-related exposures and health are necessary to perform health impact assessments and calculate attributable deaths due to climate extremes. To estimate these functions, epidemiologists rely on complex models that typically require large population samples to get good risk estimates. Therefore, it can be difficult to estimate the exposure response function in smaller populations with low outcome counts, such as rural areas, or subgroups, such as children. We propose a novel regression modelling method that can improve estimation of this function by adding shape constraints to the nonlinear term in the model. We illustrate this method through a simple example of temperature and mortality with a small-area dataset from Italy. In the example, we demonstrate how the exposure response function is estimated, and show that the new modelling method can overcome the instability that is often observed with traditional methods. The use of this shape-constrained method can improve our understanding of the impacts of climate extremes on under-researched populations and help us assess and project the health burdens due to these extremes. Applicable to a variety of environmental exposures, this method has wide reaching applications to advance our understanding of the health effects of our changing climate.

Compounding impacts of climate change and urbanisation on water-energy-food Nexus in global south countries

Taiwo Temitope Bamgboye, Tamara Avellan, Bjorn Klove, Ali Torabi Haghighi

University of Oulu, Oulu, North of Finland, Finland

Abstract

As climate change and urbanisation continue to reshape global resource demand and supply, Global South countries face compounded challenges in managing the interconnected water, energy, and food (WEF) nexus. This systematic review assessed the current state of research on their combined impact across Africa, Asia, Latin America, and the Caribbean, analysing 75 peer-reviewed articles published between 2011 and 2023. Key findings include the following:

- (1) No literature was found analysing the WEF Nexus, climate change, and urbanisation. This gap suggests that policymakers and resource managers may lack full understanding of their combined impact on WEF insecurities.
- (2) Climate change primarily affects resource supply through biophysical impacts, while urbanisation through socioeconomic impacts influences resource demand and consumption patterns. Together, these two disrupt the balance between supply and demand, increasing insecurities across the WEF elements.
- (3) In addition, governance issues such as weak systems, siloed government structures, and low political will hinder effective WEF nexus management.
- (4) Qualitative methods were the most prominent in studying both problems, suggesting a focus on contextual understanding.
- (5) Distinctively, no existing solutions simultaneously address the impact of climate change and urbanisation on the WEF nexus.

The proposed solutions to these impacts tend to target one driver in isolation, such as renewable energy for climate mitigation, or urban agriculture for urban resilience. This review highlights the need to address the compounding impact of these problems to ensure an equilibrium between supply and demand in the face of global environmental changes.

Quantifying the rarity behind European loss-causing floods: a precipitation-frequency framework

Alok Samantaray^{1,2}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2}

¹Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

Abstract

Flooding causes billions of dollars in losses every year, and these impacts are likely to rise with more intense precipitation and growing exposure. Linking observed flood losses to the rarity of the triggering event is crucial for understanding current risk and for testing whether damaging events are truly exceptional or simply highly exposed. We propose a general framework to connect loss-causing floods in Europe to precipitation frequency using existing event catalogues and gridded climate datasets. The workflow begins with reported flood events (date, type, affected areas, losses), builds a spatial footprint (administrative union and, where available, a basin-refined version), and then extracts precipitation metrics from observation-based grids. These metrics are converted to return periods, allowing events from different years and regions to be placed on a common frequency scale. The framework is modular: datasets, footprints and duration windows can be swapped, and it is well suited to comparisons with insurance data. It highlights how clearer attribution of losses can support more targeted flood-risk management.

A social science typology of climate change storylines

Charlotte Maybom^{1,2}, Emily Boyd^{1,2}

¹Lund University, Lund, Sweden, ²Swedish center for impacts of climate extremes (climes), Lund, Sweden

Abstract

Climate change is increasingly encountered through extreme events that appear as brute physical facts. Yet such events become intelligible through stories. They are narrated as crises, risks, injustices, or failures of preparedness and woven into accounts of resilience, adaptation and responsibility. These storylines do not merely describe climate change; they actively construct what it is, who it concerns, and what can be done. This article develops a social-scientific framework for analysing and co-creating climate storylines, arguing that they are foundational to how climate change is understood, governed, and lived.

The article conceptualises storylines as social practices through which shared realities are produced. Narratives are not neutral representations; they organise meaning, shape identities, and delimit horizons of action. Storylines stabilise interpretations of change and events while rendering others marginal or unthinkable. They distribute agency and responsibility and produce subjects.

Reviewing dominant storylines in climate science the article shows how they organise climate change as a particular kind of problem. Despite their growing prominence, storylines are treated as neutral, factual devices for organising physical processes under uncertainty. This leaves a critical gap: storylines are not only representations of events but narrative constructions that actively produce meaning, social roles, and political horizons.

The article proposes a typology of four ideal-typical climate storylines: managerial-risk, resilience, crisis-emergency, and justice-political. The typology functions as an analytical heuristic, demonstrating that climate change is not a single object awaiting interpretation but a multiplicity produced through narrative, opening space for alternative imaginaries and political possibilities in a changing world.

Evaluating Microclimatic Impacts of Citywide Rooftop Photovoltaic Deployment Using WRF and a Multilayer Urban Canopy Model: Evidence from Sendai, Japan

Vinayak Bhanage, Han Soo Lee

Hiroshima University, Hiroshima, Hiroshima, Japan

Abstract

This study examines microclimatic responses to city-scale rooftop photovoltaic (PV) deployment across different coverage ratios in Sendai, Japan, using dynamic downscaling simulations. Five numerical experiments, viz. exp_ctrl, exp_25, exp_50, exp_75, and exp_100 representing rooftop photovoltaic (PV) coverage from 0% to 100%, were conducted at a 400 m spatial resolution. Spatiotemporal variations in surface air temperature, specific humidity, planetary boundary layer height (PBLH), and surface energy balance were assessed by comparing the control simulation with the four PV deployment scenarios. The results show that PV roof installation produces a discernible cooling effect, with mean daytime (nighttime) temperature reductions of 0.05°C (0.07°C), 0.06°C (0.11°C), 0.059°C (0.14°C), and 0.03°C (0.14°C) in exp_25, exp_50, exp_75, and exp_100, respectively. Higher coverage scenarios (exp_75 and exp_100) also reduced specific humidity for 70.8% and 62% time of the day. Increased PV deployment decreased ground and sensible heat fluxes, whereas latent heat flux changes remained inferior. All PV scenarios resulted in lower mean PBLH compared with the exp_ctrl. Electricity production increased linearly with higher PV coverage, with compact urban forms generating the most energy per unit area due to dense rooftop availability. These findings offer valuable insights for urban planners and policymakers designing effective PV deployment strategies.

Wikimpacts 1.0: A new global climate impact database based on automated information extraction from Wikipedia

Ni Li^{1,2}, Wim Thiery³, Shorouq Zahra^{4,5}, Mariana Madruga de Brito⁶, Koffi Worou^{7,5}, Murathan Kurfali^{4,5}, Seppe Lampe¹, Paul Munoz¹, Clare Flynn^{5,7}, Camila Trigo¹, Joakim Nivre^{4,5,8}, Jakob Zscheischler^{2,9,10}, Gabriele Messori^{5,7,11}

¹Department of Water and Climate, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussel, Belgium. ²Department of Hydro Sciences, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany. ³Department of Water and Climate, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussel, Sweden. ⁴RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁵Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁶Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research — UFZ, Leipzig, Germany. ⁷Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁸Department of Linguistics and Philology, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁹Department of Compound Environmental Risks, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research — UFZ, Leipzig, Germany. ¹⁰Center for Scalable Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence (ScaDS.AI), Leipzig, Germany. ¹¹Department of Meteorology and Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Extreme climate events pose serious threats to human society and ecosystems. Measuring their impacts remains a crucial challenge scientifically. Although data linking climate hazards to socio-economic effects are crucial, their public availability is still relatively sparse. Existing open databases such as the EM-DAT and DesInventar Sendai offer some impact data on climate extremes, but impact data on climate extremes also appear in newspapers, reports, and online sources like Wikipedia.

We introduce Wikimpacts 1.0, a comprehensive global database on climate impacts developed using natural language processing techniques. This database utilizes the GPT4o large language model for extracting information, following document selection, post-processing, and data consolidation. In this release, impact data for each event is recorded at three levels: event, national, and sub-national. Categories include the number of deaths, injuries, homelessness, displacements, affected individuals, damaged buildings, and insured or total economic damages. This dataset encompasses 2,928 events from 1034 to 2024, featuring 20,186 national and 36,394 sub-national data entries. Comparison with manually annotated data from 156 events shows that the Wikimpacts database is highly accurate in the event level for time, location, deaths, and economic damage, though details on injuries, affected individuals, homelessness, displacements, and building damage are slightly less precise. An analysis from 1900 to 2024 demonstrates that sub-national data provides more comprehensive coverage of tropical and extratropical storms, and wildfires than EM-DAT. Our study emphasizes the potential of natural language processing in creating open databases with reliable information on climate event impacts.

Challenges and Opportunities for Understanding Societal Impacts of Climate Extremes

Gabriele Messori^{1,2}, Emily Boyd^{3,4}, Joakim Nivre^{5,2}, Elena Raffetti^{6,2}

¹Dept. of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ³Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ⁴Swedish Centre for Impacts of Climate Extremes (climes), Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ⁵Department of Linguistics and Philology, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁶Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Climate extremes exact a heavy toll on society, with adverse impacts unequally distributed across populations. Here, we outline key challenges and opportunities for advancing research on understanding societal impacts of climate extremes. We identify three key challenges relating to data, process understanding and projections. Specifically: limited availability and quality of impact data, difficulties in elucidating the genesis of impacts and lack of reliable impact projections. We argue that there is a window of opportunity to address several dimensions of these challenges and we highlight recent examples and ongoing developments that hold transformative potential for the research field. Examples include: Leveraging large language models for impact data extraction, tailoring data-driven methods to elucidate how intersecting vulnerabilities shape differential impacts, and developing semi-quantitative storyline approaches to project future impacts. We conclude with a call to build momentum by fostering interdisciplinary research and collaboration across sectors.

Energy system impacts

Storylines of future summertime renewable electricity droughts in Europe under climate warming and rising air conditioning demand

Yu Meng^{1,2}, Johannes Schmidt³, Jakob Zscheischler^{1,2}, Emanuele Bevacqua¹

¹Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Leipzig, Germany. ²TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany. ³University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

Abstract

Decarbonised power systems increasingly rely on renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, to mitigate global warming. However, little is known about summertime renewable electricity droughts (REDs) — periods characterised by high residual load (unmet demand by renewable sources), particularly as hotter summers drive an increase in air conditioning (AC) installation. We propose a framework to study how future AC installation and climate warming jointly impact summertime REDs. Specifically, by using hourly renewable electricity output from the atlite/PyPSA-Eur workflow driven by ERA5 reanalyses and nudged AWI climate simulations, we explore how observed REDs during 2017–2023 may unfold under different warming and AC installation storyline. First, we will construct future hourly electricity demand that incorporates projected AC installation and higher temperatures. Second, we will identify historical REDs and then link these events to compound weather-driven extremes of renewable supply and electricity demand. Finally, we will investigate how historical summer REDs are expected to evolve with future AC installation under +2 °C, +3 °C, and +4 °C global warming levels. Our framework will inform on the drivers of summertime REDs under present and future conditions, providing insights for enhancing the resilience of Europe's power system in a warmer, AC-dominated future.

Investigation of meteorological conditions leading to extreme variable renewable energy shortage events in Germany

Onno Nennecke, Peter Pflaederer, Sebastian Sippel

Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany

Abstract

The pursuit of a climate-neutral future accelerates the expansion of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power. One issue with these technologies is their dependence on favourable weather conditions. Especially critical for grid stability are periods of extremely low renewable energy production and a coinciding high demand, so-called variable renewable energy shortages (VRES). VRES are commonly studied with observational data, which only represent one possible realisation of internal climate variability and are therefore not sufficient to adequately study extreme VRES. In this study, we validate a simple energy model and apply it to 1000 years of climate data from different Earth System Models (ESMs) and ERA5 reanalysis data for Germany. The model outputs are analysed with regard to seasonality, event magnitude, behaviour, duration, composition, and large-scale weather regimes. It is found that VRES events exhibit a pronounced seasonality, with both occurrence and magnitude peaking in mid-winter. Variability in wind speed over Germany is identified as the main driver of these events, while fluctuations in incoming solar radiation contribute only marginally during the winter months. Weather pattern clustering further supports previous findings, confirming the dominant influence of blocked circulation regimes in the formation of VRES over Germany. The most extreme fixed-length VRES derived from ESM data are up to 6.5 % (1-day events) and 8.8 % (7-day events) more severe than those identified from reanalysis data. These results provide robust metrics for energy system planners and contribute to a deeper understanding of the climatic drivers behind low-renewable periods.

Power consumption and carbon footprint of open warming beds and closed incubators

Marie-Louise Herrmann^{1,2}, Sven Martin³, Ulrich Thome², Benjamin Ackermann²

¹University Hospital Eppendorf; Department of Childrens' psychiatry, Hamburg, Germany.

²Department of Neonatology, Children's University Hospital, Leipzig, Germany. ³Innovation Center Computer Assisted Surgery (ICCAS); Institut of the faculty of medicine, University Leipzig, Leipzig, Germany

Abstract

Background:

Pre-heated incubators and warming beds are essential for neonatal emergency admissions but contribute to the energy demand of neonatal-intensive-care-units (NICUs). Given the healthcare sector's 4.4% share of global CO₂ emissions, optimizing pre-heating parameters looks promising for saving both environmental and financial costs.

Methods:

Electricity consumption of warming beds (Babytherm 8010, Dräger) and incubators (Giraffe Omnibed, GE Healthcare) was recorded during standby, heating, and maintenance under varying temperature settings and two cover types. Annual electricity use, costs (0.24 €/kWh), and CO₂ emissions (226 g/kWh) were calculated.

Results:

Closed pre-heated incubators consumed 962 kWh/year at 30°C (217 kg CO₂) and 1,494 kWh/year at 37°C (338 kg CO₂). Heating from 34°C to 37°C reduced the warm-up time to 22 minutes, compared to 51 minutes at 30°C. Active heating processes required the most energy (equivalent to 1,925 kWh/year, 435 kg CO₂). Open warming beds exhibited higher variability, ranging from 131 kWh/year (0% heater) to 4,610 kWh/year (100% heater), equivalent to 30–1,042 kg CO₂. The heater's output and the incubator's set temperature were the primary drivers of consumption, while ambient temperature had no significant effect. Incubator covers lowered energy use; a thicker cover reduced power consumption by 12.5% (3.8–24.7%), reflective covers achieved 20.2% (10.1–30.7%) savings at 37°C.

Conclusion:

The energy demand of NICU thermal devices varies with settings. Reducing pre-heating temperatures and using incubator covers can lower electricity use, CO₂ emissions, and costs while maintaining clinical readiness.

Climate attribution, forecasting, monitoring, and projections

AI-Driven Monitoring and Forecasting of Marine Mucilage: A Climate Impact Case from the Marmara Sea

Ece İldem¹, Ahmet Zelka², Arya Zeynep Mete³

¹Bogazici University, İstanbul, Turkey. ²Uskudar University, İstanbul, Turkey. ³Hacettepe University, Ankara, Turkey

Abstract

Marine mucilage (“sea snot”) events increasingly affect European seas, threatening marine ecosystems, tourism, and industrial operations such as fisheries and coastal energy production. The 2021 Marmara Sea crisis, in one of Europe’s most eutrophic and climatically sensitive semi-enclosed basins, revealed how mucilage can blanket ports and coasts, underscoring the urgent need for reliable detection and forecasting systems. We propose to develop and evaluate AI-based approaches for mucilage detection and early prediction under limited labels and imperfect satellite coverage. Using multispectral satellite imagery and environmental reanalysis data from ERA5, we will establish realistic baselines and explore spatiotemporal representations that can identify mucilage-like water states without dense annotation. We will systematically compare complementary AI techniques—a supervised U-Net for pixel-wise detection, Segment Anything (SAM) for semi-automatic mask generation, and multiple graph neural network architectures (GraphSAGE, GAT, GraphConv) combined with Deep Graph Infomax—to determine the most robust representations for detecting and forecasting mucilage formation. Our dataset will be enhanced with additional satellite sources, including PlanetScope, Landsat, and Copernicus imagery accessible via Google Earth Engine, to improve spatial and temporal coverage. Proxy explainability using Random Forest feature importance will link spectral and environmental drivers to observed phenomena. The best-performing components will inform a transparent, scalable forecasting pipeline integrating physical and environmental predictors. This framework, initially applied to the Marmara Sea, will be extendable to other semi-enclosed basins such as the Adriatic and Aegean, supporting European efforts toward coastal resilience and the Digital Twin Ocean initiative.

Assessing Power Network Resilience to Catastrophic Medicanes: The Case of Ianos (2020) in Present and Future Climate

Emmanouil Flaounas^{1,2}, Zacharias fasoulakis³, Dimitrios V. Bilonis³, Dimitrios Vamvatsikos³

¹ETH, Zurich, Switzerland. ²HCMR, Athens, Greece. ³Institute of Steel Structures, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

Abstract

Catastrophic Medicanes—Mediterranean hurricanes—are among the most destructive environmental hazards in the region. Despite their smaller size, relative to tropical cyclones, they can reach comparable intensities, producing severe windstorms that inflict substantial socioeconomic impacts, especially on critical infrastructure.

This study focuses on the case of Medicane Ianos (2020), which caused widespread power outages across western Greece. Our aim is to evaluate the resilience of the electrical power network with emphasis on damage to distribution poles. High-resolution atmospheric modeling is used to simulate Ianos' wind-gust footprint while stochastic risk methods are used to assess structural vulnerability and cascading effects on the grid. To probe climate-change implications, we conduct a sensitivity experiment in which sea-surface temperatures are increased, thereby emulating a warmer Mediterranean Sea. The resulting changes in wind intensity and spatial damage probabilities enable us to quantify Ianos' potential future impacts under warmer SSTs.

Using the Greek power grid as a case study, we demonstrate that Medicanes—projected to intensify with SST warming—pose an increasing risks to energy infrastructure. The work proposes a transferable framework for assessing power-network vulnerability to extreme wind events, offering insights applicable to other Mediterranean countries confronting the growing threat of Medicanes.

Analyzing Rainfall Patterns and Intensity in Bangkok Using GNSS-Derived PWV and Meteorological Observations

Chokchai Trakolkul¹, Chaiyut Charoenphon², Supattra Visessri², Chalermchon Satirapod²

¹Rajamangala University of Technology Suvarnabhumi, Phra Nakhon Si Ayutthaya, Thailand.

²Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

Abstract

Short-term rainfall prediction in tropical megacities remains a challenge due to highly variable atmospheric conditions. This study investigates the potential of GNSS-derived precipitable water vapor (PWV) as a predictor of rainfall occurrence, intensity, and duration in the Bangkok Metropolitan Region, Thailand. High-resolution GNSS data from five Continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS) collected between 2019 and 2023 were processed using GipsyX to estimate PWV from tropospheric delays. These PWV estimates were integrated with rainfall, relative humidity, and weather radar data processed through LROSE software. Results show that elevated PWV consistently precedes rainfall events by several hours, with higher PWV values associated with more intense and longer-duration precipitation. Radar imagery confirmed strong spatial and temporal alignment between convective systems and PWV signals. The integration of GNSS-derived PWV with meteorological and radar observations offers a robust framework for short-term rainfall forecasting in complex urban settings. This approach enhances understanding of atmospheric moisture dynamics and provides practical support for weather forecasting, flood preparedness, and water resource management in tropical cities.

Sensitivity of Extreme Precipitation to Warming in a Global Storm-Resolving Model

Malena Contizanetti^{1,2}, Alejandro Uribe^{1,2}, Thorsten Mauritsen^{1,2}, Frida Bender^{1,2}

¹Stockholm University, Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden

Abstract

Understanding changes in extreme precipitation under global warming is crucial for assessing climate hazards. However, projections from global climate models exhibit significant uncertainties, particularly in the tropics. This study investigates the response of extreme precipitation to warming using a high-resolution, global storm-resolving model that eliminates the need for convective parameterization.

In the extratropics, the storm-resolving simulations show increases following thermodynamic expectation, consistent with global climate model simulations. In contrast, the tropics exhibit a lower response, whereas global models simulate stronger increases. A physical scaling analysis reveals that the zonal mean sensitivity closely follows the thermodynamic contribution, while regional deviations are linked to a weakening of the dynamical component over tropical land. These results highlight the importance of explicitly resolving convective dynamics to reduce uncertainty in projections of extreme precipitation.

Evaluating ERA5 Precipitable Water Vapor and Its Application to Drought Monitoring through the SPCI over Thailand

Sothyda Khor, Piyatida Ruangrassamee, Pongsak Suttinon, Chalermchon Satirapod, Supattra Visessri
Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

Abstract

Precipitable Water Vapor (PWV) is the total atmospheric moisture in a vertical column. It is an important variable for understanding hydrometeorological processes, storm development, and drought dynamics. This study compares PWV derived from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA5 reanalysis with ground-based Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) observations to evaluate spatial and temporal consistency across Thailand. Bias and root mean square error (RMSE) are used to assess the accuracy of ERA5 daily PWV against GNSS observations across six geographical regions. The comparison shows strong agreement, with bias values generally within -2 to 2 mm/day and average RMSE below 3 mm/day. Since ERA5 provides long-term, spatially continuous reanalysis data, it is further used to compute a Standardized Precipitation Conversion Index (SPCI) by integrating ERA5 PWV and precipitation to characterize drought variability over 3-, 6-, and 12-month periods from 1985 to 2025. The SPCI assesses drought based on the concept of precipitation efficiency, describing how effectively atmospheric moisture is converted into rainfall. The 3-month SPCI reflects strong seasonal fluctuations linked to the monsoon cycle, while the 6- and 12-month scales demonstrate persistent drought patterns. Regionally averaged results show that Northeastern region, which is predominantly low-lying with undulations and hills, experiences more frequent and prolonged droughts, while Western coastal region shows shorter and less severe droughts under the influence of monsoonal moisture. These results highlight the potential of PWV as a simple and effective atmospheric indicator for regional drought monitoring, offering a complementary approach to conventional precipitation-based assessments.

Projected Changes in Extreme Precipitation from CMIP6 in the Mae Klong River Basin, Thailand

Winai Chaowiwat¹, Teerawat Ram-Indra², [Piyatida Ruangrassamee](#)²

¹Hydro-Informatics Institute (Public Organization), Bangkok, Thailand. ²Department of Water Resources Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

Abstract

Increasing frequency and intensity of extreme rainfall events threaten flood resilience in Thailand, including the Mae Klong River Basin. In this study, four extreme precipitation indices for flood, namely PRCPTOT, R35mm, R95p, and Rx5day were calculated for the period 1985–2014 using the observed daily rainfall data from the Thai Meteorological Department and bias-corrected rainfall using Scaled Distribution Mapping (SDM) with 5 km x 5 km from three selected CMIP6 general circulation models (GCMs), namely BCC-CSM2-MR, CESM2, and CanESM5. The projected variability of these indices was analyzed under two Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5, for the period 2016–2050. All three bias-corrected GCMs exhibit spatial patterns of the extreme precipitation indices that are consistent with observations. The projected temporal variability and spatial distribution of the indices differ across the three models. For CanESM5 under SSP5-8.5, the period 2041–2050 demonstrates the highest variability in PRCPTOT, with average values ranging from approximately 1,300 to 2,000 mm. Observed data indicate that R35mm ranges from 8 to 10 days. All three GCMs project an increasing long-term trend in R35mm, particularly under the high-emission SSP5-8.5 scenario. Nearly the entire Mae Klong River Basin exhibits R95p value greater than 200 mm. When comparing the three GCMs, BCC-CSM2-MR shows the highest variability and demonstrates a larger increase in R95p than the other two GCMs. For CESM2 under the SSP3-7.0 scenario, the average Rx5day values range from approximately 120 to 180 mm. Under SSP5-8.5, the periods 2031–2035 and 2041–2050 exhibit the highest variability.

Consecutive hot and dry events: a compound event attribution study

Cristina Deidda¹, Wim Thiery¹, Patrick Willems², Jakob Zscheischler³

¹Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Bruxelles, Belgium. ²KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium. ³Helmholtz, Helmholtz, Germany

Abstract

In recent years, we have been experiencing an increasing frequency of heatwaves and drought events, with growing socioeconomic and environmental consequences. The occurrence of these extremes in consecutive years amplifies their impacts, leading to greater economic losses and longer recovery times across multiple sectors, from transport infrastructure to agriculture. Consecutive droughts can significantly affect vegetation growth and place additional stress on agricultural systems. Compound hot and dry events may also trigger cascading effects, such as the exceptionally low water levels observed in the Rhine River in 2018, which disrupted navigation.

In this study, we explore the use of univariate, bivariate and temporal compound attribution to show how much climate change is influencing the probability not only of single events, but compound and consecutive events. In particular, we propose a case study to investigate how the probability of consecutive extremes is changing in a warmer climate. The aim of the study, is to highlight the urgency of putting attention not only on the impact of the single events but of the larger impacts that can be caused by the always more frequent consecutive extremes, and consecutive co-occurrent extremes. Finally, we discuss some of possible implications of these findings for policymakers and practitioners involved in climate adaptation and risk management.

Uncertainty Quantification of the regional temperature consequences of a large AMOC decrease

Jonathan Rosser, David Stainforth

London School of Economics, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

We use data from a range of modelling approaches (including CMIP, ClimTip, and NAHosMIP) to quantify the uncertainty in the regional mean surface temperature impacts of a large AMOC decrease in the 21st Century. ESMs/GCMs primarily show gradual AMOC slowdown in the 21st and early 22nd century. Other approaches suggest that a “tipping point” may be present which could lead to faster decline in the AMOC during this period. This study aims to estimate the impacts of this decline and the range of possible outcomes which can be inferred from the ensemble of climate models and approaches. Changes in temperature and AMOC will be analysed under a range of forcing scenarios including SSP scenarios for global warming, freshwater hosing scenarios, and ClimTip runs showing a combination of global warming and freshwater hosing. The relationships between AMOC change, global mean surface temperature and regional mean surface temperature will be described, as well as our uncertainty in these values based on the model ensembles. These relationships can be used to estimate responses to alternative trajectories and changes. Annual mean regional/national temperatures will be presented under a range of potential AMOC trajectories and the potential range of outcomes will be estimated for each scenario and location. These methods can be extended to both seasonal temperature and annual precipitation, and the data produced is highly consequential for economic impact assessments and adaptation planning.

Building Climate Resilience through Urban Climate Analysis. Case study: Galanta (Slovakia)

Veronika Beranová¹, Norbert Polčák^{1,2}, Igor Matečný¹

¹Comenius University in Bratislava, Department of Physical Geography and Geoinformatics, Bratislava, Slovakia. ²Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute, Bratislava, Slovakia

Abstract

Urban climate research is increasingly relevant as climate change intensifies the frequency and severity of extreme thermal events, posing serious risks to urban populations. This study characterizes the urban climate of Galanta, Slovakia, using a network of 19 thermal dataloggers recording at 10-minute intervals from July to October 2025. Twelve sensors were placed in urban areas and seven in suburban areas. To contextualize the measurements, synoptic meteorological analyses were conducted to identify prevailing atmospheric conditions. The study focused on evaluating the intensity and temporal variability of the urban heat island (UHI) effect across different urban morphologies. Results show that densely built-up urban areas with limited vegetation exhibited temperatures approximately 2.3 °C higher than suburban areas. Morning minimum temperatures revealed even greater differences, reaching up to 3 °C. These variations are influenced by geomorphological factors and the presence of water elements. The findings highlight that UHI intensity in Galanta is closely linked to urban structure and local climatic conditions. This knowledge provides a foundation for climate-sensitive urban planning, particularly in Central European cities with similar environmental and morphological characteristics.

Acknowledgement: This research is the result of the implementation of project no. 09104-03-V02-00002, funded by the allocation of the European Recovery and Resilience Facility for Slovakia.

Future Water Dynamics of the Nitra River Basin under Climate Change and Land Use Scenarios

Omar Cenobio-Cruz¹, Majid Niazkar^{2,3}, Róbert Blaško⁴, Jeremy Pal^{2,3}, Giuliano Di Baldassarre¹

¹Department of Earth Sciences, Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Risk Assessment and Adaptation Strategy division, Euro-Mediterranean Center of Climate Change, Venice, Italy. ³Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Venice, Italy. ⁴Slovak Environment Agency, Climate Change Adaptation Centre, Banská Bystrica, Slovakia

Abstract

Understanding the response of river discharge to changes in climate and land use is crucial for the management of water resources. This study examines seasonal discharge variability in the Nitra river basin, Slovakia, under different conditions. First, we simulated river flows for the period 1995–2023 using the semi-distributed Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE) model fed with historical time series of precipitation and temperature data. To capture spatial heterogeneity, the basin was divided into four sub-basins. To simulate future discharge, we compared 38 bias-adjusted Euro-CORDEX CMIP5 climate models with three scenarios (rcp2.6, rcp4.5, and rcp8.5) with historical baselines to identify extreme wet, extreme dry, and average climate conditions. Moreover, we run two land-use change scenarios, representing a 15% increase in natural (forest) or agricultural areas, to investigate the hydrological response within the basin.

Our model shows that increasing natural land cover leads to lower discharge values across all seasons compared to more agricultural land. River discharge variability is especially significant in winter for extreme wet and in autumn for extreme dry conditions. These findings underscore the influence of climate variability and land use on discharge dynamics, which can be useful for developing adaptive water management strategies.

Groundwater on the Edge: How Climate Warming and Urban Growth are Reshaping Bihar's Water Future

Suraj Kumar, Abhishek Kumar Choudhary, Aditya Kumar Singh, Amit Kumar, Nityanand Singh Maurya

National Institute of Technology, Patna, Bihar, India

Abstract

Groundwater, a vital freshwater resource, faces increasing threats from climate change and human activities. This study examines rainfall, temperature, and groundwater level changes from 1996 to 2020 in Bhagalpur and Khagaria districts, Bihar, India. Using remote sensing, GIS, and non-parametric statistical methods (Mann–Kendall and Sen's slope tests), results show a significant decline in annual rainfall (-25.05 mm/year) and a rise in mean temperature ($+0.021^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$), signalling regional warming aligned with global trends. Pre-monsoon groundwater levels steadily decreased due to reduced recharge and increased evapotranspiration. Land use analysis via Google Earth Engine revealed a 15% loss of agricultural land and a 9% increase in built-up areas, reducing infiltration and altering hydrological balance. Findings highlight how climate variability and land use changes exacerbate groundwater depletion in semi-urban and agricultural zones. The study emphasizes the urgent need for integrated climate–groundwater management approaches, including rainwater harvesting, artificial recharge, and sustainable irrigation. The methodology provides a replicable framework for groundwater climate impact assessment in data-scarce regions, supporting UN Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 13. This research contributes to global climate resilience knowledge, stressing the importance of local hydro-climatic monitoring for adaptive groundwater governance in a changing climate.

Characterization of aviation turbulence associated with Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones (Medicanes)

Marialuisa Simone^{1,2}, Sergio Servidio², Tommaso Alberti³

¹University of Trento, Trento, Italy. ²University of Calabria, Rende, Italy. ³Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Rome, Italy

Abstract

The Mediterranean is a climatologically sensitive region due to its transitional position between the arid subtropics and the wetter mid-latitudes. In recent years, Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones, or *Medicanes*, have gained increasing attention. These rare baroclinic cyclones that evolve in their mature stage into vortices with structural characteristics similar to tropical cyclones. Although they occur only a few times per decade, Medicanes can produce severe socio-economic impacts through intense precipitation, strong winds, and coastal flooding.

Observational and modeling studies indicate that rising sea surface temperatures may affect Mediane evolution, potentially leading to stronger storms. Understanding their dynamics is therefore important not only for climatology but also for operational sectors such as aviation, which are directly exposed to atmospheric hazards. While the surface impacts of Medicanes have been widely studied, their influence on upper-tropospheric conditions, particularly turbulence relevant to aviation, remains poorly documented. In-flight encounters with turbulent eddies represent a major aviation hazard, often resulting in injuries, aircraft damage, and economic losses to airlines.

This study presents the first systematic investigation of aviation-scale turbulence associated with eleven Medicanes that occurred between 1996 and 2023. The analysis is based on three empirical turbulence diagnostics (TI1, TI2, and TI3), commonly used to identify synoptic-scale patterns conducive to shear-induced turbulence. These indices, derived from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, are computed for each Mediane across the 900–200 hPa layer and as a function of radial distance from the cyclone center, with the aim of assessing how turbulence conditions within Medicanes evolve in a changing climate.

Assessing the real-world economic value of weather forecasts under compounding extremes

Leonardo Olivetti^{1,2,3}, Gabriele Messori^{1,2,4}, Paolo Avner^{5,6}, Stéphane Hallegatte⁵

¹Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden. ²Swedish center for impacts of climate extremes (climes), Uppsala, Sweden. ³CNDS, Uppsala, Sweden. ⁴Department of Meteorology, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁵World Bank Group, Washington, United States. ⁶GFDRR (Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery), Washington, United States

Abstract

Recent advances in data-driven weather forecasting have led to AI-based models that often match or surpass the predictive skill of traditional physical models. However, direct comparison between these approaches remains difficult, as they tend to differ in their strengths and weaknesses. As a result, their usefulness in practice can vary substantially across applications. Despite this, most existing studies compare forecasting systems primarily in terms of meteorological skill, paying limited attention to their value for real-world decision-making.

In this work, we address this gap by introducing an application-dependent framework to assess the practical value of both AI and physics-based weather forecasts. Building on the classical concept of relative economic value, we extend the framework to better capture realistic decision contexts. In particular, we allow for varying cost–loss ratios to represent different forecast and protection costs, and we incorporate flexible penalty functions to account for compounding losses from repeated forecast misses as well as reduced user trust resulting from repeated false alarms.

We showcase the framework using several case studies focused on cities facing significant economic risks from weather-related hazards. The results show that forecast value depends not only on forecast accuracy and costs, but also on how losses from repeated errors are modelled. Lastly, we argue for the importance of evaluating practical value alongside meteorological skill when developing and comparing weather forecasting models.